

Safe-, sUstainable- and R recyclable-by design P olymeric systems
A guidance towardS next generation of plastics

Start date of the project: 01/06/2022
Duration 42 months

Deliverable D4.3.

HAZARD ASSESSMENT STRATEGY

Work Package	4	Development and use of SSRbD Assessment tools, methods and guidance
WP Leader		Sébastien Artous, CEA
Lead beneficiary		Yvonne Staal, RIVM
Contributing beneficiaries		RIVM, UGA, LEITAT
Reviewer		S. ARTOUS (CEA), V. CAZZAGON (LEITAT), S. CLAVAGUERA (CEA)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101057901.

Nature of the deliverable		
R	Report, document	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DMP	Data Management Plan	<input type="checkbox"/>

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SEN	Sensitive, Restricted to a group specified by the consortium under conditions set out in grant agreement	<input type="checkbox"/>

Quality procedure			
Contractual delivery date	31/05/2025		
Actual delivery date	30/05/2025		
Version accepted by the Steering Board	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Report uploaded via Research Participant Portal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Acknowledgements

The SURPASS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101057901. This publication reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Version history

Version	Date	Partner – Author	Email	Comments ¹
	17-04-2025	Yvonne C.M. Staal	Yvonne.Staal@rivm.nl	
	17-04-2025	Marion Berenguer	Marion.Berenguer@cea.fr	
	17-04-2025	Thierry Douki	Thierry.Douki@cea.fr	
	17-04-2025	Ana Maria Candalija Iserte	amcandalija@leitat.org	
	17-04-2025	Ruben Martinez	rmartinez@leitat.org	
	17-04-2025	M. Bouwmeester	Manon.Bouwmeester@rivm.nl	
	17-04-2025	Sebastiaan L. Zoutendijk	Bas.Zoutendijk@rivm.nl	
	17-04-2025	Emiel Rorije	Emiel.Rorije@rivm.nl	
	30-04-2025	Lya G. Soeteman-Hernandez	Lya.Hernandez@rivm.nl	
	29-05-2025	CEA - S. Clavaguera	simon.clavaguera@cea.fr	Final version

¹ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

Executive summary

This report presents the hazard assessments performed in the frame of the SSRbD SURPASS approach. It complements reports D4.2 on release and exposure scenarios, D4.4 on hazard assessment using QSAR modelling and reports D4.5 and D4.6 on environmental assessment by LCA and economic assessment by LCC.

The EC Joint Research Centre (JRC) safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) framework consists of an iterative process of (re-)design and safety and sustainability assessment phases along the innovation process. The (re-)design phase consists of the application of guiding principles to steer the development process. The goal, the scope and the system boundaries – which will frame the assessment of the chemical or material – are defined in this phase. The assessment phase comprises of: risk assessment (hazard, workers exposure during production, exposure during use) and environmental life-cycle assessment. The assessments can be carried out either on newly developed chemicals and/or materials, or on existing chemicals and/or materials to improve their safety and sustainability performance during production, use and/or end-of-life.

Following the risk assessment component of the JRC framework, hazard the of ingredients was assessed using a stepwise approach. Starting with the collection of existing data, which was lacking for most substances, we performed modelling of the Quantitative Structure Activity Relation (QSAR) (described in D4.4) and in vitro and ecotoxicity testing (described in D4.3). Based on hazard endpoints, assays, cell models and animal models were selected. Furthermore, substances were selected which differed in the reference production route and the SSRbD alternative route. A further selection was made by limiting the number of concentrations tested in each assay, to obtain hazard information on the most relevant substances. Some ingredients could not be tested in the selected in vitro assays, for example the pellets that are used in CS3. In such cases we tested an alternative, in this case the migration samples.

Case Study 1

CS1 addresses the building sector. In this CS, polyurethane-based window frames are intended to replace those made of PVC, wood or aluminium. Three groups of substances were identified, the polyols, catalysts and disulfide. Polyol I is the fossil based reference product, whereas the combination of Polyols A, B, C and D are used for the bio-based SSRbD alternative product. Catalysts or disulfide are used to recycle the product.

The polyols used in the bio-based route were found to be more hazardous in the assays conducted. Effects on cytotoxicity, oxidative stress, cytokine secretion and aquatoxic effects were found. No endocrine disruption potential was detected.

The hazard potential of the catalysts differed between the substances, whereas Bi-Cat resulted in the most responses, THEED was the least responsive substance. Some more hazards were identified for disulfide, among which a potential endocrine disrupting effect.

Case Study 2

CS2 focuses on the railway sector. The aim of this CS is to develop a composite material that is lighter than metal and can be used in structural applications, thus enabling a significant reduction in vehicle weight and energy consumption over its lifetime. Also for this case study, three groups of substances were identified: the hardeners, the A-parts and the leachates. MDA is used as a reference hardener, whereas 4-AFD and 2-AFD are alternative hardeners. The A-parts consisted of a resin and a flame retardant. As these substances could not be tested independently, they were tested in combination.

Of the hardeners tested, MDA was least cytotoxic, but did induce effects on other parameters, like oxidative stress and cytokine release. All A-parts were potentially genotoxic. Also effects on oxidative stress and cytokine release were observed.

The leachates were not tested in all assays, therefore not all hazard information is available. Effects were found on genotoxicity, corresponding to the effects also observed for A-parts and, for Leach-TCPP on endocrine disruption potential.

Case Study 3

CS3 focuses on the packaging sector. CS3 is aimed at processing polyolefin multi-nanolayer (MNL) films for food packaging, barrier layer (EVOH or PA) with less compatibilizer. Instead of the ingredients, migration samples were assessed for hazard. None of the migration samples induced any response in the assays conducted. Toxicity testing was limited due to toxicity observed by the solvent. Likely, quantities of migrated substances in the samples are very low, too low to induce any effect at the low concentrations tested and/or in comparison to the effects of the solvents used. Therefore, no conclusions can be drawn on a potential hazard of the substances migrating from the MultiNanoLayered films.

Conclusion

To facilitate interpretation of the results and to compare products and ingredients with respect to their hazard, hazard scores were calculated based on the above described results. Interpretation of scoring results should, however, be done with caution. Evaluation of the results, underlying the score, should always be done before drawing conclusions on hazard. This scoring system is integrated into a global SSRbD scoring system, see deliverable D5.1.

The results of hazard testing can be used to provide guidance on the replacement of a hazardous ingredient by a less hazardous alternative. It is important to note that the absence or presence of hazards identified by the assays conducted are only indicative of a potential hazard and can be used to guide further hazard assessment.

List of acronyms

Abbreviation	Full name
53BP1	p53-binding protein 1
ALI	Air-Liquid-Interface
AR	Androgen receptor
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BDS	BioDectectionSystems
BMC	Bench mark concentration
BSA	Bovine serum albumin
CALUX	Chemically Activated LUciferase eXpression
CED	Critical effect dose
CES	Critical effect size
CM-H2DCFDA	5(and-6)-chloromethyl-2'7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate, acetyl ester
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CS	Case Study
DiP	Difference in Performance
DMEM	Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DPBS	Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffered Saline
dTHP-1	Differentiated THP-1 cells
EC ₂₀	Concentration producing 20% of the maximal response
EC ₅₀	Concentration producing 50% of the maximal response
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
ED	Endocrine disruption
ELISA	Enzyme-Linked ImmunoSorbent Assay
equimolar	Same dose level
equitoxic	Dose level inducing a similar level of cytotoxicity
Er α	Estrogen receptor alpha
EU	European Union
EU-CSS	EU - Chemical Strategy for Sustainability
FCS	Fetal Calf serum
H295R	H295R Steroidogenesis Assay
HPLC-MS/MS	High Performance Liquid Chromatography associated with electrospray tandem Mass Spectrometry
IC ₅₀	Concentration that inhibits a biological process by 50%
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LDH	Assay to determine cytotoxicity based on membrane integrity, lactate dehydrogenase

LPS	Lypopolysaccharide
MNL	MultiNanoLayered
NC	Negative control, non-exposed cells
NEAA	Non-Essential Amino Acids
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PBS	Phosphate Buffered Saline
PC	Positive control, substance that should give a response in a specific assay
PMA	Phorbol-12-myristate-13-acetate
PU	Polyurethane
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
QCM	Quartz Crystal Microbalance
QSAR	Quantitative Structure–Activity Relation
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
RPMI	Roswell Park Memorial Institute
SC	Solvent control, response of the solvent only, to control for potential effects of the solvent
SSbD	Safe-and-sustainable-by-design
SSIA	Safe(r) and Sustainable Innovation Approach
SSRbD	Safe-, Sustainable-, and Recyclable-by-Design
TEER	Trans-epithelial electrical resistance
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WST-1	Assay to determine cytotoxicity based on mitochondrial activity, named after a specific tetrazolium salt
ZFET	Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity

List of substances and their identification

Below the list of substances assessed in this deliverable. Blue indicates the reference substance in a specific substance category.

Case Study 1	Substance name:	SURPASS Code:	CAS No(s):	Abbreviation:
Catalysts	Bismuth neodecanoate	CS1_16	34364-26-6	Bi-Cat
	Cystamine	CS1_26	56-17-7	Cystamine
	N,N,N',N'-Tétrakis-(2-hydroxyéthyl)-éthylènediamine	CS1_18	140-07-8	THEED
Disulfide	2-hydroxyethyl disulfide	CS1_08	1892-29-1	Disulfide
Polyols	Polyol I	CS1_05	-	Polyol I
	Polyol A	CS1_01	-	Polyol A
	Polyol B	CS1_02	-	Polyol B
	Polyol C	CS1_03	-	Polyol C
	Polyol D	CS1_04	-	Polyol D

Case Study 2	Substance name:	SURPASS Code:	CAS No(s):	Abbreviation:
A-Parts	A-Part with TCPP	CS2_20	1675-54-3 / 2425-79-8 / 13674-84-5	AP-CL
	A-Part w/o flame retardant	CS2_01	1675-54-3 / 2425-79-8	AP1
	A-Part with DOPO modified epoxy resin	CS2_17	1675-54-3 / 2425-79-8 / 300371-38-4 / 9003-36-5	AP2
	A-Part with Phosphorous modified epoxy resin	CS2_18	1675-54-3 / 2425-79-8 / NA	AP3
	A-Part with Aluminium diethyl phosphinate	CS2_19	1675-54-3 / 2425-79-8 / 225789-38-8	AP4
Hardeners	4,4'-Diaminodiphenylmethane	CS2_14	101-77-9	MDA
	4-Aminophenyl disulfide	CS2_02	722-27-0	4-AFD
	2-Aminophenyl disulfide	CS2_15	1141-88-4	2-AFD
Leachates	Leachate from composite with TCPP as reference - concentrated	CS2_40	-	Leach-TCPP
	Leachate from composite with SP1 (w/o flame retardant) - concentrated	CS2_36	-	Leach-SP1
	Leachate from composite with SP2 - concentrated	CS2_37	-	Leach-SP2
	Leachate from composite with SP3 - concentrated	CS2_38	-	Leach-SP3
	Leachate from composite with SP4 - concentrated	CS2_39	-	Leach-SP4

Case Study 3	Substance name:	SURPASS Code:	CAS No(s):	Abbreviation:
Leachates in Acetic Acid	leachate Reference PO/PA with compatibilizer 11 layers S0018-43 B - acetic acid 3%	CS3_08	-	PO/PA/compat 11 B
	leachate PE/PA 65 layers with compatibilizer S0018-53 B - acetic acid 3%	CS3_14	-	PE/compat/PA 65 B
	leachate PE/EVOH 129 layers without compatibilizer S0018-76 B - acetic acid 3%	CS3_10	-	PE/EVOH 129 B
	leachate PE/EVOH 129 layers with compatibilizer S0018-78 B - acetic acid 3%	CS3_12	-	PE/compat/EVOH 129 B
Leachates in Ethanol	leachate Reference PO/PA with compatibilizer 11 layers S0018-43 E95 - Ethanol95	CS3_07	-	PO/PA/compat 11 E95
	leachate PE/PA 65 layers with compatibilizer S0018-53 E95 - Ethanol95	CS3_13	-	PE/compat/PA 65 E95
	leachate PE/EVOH 129 layers without compatibilizer S0018-76 E95 - Ethanol95	CS3_09	-	PE/EVOH 129 E95
	leachate PE/EVOH 129 layers with compatibilizer S0018-78 E95 - Ethanol95	CS3_11	-	PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95

Table of contents

1.	Introduction.....	15
1.1	Background	15
1.2	Sources of hazard data.....	16
1.2.1	ECHA database.....	17
1.2.2	QSAR modelling	17
1.2.3	<i>In vitro</i> testing.....	17
1.3	Selection of substances and concentrations	18
1.3.1	General approach	18
1.3.2	Case study specific choices in testing of substances	18
2	Selected models	20
2.1	Models representing exposure routes.....	20
2.2	Models for fresh water toxicity and endocrine disruption.....	22
3	Selected <i>in vitro</i> assays.....	22
3.1	Cytotoxicity assessment.....	24
3.1.1	WST-1 assay	24
3.1.2	LDH assay.....	24
3.1.3	Alamar Blue assay.....	26
3.2	Oxidative stress assessment	27
3.2.1	CM-H ₂ DCFDA assay.....	27
3.2.2	Cellular ROS Assay kit	28
3.2.3	Protein carbonylation	29
3.3	Epigenetics	30
3.3.1	Quantification of methylated cytosine in total DNA using HPLC-MS	30
3.4	Inflammation.....	31
3.4.1	Cytokine assessment of inhalation model.....	31
3.4.2	Cytokine assessment of dermal and oral model	32

3.5	Genotoxicity.....	32
3.5.1	53BP1 assay for double strand break assessment	32
3.5.2	Comet assay for DNA damage assessment	34
3.6	Endocrine disruption.....	36
3.6.1	ER α and AR assessment	36
3.6.2	Transgenic zebrafish line for thyroid disruption	38
3.6.3	H295R Steroidogenesis assay	38
3.7	Aquatic toxicity	39
3.7.1	<i>Daphnia Magna</i>	39
3.7.2	Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET)	40
3.8	Statistical analysis	41
4	Results CS1	43
4.1	CS1 SSbD routes and tested substances	43
4.2	CS1 Polyols	44
4.2.1	ECHA data	44
4.2.2	General human health.....	47
4.2.3	Genotoxicity.....	56
4.2.4	Endocrine disruption	58
4.2.5	Aquatic toxicity	60
4.2.6	Short summary	62
4.3	CS1 Catalysts	62
4.3.1	ECHA data	62
4.3.2	General human health.....	64
4.3.3	Genotoxicity.....	72
4.3.4	Endocrine disruption	73
4.3.5	Aquatic toxicity	75
4.3.6	Short summary	76

4.4	CS1 Disulfide	77
4.4.1	ECHA data	77
4.4.2	General human health.....	80
4.4.3	Genotoxicity.....	86
4.4.4	Endocrine disruption	87
4.4.5	Aquatic toxicity	89
4.4.6	Short summary	90
5	Results CS2	90
5.1	CS2 SSbD routes and tested substances	90
5.2	CS2 Hardeners.....	92
5.2.1	ECHA data	93
5.2.2	General human health.....	94
5.2.3	Genotoxicity.....	103
5.2.4	Endocrine disruption	104
5.2.5	Aquatic toxicity	107
5.2.6	Short summary	109
5.3	CS2 A-Parts.....	109
5.3.1	ECHA data	110
5.3.2	General human health.....	113
5.3.3	Genotoxicity.....	120
5.3.4	Endocrine disruption	121
5.3.5	Aquatic toxicity	122
5.3.6	Short summary	124
5.4	CS2 Leachates from composites	124
5.4.1	ECHA data	124
5.4.2	General human health.....	124
5.4.3	Genotoxicity.....	127

5.4.4	Endocrine disruption	128
5.4.5	Aquatic toxicity	131
5.4.6	Short summary	132
6	Results CS3	132
6.1	CS3 SSbD routes	132
6.2	CS3 Migration samples.....	132
6.2.1	ECHA data	133
6.2.2	General human health.....	135
6.2.3	Genotoxicity.....	142
6.2.4	Endocrine disruption	144
6.2.5	Aquatic toxicity	145
6.2.6	Short summary	146
7	Hazard scoring.....	146
7.1	Purpose and strategy	146
7.2	Hazard scoring steps	147
7.2.1	Data for hazard scoring	147
7.2.2	Setting a response for a no effect level and a low effect level.....	148
7.2.3	Evaluation of statistical significance.....	150
7.2.4	Normalization of the data	150
7.2.5	Calculation of absolute differences	151
7.2.6	Averaging of assay outcomes measuring the same health hazard	152
7.2.7	Thresholds for substance hazard.....	152
7.2.8	Combining ingredient scores into a performance score and their thresholds.....	153
7.2.9	Scoring considerations.....	153
7.3	CS1	154
7.3.1	Hazard scores.....	154
7.3.2	Differences in Performance (DiP)	157

7.4	CS2	159
7.4.1	Hazard scores.....	159
7.4.2	Differences in Performance (DiP)	164
7.5	CS3	167
8	Deviations from the workplan.....	168
9	Conclusions and perspectives	168
10	References.....	169
11	Appendices	170
11.1	CS1 – Polyols	175
11.1.1	General human health	175
11.1.2	Genotoxicity	178
11.1.3	Endocrine disruption	180
11.2	CS1 – Catalysts	180
11.2.1	General human health	180
11.2.2	Genotoxicity	183
11.2.3	Endocrine disruption	184
11.3	CS1 – Disulfide (2-hydroxyethyl disulfide)	184
11.3.1	General human health	184
11.3.2	Genotoxicity	185
11.3.3	Endocrine disruption	186
11.4	CS2 - Hardeners.....	186
11.4.1	General human health	186
11.4.2	Genotoxicity	189
11.4.3	Endocrine disruption	190
11.5	CS2 – A-Parts.....	191
11.5.1	General human health	191
11.5.2	Genotoxicity	193
11.5.3	Endocrine disruption	194

11.6	CS2 – Leachates from composites	194
11.6.1	General human health	194
11.6.2	Genotoxicity	196
11.6.3	Endocrine disruption	197
11.7	CS3 – Migration samples.....	197
11.7.1	General human health	197
11.7.2	Genotoxicity	200
11.7.3	Endocrine disruption	202

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The safe-and-sustainable-by-design (SSbD) concept integrates functionality with safety and sustainability aspects at an early phase of the innovation and product development process in order to minimize potential hazard(s) and/or exposure and to maximize sustainability. The H2020 project SURPASS aims to develop a Safe-, Sustainable-, and Recyclable-by-Design (SSRbD) assessment and guidance dedicated to plastic materials. SURPASS focuses on 3 case studies: 1) Building sector: New recyclable-by-design bio-sourced polyurethane resins (PU) with enhanced vitrimer properties to replace polyvinyl chloride (PVC) for window frames, 2) Transport sector: New fire-resistant recyclable epoxy-vitrimer based composites integrating non-releasable fire-retardancy moieties, as alternative to metal for the train structure, and 3) Packaging sector: MultiNanoLayered (MNL) films optimizing their composition and compatibilizer content to make films efficient and recyclable, replacing current multi-layers films that today face uncertainty in recycling with respect to partially challenging designs and compositions, or lack of sorting and dedicated processing. In line with the SSbD framework from the EU Joint Research Centre (JRC), we have developed an SSRbD strategy that considers exposure and release, hazard and life-cycle assessment and costing, taking into account the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the development stage of each case study. The focus of the current work is to develop a hazard assessment strategy in an SSRbD context allowing integration of hazard evaluation during the development process.

The SSbD concept is described in the EU - Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (EU-CSS). JRC has developed a framework for SSbD criteria where an integrated and iterative two-phase approach is recommended consisting of: i) a (re)-design phase in which guiding principles are proposed and ii) a step-wise hierarchical approach to address chemical safety, direct toxicological/ecotoxicological impact, and aspects of environmental sustainability (Caldeira, 2022). A need for a mindset change, to ensure that newly developed materials combine functionality with safety and sustainability from the innovation phase, is also taken into account by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) through the Safe(r) and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA) (OECD, 2022). These approaches from JRC and OECD form the basis for the integrated approach developed in SURPASS, together with the CEN 1325 (CEN 2014) and ISO 15686-5 standards.

The focus of hazard assessment in SURPASS is mainly on step 1 of the framework proposed by JRC. Together with D4.2 and D4.4, this work falls under steps 1, 2 and 3 of the framework (Figure 1.1-1). Hazard evaluation in the SSRbD context is applied to three selected case studies.

Figure 1.1-1: Iterative approach of SSbD, as proposed by JRC (European Commission: Joint Research Centre, Abbate, E., Garmendia Aguirre, I., Bracalente, G., Mancini, L. et al., *Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials – Methodological guidance*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/28450>)

1.2 Sources of hazard data

For hazard evaluation, different sources of hazard data were used, the main ones being the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) database, Quantitative Structure–Activity Relation (QSAR) modelling and *in vitro* testing. Ideally, these steps follow a tiered approach, parallel to the increasing TRL of the product development process. Existing hazard information was collected in an early stage of the project to allow feedback on potential hazards to the case study teams. Subsequent steps, namely QSAR modelling and *in vitro* testing, were conducted in parallel. A schematic overview of the approach is shown in Figure 1.2-1.

Figure 1.2-1: Hazard assessment approach followed in the SURPASS project. The focus is on the green part, whereas in collaboration with D4.2 and D4.3 the orange parts are addressed for specific questions and case studies. D4.4 addresses steps 5, 5a and 7 of the diagram. A more detailed explanation of the diagram can be found in D4.3.

1.2.1 ECHA database

Information on human hazard, environmental hazard and physical chemical hazards of all substances of each of the SURPASS case studies was searched on the ECHA database (<https://echa.europa.eu/information-on-chemicals>). Information on classification and labelling was collected in tables and are presented in the results section of this deliverable.

1.2.2 QSAR modelling

QSAR modelling focussed on environmental hazards. More details on the approach and results of QSAR modelling are described in D4.4.

1.2.3 *In vitro* testing

Early in the development process, hazard assessment was performed using *in vitro* methods considering dermal, oral and inhalation exposure routes and focused on the most important hazard endpoints: cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, inflammatory response, oxidative stress, epigenetic changes, endocrine disruption and acute aquatic toxicity. Dermal, oral and respiratory cell models were used to assess cytotoxicity, cytokine production as a measure for inflammatory response, oxidative stress, genotoxicity (oral and dermal only) and epigenetic changes (oral only). Endocrine disruption is exposure route independent and was assessed with specific assays. Acute aquatic toxicity was assessed as an indicator for fresh water ecotoxicity. Specific assays were selected for combinations of cell

models and parameters, based on their applicability in the context and the experience with the assays in the laboratories.

1.3 Selection of substances and concentrations

1.3.1 General approach

As SSRbD requires a pragmatic approach, choices were made on the substances and number of concentrations to test.

Only those substances were included that differed between the production routes. If a substance is used both in the reference production process and in the SSRbD alternative route, it will have no relative impact on hazard evaluation. Nevertheless, hazard assessment of such substances could be important for avoiding ingredients with undesirable hazard properties, such as genotoxicity. In our approach hazard flags of substances in both the reference and the alternative route were not identified (only exception is the diisocyanate in CS1).

Generally, in hazard assessment, a full dose response curve is made by assessment of the hazard at a range of concentrations to allow calculation of a relative response value, like a 50% effect concentration. This requires testing many concentrations of each substance in each assay, which was not feasible for two main reasons. Firstly, many substances were only available in limited quantities, this is specifically the case for the CS3 migration samples. Secondly, in a low Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the production process, screening on potential hazard properties may already provide sufficient information to decide to continue or not. Full dose-response analysis, (even) with in vitro assays, requires substantial efforts, which could be a next step in hazard assessment in an SSRbD context. Therefore, our approach can be considered a hazard screening, based on which a full hazard assessment can be conducted as part of steps 2 and 3 of the JRC framework.

Therefore, for each substance, a maximum of two concentrations were tested in each cell model and assay. These concentrations were selected in a way that allows comparison between the reference product and the SSRbD alternative product. One concentration was selected at 80% viability and the other being at the same concentration for both the alternative and reference substances. For the zebrafish model a different approach was used due to practical reason. In short, the no observed effect level was determined using the zebrafish embryo toxicity test. This concentration was tested for thyroid disruption in the transgenic line. Upon a positive effect, two additional concentrations were tested, where applicable to compare the alternative and reference substances.

1.3.2 Case study specific choices in testing of substances

In addition to the substances used in the production process, other potential hazardous substances are those that could be:

- released during production or use;
- formed during the production process;
- leaching out during the use phase;
- released during the recycling phase.

Therefore, hazard evaluation of these substances should be included in case human or environmental exposure is relevant (Figure 1.2-1).

The three case studies focus on plastic materials, therefore some of the ingredients are pellets, which cannot be tested with in vitro assays. In such cases, an alternative was used for hazard assessment, these could be leachates or migration samples. These choices were case study specific and outlined below.

Case study 1

All ingredients used in case study 1 (CS1) could be tested in the in vitro assays. For this case study, no leachates or migration samples were tested. However, a discrimination between priority 1 and priority 2 substances were made, for endpoints that could not be assessed for the high number of substances. Priority 1 substances were the ingredients that differed between the reference production route and the alternative route. Priority 2 substances were the ingredients that were used in both the reference production route and the alternative route. Specifications of the substances can be found in Table 1.3-1.

Case study 2

For case study 2 (CS2) there were 2 groups of ingredients: hardeners and flame retardants. Resins were used in all routes. The resin and flame retardants could not be tested with in vitro assays due to their physical chemical properties, so these were tested in combination, together referred to as A-Parts. In addition, leachates from composites with different flame retardants but the same hardener (4-AFD) were available. The hardeners and A-parts were considered the priority 1 substances, the leachates were priority 2 substances (Table 1.3-1).

Case study 3

All ingredients for case study 3 (CS3) were pellets, which could not be directly tested with in vitro assays. As for food packaging, migration of substances from the plastic films is assessed, we have used the migration samples for hazard assessment. For each film, a migration sample in 3% acetic acid (referred to in the Table as B) and a migration sample in 95% ethanol (referred to in the Table as E95) were provided. The concentrated migration samples were tested at a single dose (expressed in % dilution in the medium) (Table 1.3-1).

Table 1.3-1: Overview of the substances tested for each of the case studies.

	Case Study 1	Case Study 2	Case Study 3
Priority 1	Bi-Cat Cystamine THEED Disulfide Polyol I Polyol A Polyol B Polyol C Polyol D	AP-CL AP1 AP2 AP3 AP4 MDA 4-AFD 2-AFD	PO/PA/compat 11 B PE/compat/PA 65 B PE/EVOH 129 B PE/compat/EVOH 129 B PO/PA/compat 11 E95 PE/compat/PA 65 E95 PE/EVOH 129 E95 PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95
Priority 2	Diisocyanate Niax Catalyst Niax Silicon FR CROS 484	Leach-TCPP Leach-SP1 Leach-SP2 Leach-SP3 Leach-SP4	

2 Selected models

The human in vitro models used reflect the main exposure routes, of workers and consumers potentially exposed to substances used and/or released along the life cycle of each product, namely dermal contact, ingestion (as a consequence of hand to mouth contact) and inhalation (Section 2.1). Aquatic toxicity was studied using *Daphnia magna* and zebrafish, *Danio rerio*, as models. For endocrine disruption CALUX® (Chemically Activated Luciferase eXpression) assays, the H295R steroidogenesis assay and a transgenic zebrafish line for thyroglobulin were used to study disruption of estrogen, androgen, thyroid or steroidogenesis modalities. The models for aquatic toxicity and endocrine disruption are described in Section 2.2.

2.1 Models representing exposure routes

Dermal contact: HaCaT cells (CLS, Eppelheim, Germany), an immortalized human keratinocytic cell line, were cultured in high glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium with Glutamine (DMEM + GlutaMAX™; 31966021, Gibco, Illkirch, France) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco), 100 UI/mL penicillin and 0.1 mg/mL streptomycin (Sigma), and maintained under an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37 °C.

Ingestion: Caco-2 cells (ATCC HTB-37) were used as oral model. This is an immortalized cell line of human colorectal adenocarcinoma, were cultured in high glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium with Glutamine (DMEM + GlutaMAX™; 31966021, Gibco, Illkirch, France) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco), 1% non-essential amino acids (NEAA, Sigma), 100 UI/mL penicillin and 0.1 mg/mL streptomycin (Sigma), and maintained under an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37 °C.

Inhalation mono-cultures in submerged conditions: Monocultures of A549 cells (ATCC-CCL-185), an immortalized adenocarcinoma human alveolar basal epithelial cell line, were cultured in RPMI medium (Gibco, Ref. 31870025) supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (Gibco, Ref. 10438-026), 1 %

Penicillin-Streptomycin (15140122, ThermoFisher Scientific) and 1 % L-Glutamine (A2916801, ThermoFisher Scientific), and maintained under an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37 °C. For cytotoxicity and cellular ROS experiments, A549 were plated in 96-well plates at 10000 cells/well and maintained for 24h prior to the exposure experiments. Monocultures of THP-1 (ATCC TIB-202), a human leukemia monocytic cell line, were cultured in RPMI medium (Gibco, Ref. 31870025) supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (Gibco, Ref. 10438-026), 1 % Penicillin-Streptomycin (15140122, ThermoFisher Scientific), 1 % L-Glutamine (A2916801, ThermoFisher Scientific) and 0.05 mM β-Mercaptoethanol (31350010, ThermoFisher Scientific), and maintained under an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37 °C. To differentiate the THP-1 cells to a macrophage-like phenotype (dTHP-1), cells were plated at 25000 cells/well in 96-well plates and supplemented with 100 ng/ml phorbol-12-myristate-13-acetate (PMA) (Sigma P8139) for 24h, followed by a 24h recovering period in the basal medium without PMA.

Inhalation co-cultures in Air-Liquid Interface conditions: Co-cultures of A549 and dTHP-1 were prepared as follows (Figure 2.1-1). First, 50000 A549 cells were plated in the apical side of a 12 mm Transwell® with 0.4 μm Pore Polyester Membrane Insert (Corning®, Ref 3460, surface area of 1.12cm²), cultured in RPMI medium (Gibco, Ref. 31870025) supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (Gibco, Ref. 10438-026), 1 % Penicillin-Streptomycin (15140122, ThermoFisher Scientific) and 1 % L-Glutamine (A2916801, ThermoFisher Scientific) in the basolateral and the apical side, and maintained under an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37 °C. After 3 days in culture, the apical medium was removed and cells maintained in air-liquid interface (ALI) conditions. After 5 days in culture, PMA-differentiated THP-1 were plated on top of the A549 cells at a 1:10 ratio, and the co-cultures were maintained for 24h more before exposing them to the test substances. The co-culture at the ALI enables more realistic exposure conditions in an environment that better resembles the lung, such as production of surfactant and enabling cross-talk between epithelial and immune cells, making them a valuable tool for drug testing and for studying respiratory effects.

Figure 2.1-1: Co-cultures of A549 + dTHP-1 in ALI. **A)** Scheme for culture and exposure set up. **B)** Membrane inserts where A549 and dTHP-1 cells are plated on the apical side in contact with air and in contact with medium in the basolateral side. **C)** Schematic of the phases of the nebulisation exposure using the VITROCELL Cloud 12 device.

2.2 Models for fresh water toxicity and endocrine disruption

Daphnia magna

Daphnia magna, freshwater arthropods commonly used as a model organism in ecotoxicology, were cultured in ASTM hard water medium (containing $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, MgSO_4 , NaHCO_3 , and KCl) prepared according to the standard guideline. Cultures were maintained under a 16:8 h light:dark photoperiod at 20 ± 1 °C and fed once each two days with a concentrated suspension of green algae (*Raphidocelis subcapitata*) as a nutrient. Water was also renewed three times per week to maintain optimal conditions.

Zebrafish

Zebrafish, *Danio rerio*, were maintained and bred in an automatic Zebtec flow-through system (Tecniplast S.p.A, Buguggiate, Italy) in the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) facility. The pH was maintained at 7.5 ± 0.5 , temperature at 27.5 ± 0.5 °C (adults) and 30.0 ± 0.5 °C (embryos), and conductivity at 500 ± 100 μS . The photoperiod was set at a light/dark cycle of 14/10 h. Zebrafish were fed 3 times a day, twice with SDS (Special Diet Services, Tecnilab-BMI BV, the Netherlands) 100, 200, 300, or small granules (depending on age), and once with frozen artemia (Superfish).

CALUX® assays

Estrogen receptor alpha responsive (ER α) and androgen receptor responsive (AR) CALUX® cells are engineered human osteosarcoma cell lines U2OS incorporating the firefly luciferase gene coupled to the respective responsive elements as a reporter gene. Both cell lines were purchased from BioDetection Systems (BDS, Netherlands) and cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's / F12 medium (1:1) with phenol red and GlutaMAX™ Supplement (DMEM/F12 ; 31331, Gibco, Illkirch, France) supplemented with 7.5% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco), 1% non-essential amino acids (NEAA, Sigma), 10 UI/mL penicillin and 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin (Sigma), and 0.2 mg/mL geneticin (G-418) as selective agent. Cells were maintained under an atmosphere of 5% CO_2 at 37 °C.

H295R steroidogenesis assay

The in vitro H295R Steroidogenesis Assay (H295R) described in OECD test guideline 456 (OECD, 2023) utilises human adenocarcinoma cell line NCI-H295R. In this cell line, the human steroidogenesis pathway is fully functional and active. Upon exposure of this cell line to a test substance, the effect on steroidogenesis can be assessed by quantifying the amount of 17 β -estradiol (E2) and testosterone (T) produced by the cells and comparing this to cells exposed to a vehicle control. This assay is only performed for case study 3 and outsourced to BioDetection Systems (BDS, Amsterdam).

3 Selected *in vitro* assays

Hazard assessment was performed for the toxicological endpoints: cytotoxicity, oxidative stress, inflammation, epigenetics, genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and aquatic toxicity. The different assays used to assess these toxicological endpoints are described in this Chapter.

Exposure of oral and dermal models: Exposure of oral and dermal models was done by applying the substance (in solvent) to cell culture medium, which is further specified for the specific assays. Exposure of inhalation models was more complex and therefore described in more detail below.

Exposure of inhalation models: For the exposure of the co-cultures to the test substances, only one sub-lethal dose of the materials was used for the same subgroup of materials (reference material and alternatives). This selected dose was extrapolated from the highest EC20 for that group of materials having into account the amount of substance and the volumes and surface area of the different plates and inserts. Whenever exposition by nebulisation was not possible due to the high concentration or volume of solution needed or incompatible vehicle composition (substance should be diluted in 1% NaCl solution for nebulisation), test substances were exposed in semi-ALI conditions, using a maximal 100 μL volume of substance on top of the apical side. For the CS1 materials, a 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{insert}$ dose was selected for the polyols group. For the catalysts group (cystamine, THEED and bismuth neodecanoate), a 70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{insert}$ dose was selected, exposed in semi-ALI conditions. As no reference substance is available for the additives group (Niax catalyst A1, Niax Silicone L6642, FR CROS 484 and hydroxyethyl disulfide) and EC50 values were higher than the highest concentration tested, we decided testing them at the same 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{insert}$ dose, exposed in semi-ALI conditions, to be comparable to the polyols. For CS2 materials, a 3.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{insert}$ dose was selected for the hardeners group and a 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{insert}$ dose was selected for the A-Parts group, exposed in semi-ALI conditions. Two inserts were used per condition tested and three independent experiments were performed.

The aerosol chamber was mounted and humidity in the aerosol chamber was allowed to saturate for 30 min. The chamber wells were filled with 3.1 mL of medium and the inserts were placed into the wells to be nebulised with one substance at a time. Between exposures to different substances, the aerosol chamber and nebuliser were cleaned, and the required wells of the exposure chamber were rinsed and filled with fresh A549 medium. For non-treated controls, a 200 μL control 1% saline solution was nebulized. Subsequently, 200 μL of the substance's suspension corresponding to a deposited concentration of about 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ was nebulized in the exposure chamber. The sedimentation process and deposited dose was observed based on the Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM) signal. First the signal was measured for 1 minute before starting the nebulization to ensure the fluctuation should not be more than 25 ng/cm^2 . Once the nebulisation started the chamber was maintained closed for 6 min to ensure a complete settlement of the test substance to the inserts and QCM. Then the exposure top was lifted for 1 min allowing the QCM to dry, and 3 min more were measured afterwards with the lid on. Data analysis on the QCM signal to determine the delivered dose was performed on the mean of the last 30 values of deposition recorded.

When exposure was finished, cell culture inserts were placed back to the cell culture plate and transferred back to the incubator for 24h before sample collection. After 24h exposure, medium was added to the apical side of the inserts for 30 minutes. Of the apical and basolateral supernatants, 50 μL of each insert were collected for the LDH cytotoxicity assay. The residual supernatants were stored at -80 °C for ELISAs. The inserts with cells were rinsed with PBS twice, and stored at -80 °C for protein carbonylation analyses.

3.1 Cytotoxicity assessment

3.1.1 WST-1 assay

The WST-1 assay is a colorimetric test providing information on cell viability. It is performed for the oral and dermal model (Section 2).

The assay protocol is based on the cleavage of the slightly red tetrazolium salt WST-1 to a dark red formazan dye that is then measured by absorbance reading at 450nm. This cleavage being done by cellular mitochondrial dehydrogenases, the amount of formazan dye depends directly on the activity of mitochondrial dehydrogenases, reflecting consequently the amount of viable cells (Figure 3.1-1).

Material and method

On the day prior to the treatment, HaCaT and Caco-2 cells were seeded into 96-well plates (respectively 3.5×10^4 and 3.0×10^4 cells/well) in culture medium. On the next day, 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{w}$ of suspensions containing different treatment conditions was added for 48 h. At the end of the treatment, both WST-1 assay and LDH assay were performed in parallel.

For WST-1, tetrazolium salt WST-1 (4-[3-(4-iodophenyl)-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-2H-5-tetrazolio]-1,3-benzene disulfonate) solution (Cell Proliferation Reagent WST-1, Roche) was added to the treated plates at final dilution of 1:10 in medium without serum. After 1h and 1h30 at 37 °C, respectively for Caco-2 and HaCaT cells, absorbance was measured at 450nm – 650nm (SpectraMax iD3, Molecular Devices). The delta values were collected and data normalization was done by setting the solvent control level at 100% viability.

3.1.2 LDH assay

The LDH assay is a colorimetric test providing information on membrane permeability and integrity. It is performed for the three exposure routes (Section 2).

The protocol is based on the dosage of lactate dehydrogenase activity (LDH) in the cell supernatant. Indeed, LDH is a stable cytoplasmic enzyme that is released into the cell culture supernatant after damage to the plasma membrane. An increase in the amount of dead or plasma membrane damaged cells results in an increase in LDH activity in the culture supernatant, which is directly related to the amount of formazan formed (Figure 3.1-2).

Materials and Methods

On the day prior to the treatment, HaCaT and Caco-2 cells were seeded into 96-well plates (respectively 3.5×10^4 and 3.0×10^4 cells/well) in culture medium. On the next day, 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{w}$ of suspensions containing different treatment conditions was added for 48 h. At the end of the treatment, both WST-1 assay and LDH assay were performed in parallel.

For LDH assay, 50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{w}$ of medium were collected from the treated plates and dispensed into new empty plates. Measurement of LDH activity was performed using LDH cytotoxicity assay kit (Sigma) for the CS2 Hardeners and CS2 A-Parts. For the other SURPASS products, Cytotoxicity Detection Kit LDH (Roche) was used. For both kits, the reaction mix preparation, the incubation and the reaction stop were performed according the supplier instructions. Raw data were normalized by setting the solvent control at 0% and the positive control at 100% mortality. Treated data were then expressed in % of cell viability.

In the case of the cytotoxicity studies for the inhalation cell models, A549 and dTHP-1 cells were seeded into 96-well plates (10000 and 25000 cells/well respectively) in monocultures. Cells were exposed to a range of concentrations of the different substances: 1-10-25-50-100-250-500-1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for the CS1 polyols, 1-5-10-25-50-75-100-200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for all the other substances of CS1 and CS2, and 6 2-factor dilution starting from 1:1000 for the CS3 substances. After 24h treatment, Alamar Blue assay and CyQUANT™ LDH Cytotoxicity Assay Kit assay (ThermoFisher Scientific) were performed in parallel following the manufacturer's instructions and measuring the absorbance at 490 nm and 680 nm with a plate reader. Solvent controls (SC), with only vehicle solution for test substance added matching the

quantity in treatments, and positive controls (PC), consisting in 1% Triton X-100, were added. To determine LDH activity, subtract the 680-nm absorbance value (background) from the 490-nm absorbance before calculation of % Cytotoxicity. Percentage of cytotoxicity was calculated with the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Cytotoxicity} = \left(\frac{\text{TC Abs} - \text{SC Abs}}{\text{Max LDH Abs} - \text{SC Abs}} \times 100 \right)$$

Where:

TC Abs: corrected absorbance of test wells

SC Abs: corrected absorbance of non-treated controls

Max LDH: Abs corrected absorbance of positive control well

Finally, results are analysed by plotting absorbance intensity versus logarithmic transformation of the substance concentration. Toxicity curves and IC50 values were generated in GraphPad Prism using a non-linear regression log(inhibitor) vs. response – variable slope (four parameters) fitting curve (bottom constrain at 0% and 100% top constrain). Each test substance was assayed in technical in-plate duplicate in 3 independent experiments.

3.1.3 Alamar Blue assay

The AlamarBlue assay was performed for the inhalation models (Section 2) as measure for cytotoxicity. AlamarBlue® cell viability reagent functions as a cell health indicator by using the reducing power of living cells to quantitatively measure the proliferation of different cell lines, allowing to establish relative cytotoxicity of agents within various chemical classes. When cells are alive, they maintain a reducing environment within the cytosol of the cell. Resazurin, the active ingredient of AlamarBlue® reagent, is a non-toxic, cell permeable compound that is blue in colour and virtually non-fluorescent. Upon entering cells, resazurin is reduced to resorufin, a compound that is red in colour and highly fluorescent. Viable cells continuously convert resazurin to resorufin, increasing the overall fluorescence and colour of the media surrounding cells.

Material and method

In the case of the cytotoxicity studies for the inhalation cell models, A549 and dTHP-1 cells were seeded into 96-well plates (10000 and 25000 cells/well respectively) in monocultures. Cells were exposed to a range of concentrations of the different substances: 1-10-25-50-100-250-500-1000 µg/mL for the CS1 polyols, 1-5-10-25-50-75-100-200 µg/mL for all the other substances from CS1 and CS2, and 6 2-factor dilution starting from 1:1000 for the CS3 samples. After 24h treatment, AlamarBlue® assay (ThermoFisher Scientific) was performed by adding the 10X AlamarBlue® solution to the cell medium followed by a 1–4 hours incubation at 37°C. Solvent controls (SC), with only vehicle solution for test substances added matching the quantity in treatments, and positive controls (PC), consisting in 1% Triton X-100, were added. The resulting absorbance of AlamarBlue® reagent can be read on a spectrophotometer at 570 nm, using 600 nm as a reference wavelength. Percentage of cytotoxicity was calculated by following the next equation:

$$\% \text{ Cytotoxicity} = 100 - \left(\frac{(O600 \times A570) - (O570 \times A600)}{(O600 \times C570) - (O570 \times C600)} \times 100 \right)$$

Where:

O570 : molar extinction coefficient (E) of oxidized alamarBlue (blue) at 570 nm

O600 : E of oxidized alamarBlue at 600 nm

C570 : absorbance of positive growth control well (cells plus alamarBlue but no test agent) at 570 nm

C600 : absorbance of positive growth control well (cells plus alamarBlue but no test agent) at 600 nm

A570 : absorbance of test wells at 570 nm

A600 : absorbance of test wells at 600 nm

Finally, results are analysed by plotting absorbance intensity versus log of substance concentration. Toxicity curves and IC50 values were generated in GraphPad Prism using a non-linear regression log(inhibitor) vs. response – variable slope (four parameters) fitting curve (bottom constrain at 0% and 100% top constrain). Each test substance was assayed in technical in-plate duplicate in 3 independent experiments.

3.2 Oxidative stress assessment

3.2.1 CM-H₂DCFDA assay

Oxidative stress is defined as an imbalance between the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and cellular antioxidant capacities. This imbalance is an indicator cellular dysfunction and is involved in the induction of damage to biomolecules.

The CM-H₂DCFDA assay is a fluorimetric test providing information on oxidative stress in the cells. It is based on the use of a probe to monitor this imbalance within cells. Indeed, the CM-H₂DCFDA probe diffuses passively into cells, where its acetate groups are cleaved by intracellular esterases and its thiol-reactive chloromethyl group reacts with intracellular glutathione and other thiols. The resulting adduct is thus trapped inside the cell. In the presence of ROS, the dihydro-fluorescein part of the molecule is oxidized into fluorescent fluorescein (Figure 3.2-1), which can be monitored using a microplate reader, using appropriate excitation sources and filters.

Material and method

Production of intracellular ROS content was monitored using CMH₂DCFDA (5(and-6)-chloromethyl-2'7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate, acetyl ester, Invitrogen, France) assay. On the day prior to the treatment, HaCaT cells and Caco-2 cells were seeded into black 96-well plates (respectively 3.5x10⁴ and 3.0x10⁴ cells/well) in culture medium. On the next day, cells were rinsed with Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffered Saline (DPBS, Gibco, Illkirch, France) and incubated for 1 h with a DPBS solution containing 5 μM CMH₂DCFDA (Invitrogen) and 0.6% DMSO. As control, wells were only incubated with a DPBS solution containing 0.6% DMSO. At the end of the incubation, cells were rinsed with DPBS. High glucose DMEM without phenol red (31053028, Gibco, Illkirch, France) supplemented with 4 mM GlutaMax (35050061, Gibco), 1 mM sodium pyruvate (S8636, Sigma) and with 10% fetal bovine serum, 100 UI/mL penicillin and 0.1 mg mL⁻¹ streptomycin was added in wells, followed by a 45 min incubation. Then, medium was discarded and suspensions containing different treatment conditions were added. As positive control, a solution with 250 μM *tert*-Butyl hydroperoxide (tBuOOH, Sigma) was added to wells. After a 4hour treatment, the fluorescence of fluorescein was measured at λ_{exc}/λ_{em} 488 nm/535 nm (SpectraMax iD3, Molecular Devices). Potential interferences of SURPASS products were taken into account by measuring the fluorescence of cells exposed to tested substances or DCBP incubated with a solution containing 0.6% DMSO without CMH₂DCFDA.

The obtained values were subtracted from those obtained in the absence of the probe. Results were then normalized by setting the solvent control level at 0% and the positive control level at 100%.

3.2.2 Cellular ROS Assay kit

Cellular Reactive Oxygen Species Detection Assay Kit (Red Fluorescence) (ab186027, Abcam) is a sensitive fluorometric one-step assay to detect intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as superoxide and hydroxyl radical in live cells. The assay uses a Red dye to quantify ROS: the dye is cell-permeable and reacts with ROS present in the cell to generate a red fluorescent signal (Ex/Em = 520/605 nm).

Material and method

A549 were seeded into 96-well plates (10000 cells/well) in monocultures and maintained for 24h before the ROS assay. Following the manufacturer's instructions, cells were incubated with the ROS Red Stain working solution for 1h, and afterwards exposed the different test compounds for a maximum of 5h. Equitoxic concentrations of the test compounds were tested, EC20 and EC50 concentrations were tested when it was possible to calculate. When no EC50 value could be calculated, the test compound were tested at the maximum concentration tested in the cytotoxicity experiments. Solvent controls (SC), with only vehicle solution for test compound added matching the quantity in treatments, and positive controls (PC), consisting of a 5M tert-Butyl hydroperoxide solution (TBHP), were included in each assay. Fluorescence was measured (Ex.520/Em.605) at different timepoints 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h and 5h. Percentage of ROS was calculated by dividing the test compound fluorescence by the SC fluorescence and multiplying by 100.

3.2.3 Protein carbonylation

Formation of protein carbonyls (aldehydes and ketones) is the most prevalent type of irreversible protein oxidation that can be promoted by ROS. The carbonyl group can be introduced in the protein through oxidative modification of susceptible amino acid residues like lysine threonine proline and arginine, altering the protein function and structure. This process disrupts protein-protein interactions and impairs enzyme activity leading to protein dysfunction. Carbonylated proteins fail to perform effectively within cellular systems and accumulate in cells. These accumulations can form large aggregates which cells often recognize as damaged. Protein degradation systems struggle to efficiently degrade these aggregates which can lead to further cellular dysfunction. Analysing protein carbonylation is a useful tool for studying qualitatively and quantitatively the level of oxidative stress which had been acting upon chemical-exposed cells.

The Protein Carbonyl ELISA Kit (ab238536 Abcam) quantitatively measures protein carbonyls in cell lysates. First protein samples were allowed to adsorb to wells of a 96-well plate and then react with dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH), which allows for derivatization of the carbonyl group, followed by immunoblotting with an anti-DNP antibody. The quantity of protein carbonyls in protein sample was determined by comparing its absorbance with that of a known reduced/oxidized BSA standard curve.

Material and method

For the protein carbonylation experiments, co-cultures of A549 and dTHP-1 cells were cultured in ALI conditions and exposed to test compounds by nebulisation using a VITROCELL® Cloud 12 system. Test compounds are tested at equimolar concentrations close to the calculated EC20 concentration for the group of compounds in each case study. Solvent controls (SC), with only vehicle solution for test compound added matching the quantity in treatments, and positive controls (PC), consisting of 0.5 μ M H₂O₂ solution, were included in each assay. Cells stored at -80 °C after 24h exposures, were collected in PBS and lysed by sonication and total protein content is quantified by performing a protein assay BCA (Pierce™ BCA Protein Assay Kit, Ref 23225, ThermoFisher Scientific). Samples were prepared by diluting them to 10 μ g/mL in 1X PBS, and all standards, controls and samples were assayed in duplicate following the manufacturer's instructions. Absorbance was measured on a plate reader using 450 nm as the primary wavelength, using the fully reduced BSA standard as absorbance blank. Content of

protein carbonyl in nmol/mg in the samples was extrapolated from the reduced/oxidized BSA standard curve, and percentage of carbonylation was calculated by dividing the carbonyl content of the test samples by the SC.

3.3 Epigenetics

3.3.1 Quantification of methylated cytosine in total DNA using HPLC-MS

For this assay, the 5-methylcytosine bases present in nuclear DNA were quantified using high performance liquid chromatography associated with electrospray tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS). The aim of this method is to assess if exposure modulates the level of DNA methylation on cytosine (Figure 3.3-1). Impact of this epigenetic modification could affect the expression of important genes and lead to adverse effects. It is for example documented that tumour are either hyper- or hypomethylated in genes involved in cancer. The assay was performed in the oral model (Caco-2 cells). Not in the inhalation models and in the dermal model (HaCaT cells), in the latter model no positive control could be found.

Material and method

Caco-2 cells were grown up to 60-70% confluence. Treatment solutions were added to the cells and incubated for 48h. After treatment, culture media were collected and stored at -80°C until sample shipment to RIVM for cytokine measurement (Section 3.4.2). Cells were then collected and rinsed twice with Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffered Saline (DPBS, Gibco, Illkirch, France). The cell pellets for 5-methylcytosine quantification were stored at -20°C until extraction.

DNA extraction was performed using chemical lysis in two steps. A buffer containing triton X-100 was used to remove plasma membranes and collect nuclei. Those were lysed in a buffer containing SDS. The resulting suspension was treated by RNases and proteinases. DNA was recovered by precipitation after addition of sodium iodide and isopropanol. DNA then underwent enzymatic hydrolysis into nucleosides by a cocktail of endonucleases, phosphodiesterases and phosphatases. The resulting solution was freeze-dried and resuspended with 50µL of a solution containing 25 µM isotopically labelled internal standard for mass spectrometry detection ([¹³C,¹⁵N₂]-5-methyl-2'-deoxycytidine and [¹³C₉,¹⁵N₂]-2'-deoxycytidine). The sample were filtrated at 0.2µm and injected (20 µL) into the HPLC system (ExionLC, SCIEX) equipped with a reverse phase HPLC column (BEH 1.7 microm VanGuard FIT. 2.1x100mm column,1/pk, Waters, Drinagh, Ireland). The temperature of the column oven was set at

50 °C. The HPLC elution was performed at a flow rate of 0.3 mL min⁻¹ in the gradient mode. The mobile phases were an aqueous solution of 2 mM ammonium formate containing 0.05% formic acid (A) and ACN (B). The initial composition of the gradient was pure A and kept for 2 min. The proportion of B was then increased to 20% at 5 min. It was then set to 80% during 2 min. The solvent was changed to 100% A for 3 min. The outlet of the column was directed first to a UV diode array detector and then to the inlet of a 6500 + QTrap mass spectrometer (SCIEX) operated in the positive electrospray ionization. Multiple reaction monitoring analyses (MRM) were performed with the following specifications for 5-methyl-2'-deoxycytidine (5-MedCyd), 2'-deoxycytidine (dCyd) and their internal standards:

Q1 Mass (Da)	Q3 Mass (Da)	Dwell(msec)	ID	Retention time (min)
228.1	112.0	250	dCyd	1.8
242.0	126.0	250	5-MedCyd	3.0
240.0	119.0	250	[M+12]-dCyd	1.8
245.0	129.0	250	[M+3]-5-MedCyd	3.0

Raw data were analysed with the MultiQuant software to integrate peak areas. For each condition, mean values for dCyd and MedCyd were compared to those of their respective internal standard to obtain dCyd and MedCyd concentrations. This latter was then expressed in percentage of 5-methyl-2'-deoxycytidine with respect to 2'-deoxycytidine.

3.4 Inflammation

3.4.1 Cytokine assessment of inhalation model

The inflammatory response in the lungs after inhalation of toxic chemicals is critical for neutralizing threats and initiating tissue repair, but excessive or prolonged inflammation can lead to chronic lung diseases like fibrosis or chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (COPD). Toxicants reaching deep lung regions can disrupt alveolar epithelial cells, triggering the release of damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), which are recognised by alveolar macrophages via pattern recognition receptors (e.g., TLRs), and respond by phagocytosing particles and secreting pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1 β). Endothelial cells functions involve surfactant production and upregulation of adhesion molecules (e.g., ICAM-1), facilitating neutrophil recruitment, and can also secrete pro-inflammatory cytokines.

In the co-culture model, the A549 cells are reported to produce IL-6 and IL-8 when exposed to inflammatory stimulus such as LPS, while THP-1-derived macrophages secrete TNF- α and IL-1 β in response to DAMPs. Cytokines released from macrophages can substantially enhance the cytokine response of epithelial cells, and the other way around, contact with epithelial cells shapes the activity of alveolar macrophages.

Material and method

Co-cultures of A549 and dTHP-1 cells were cultured in ALI conditions and exposed to test compounds by nebulisation using a VITROCELL® Cloud 12 system. Test compounds are tested at equimolar concentrations close to the calculated EC20 concentration for the group of compounds in each case study. Solvent controls (SC), with only vehicle solution for test compound added matching the quantity in treatments, and positive controls (PC), consisting of 500 ng/mL Lipopolysaccharides (LPS) (L4391,

Merck), were included in each assay. After 24h exposure, medium was added to the apical side of the inserts for 30 minutes and apical and basolateral medium were collected and stored at -80 degrees until cytokine quantification. Secreted levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines were assessed by ELISA using the Human IL-6 DuoSet ELISA kit (DY206, Bio-Techne) and Human TNF-alpha DuoSet ELISA kit (DY210, Bio-Techne) and following the manufacturer's instructions. Both cytokines are central to the alveolar inflammation process, with TNF- α driving acute responses and IL-6 shaping chronic outcomes. Concentration of cytokines in the samples was calculated by extrapolation from a standard curve and percentage of cytokine production was calculated by dividing the cytokine content of the test samples by the SC.

3.4.2 Cytokine assessment of dermal and oral model

Inflammatory response in intestinal and dermal cell models was measured to assess a potential inflammatory response of the substances tested. Upon contact, substances could induce the production of cytokines and chemokines, that may attract immune cells. Prolonged inflammatory response could result in chronic inflammation and tissue damage. Measurement of a set of 13 cytokines and chemokines indicates whether the substances tested potentially induce an inflammatory response.

Materials and method

Cytokine levels in the samples were measured with the use of LEGENDplex™ HU Essential Immune Response Panel (13-plex) (Biolegend, Cat No: 740930, Lot: B428764). After rehydrating the standard with 250 μ L mQ for 10 minutes 300rpm, RT, a 1:3 serial dilution was made with assay buffer. Beads were vortexed for 1 minute after which a mix was prepared with assay buffer, bead solution and detection antibodies 1:1:1. Of this mixture, 15 μ L was pipetted in each well of a 96 well plate (Falcon, V-bottom, pp, REF353263) after which 5 μ L of standard, sample or assay buffer as control was added to the wells. This was incubated for 2 hours on a plateshaker (Heidolph titramax 100) at 600rpm, RT, while the plate was sealed and protected from light with the use of aluminum foil for all the coming steps of the assay. Next, 5 μ L SA-PE was added to all wells and incubated for 30 minutes on the plateshaker at 600 rpm, RT. Wash buffer was prepared by 20 times dilution in mQ and 150 μ L was added to all wells. The plate was centrifuged for 5 minutes at 1000xg, setting 7 for acceleration, setting 2 for break (Eppendorf centrifuge 5810R), after which the plate was decanted once to remove the supernatant, pressed onto absorbent paper and turned upside up carefully. Each pellet was resuspended in 80 μ L wash buffer and the fluorescence was measured on the FACS Canto II. Data was then processed with the online LEGENDplex software (BioLegend, Qognit), gating (selection of successful measurements) was reviewed for inconsistencies in the measurements.

3.5 Genotoxicity

3.5.1 53BP1 assay for double strand break assessment

The aim of the 53BP1 assay is to assess the genotoxic effect of substances, by measuring the induction of double-stranded lesions in the cell DNA. The detected double strand breaks are either directly induced in DNA or result from stalling of replication fork at lesions such as bulky adducts.

The DNA double-strand break signalling pathway and its repair mechanism are essential for maintaining genomic integrity. In these mechanism, p53-binding protein 1 (53BP1) is a key regulator of the cellular response to double-strand breaks in mammalian cells, promoting the joining of non-homologous DNA ends during the G1 phase of the cell cycle. Consequently, 53BP1 is a well-known DNA damage response factor, recruited at an early stage to nuclear structures at the site of DNA damage where it forms easily visualised foci.

The identification of 53BP1 foci in treated cells using an immunolabelling protocol allows the amount of DNA damage per cell to be assessed (Figure 3.5-1). This makes possible the assessment of the genotoxic effect of a given substance. Using an automated imaging and image analysis system, cells are counted and the number of foci per cell is measured.

Material and method

On the day prior to the treatment, cells were seeded into 96-well plates (black with clear bottom) at 2×10^4 cells/well in culture medium. On the next day, suspensions corresponding to different treatment conditions were added to the cells and the plates incubated for 24h. As positive control for the assay, etoposide (6,25 µM to 100 µM) was used to induce DNA breaks. At the end of the exposure, medium of wells was discarded and cells were immunostained for 53BP1. Briefly, cells were fixed with 4% formaldehyde pH 7.4 for 20 min, washed three times with PBS, and then permeabilized with 3% BSA and 0.2% triton X-100 for 15 min at room temperature. Non-specific sites were blocked in a saturation step with PBS containing 3% bovine serum albumin (BSA) for 30 min. Finally, cells were incubated with an anti-human 53BP1 polyclonal antibody (Abnova, PAB12506, dilution 1/200, Clinisciences, Nanterre, France) for 2h at room temperature under mild agitation, rinsed three times for 5 min with PBS and incubated in the dark for 1h at room temperature with goat anti-rabbit IgG-Atto488 (Merck #18,772, dilution 1/2000, St. Louis, MO, USA) in PBS containing 3% BSA. They were rinsed three times with PBS containing 0.2% triton X-100, then three times with PBS, before being counterstained with 1µg/mL DAPI (D9542 Sigma-Aldrich) in the dark for 20 min at room temperature. Each well was then washed three times with PBS, and plates were stored at 4°C in the dark with PBS containing 50% glycerol until plate reading.

Analyses were performed using a CellInsight CX5 High Content Screening automated imaging and image analysis system (Thermo Fisher Scientific). In each well, the automated microscope captures an image of cell nuclei based on the DAPI nucleic acid staining and then an image of 53BP1 foci based on Atto488 fluorescence. Then, image segmentation is performed by the HCS studio™ software: cell nuclei that are appropriate for 53BP1 foci counting are selected. Nuclei are selected based on their size and their circularity, thereby excluding fractionated nuclei of apoptotic cells or nuclei from damaged cells, and also nuclei from cells that are too close to one another (i.e., these nuclei appear to be too large), hampering their proper identification and analysis. Nuclei that are on the image edges are also excluded. Within the selected nuclei, HCS studio™ identifies 53BP1 foci as brighter and smaller spots and counts them. The thresholds for the identification of 53BP1 foci are fixed by the operator based on his informed experience and on the values that are expected in control cells (both unexposed cells and cells exposed to the positive control). Five entire wells were analysed per condition. Results are expressed as average numbers of 53BP1 foci per cell nucleus.

3.5.2 Comet assay for DNA damage assessment

The comet assay is a single cell gel electrophoresis assay, with the aim of visualizing DNA strand breaks in eukaryotic cells as measure for genotoxicity.

First, pre-treated cells are embedded in a thin layer of agarose gel on a microscope slide. Then, the lysis of the cells forms nucleoids, containing the DNA linked to the nuclear matrix. Finally, an electric field is applied to allow migration of the lysed cells on the gel and slides are observed by fluorescence microscopy after addition of a DNA intercalating agent (Figure 3.5-2). If DNA is intact, the nucleoid remains compact during electrophoresis. If DNA is damaged, the broken strands are dragged out of the nucleoid and form a comet-like pattern.

Using an imaging software, individual cellular images are analyzed and the extent of DNA damage can be assessed by measuring the comet tail intensity in comparison with the comet head.

Material and method

On the day prior to the treatment, cells were seeded into 12-well plates (2.5×10⁵ cells/well) in culture medium. On the next day, suspensions corresponding to different treatment conditions were added to the cells and the plates incubated for 24h. As positive control for the assay, methyl methanesulfonate (MMS) at 20 and 30 µg/mL, was used to induce DNA breaks. At the end of the exposure, medium of wells was discarded. The wells were rinsed with DPBS. Cells were recovered with trypsinEDTA and stored at –80 °C in a storage buffer. The comet assay was performed in its alkaline version. Briefly, microscope slides were coated with 1% normal melting point agarose (NMA) and allowed to dry. 70µL of cell suspensions were mixed with 400 µL of prewarmed 1% low melting point agarose (LMPA) and then, 70 µL of these mixtures were deposited over the agarose layer, and the LMPA/cells mix was allowed to solidify on ice. After solidification of the gels, the slides were immersed for 1h in cold lysis solution (2.5 M NaCl, 100 mM EDTA, 10 mM Tris, 1% Triton X-100 with pH 10) in the dark. Slides were rinsed three times with PBS for 5 min. DNA was then allowed to unwind for 30 min in cold alkaline electrophoresis solution (300 mM NaOH, 1 mM EDTA). Electrophoresis was performed in a field of 1.2 V cm⁻¹ and 300 mA current for 30 min in the same solution. Slides were rinsed twice with PBS for 10 min. Samples were stained with GelRed (Biotium, San Francisco, USA) for scoring. At last, 50 cells per slide were analysed under a fluorescence microscope (Zeiss) equipped with a LED emitting light with 380–770 nm wavelength (XCite Xylis, Model No. XT720L, Excelitas Canada Inc., Kitchener, Canada) at ×20 magnification. Percentage of tail DNA was measured by using comet IV software (Perceptive Instruments, Suffolk, UK).

3.6 Endocrine disruption

3.6.1 ER α and AR assessment

For CALUX[®] (Chemically Activated LUciferase eXpression) assays, mammalian cell lines were modified by incorporating the firefly luciferase gene coupled to specific responsive elements as reporter gene for the presence of compounds inducing the cellular response of interest. Here was focused on the effects on the estrogen receptor alpha (ER α) and androgen receptor (AR) as measure of disruption of the estrogen or androgen modalities.

When an agonist substance is present, the activation of the reporter gene leads to the production of the enzyme luciferase, which produces light by catalysing the oxidation of luciferin. This light signal is proportional to the amount of biologically active agonist chemical present in the sample and can be detected by luminescence with a microplate reader (Figure 3.6-1).

Determining antagonist properties is the second type of assessment can be done with the CALUX[®] assay. For this purpose, an agonist reference substance is intentionally added (to its EC50 concentration) to the experimental mixture. In this way, the basal signal is high, as the agonist reference substance induces luciferase production. Consequently, when an antagonist substance is added, the agonist reference substance is removed from the receptor and the activation of the reporter gene leading to luciferase production is thereby reduced. The decrease in light signal is proportional to the amount and the affinity of the biologically active antagonist chemical present in the sample and can be detected by luminescence with a microplate reader.

In addition to this antagonist assay, a specificity test is performed. For this purpose, the agonist reference substance is intentionally added in excess. Therefore, the inhibition of the luminescence signal by a disruptor is shifted because higher concentrations of this disruptor are needed to obtain the same effect. However, if no shift is observed, then the observed effect is not due to an inhibition of the CALUX[®] mechanism but to any other cellular process.

To identify unknown substances as potential endocrine disruptors, CALUX[®] ER α and CALUX[®] AR cell lines were purchased. Both are human osteosarcoma cell line U2OS, incorporating the firefly luciferase gene coupled to estrogen responsive elements (EREs) or androgen responsive elements respectively.

Material and method

On the day prior to the treatment, CALUX cells were seeded into white 96-well plates at 10,000 cells per well in assay medium (Dulbecco's modified Eagle's / F12 medium (1:1) without phenol red, supplemented with 5% Dextran Charcoal treated fetal bovine serum (FBS-DCC, Sigma), 1% non-essential amino acids (NEAA, Sigma), 10 UI/mL penicillin and 10 μ g/mL streptomycin (Sigma)) and maintained under an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37 °C. On the next day, cells were incubated with 100 μ L/well of treatment solutions for 24h. For agonist effect assessment, tested substances were diluted in assay medium. For antagonist effect assessment, they were diluted in assay medium containing an agonist reference substance at its EC₅₀. After incubation, treatment solutions were gently aspirated and cells were lysed. Luciferase activity was measured by luminescence assay in a microplate reader. First 100 μ L of Illuminate Mix (BDS, Netherlands) was added to the 30 μ L of cell lysate, then luminescence was measured for 4000ms and 100 μ L NaOH 0.2M was injected to stop the reaction before reading the next well.

For both agonist and antagonist assay, the endocrine disruption potential assessment was started with a pre-test. This pre-test was also carried out in parallel with a cytotoxicity test to assess the maximum non-cytotoxic dose of the substances tested. If the tested substances were showing an agonist or antagonist effect on the ER α or AR receptors in the pre-test, an additional test was performed within a narrower concentration range. For antagonist assessment, tested substances were also diluted in

assay medium containing a higher amount of ER α and AR agonist reference substance (50x and 100x respectively) to confirm the specificity of the response.

3.6.2 Transgenic zebrafish line for thyroid disruption

Zebrafish from the transgenic line *tg(tg:mCherry)* enable real-time imaging of thyroid development in eleutheroembryos through thyroid follicle fluorescence. This line was originally created by the Costagliola lab at IRIBHM in Brussels, Belgium. Investigating thyroid development in this way allows for assessment of thyroid status in the embryonic stages of zebrafish and thus allows for detection of thyroid hormone active substances.

Material and method

Newly fertilised eggs of the *tg(tg:mCherry)* zebrafish line are exposed to a sublethal concentration selected based on the results of the ZFET (described in Section 3.7.2). At the end of the exposure period (5 dpf), thyroid status is determined based on the measured fluorescence (integrated density) of the thyroid follicles in zebrafish eleutheroembryos. A fold-change in fluorescence compared to the control groups is calculated which may indicate increased or decreased follicular hypertrophy, activity and/or proliferation. In case an effect on the thyroid follicle fluorescence was observed, two additional lower concentrations were tested comparable to the alternative and/or reference substance.

3.6.3 H295R Steroidogenesis assay

The H295R steroidogenesis assay was performed to determine the effect of the tested compounds on steroidogenesis. Only the case study 3 migration samples were tested for an effect on steroidogenesis. This assay was performed by BioDetection Systems (BDS, Amsterdam, the Netherlands).

The effect on steroidogenesis can be assessed by quantifying the amount of 17 β -estradiol (E2) and testosterone (T) produced by the cells and comparing this to cells exposed to a vehicle control. At BDS, the quantification of E2 and T is performed using the ER α CALUX[®] and AR CALUX[®] bioassays, respectively. The goal of the assay according to the OECD guideline is to provide a YES/NO answer regarding the potential of a chemical to induce or inhibit the production of T and E2; however, it is also possible to report quantitative results by determining a lowest observed effect concentration (LOEC).

Material and method

The tested samples were the case study 3 migration samples, which are dissolved in two solvents: 3% acetic acid and ethanol. During both CALUX[®] and H295R exposures the exposure medium was supplemented with 0.1% DMSO to compensate for the DMSO solvent used for the reference substance and controls.

The H295R cells were seeded in 48 wells plates in assay medium, incubated for 24h and exposed for 48h to a serial dilution of the compound in triplicate (0.1% v/v). To quantify the levels of estrogens and androgens produced by the H295R cells after exposure, the assay medium was analyzed on the ER α and AR CALUX[®] bioassays as described previously (Section 3.6.1). Changes in hormone levels compared to a vehicle control (DMSO) exposure indicate that certain enzymes involved in steroidogenesis were being affected by the test compound. To eliminate false positive results in the CALUX[®] read-out, a

preliminary investigation was conducted for compounds for which the cytotoxicity in Cytotox CALUX[®] cells and activity on the ER α and AR CALUX[®] assays was unknown. This was to be able to rule out that activity observed in the CALUX[®] read out was caused by carry over of ER α or AR active compounds and not by changes in hormone levels in the H295R cells. For known compounds the results from previous analysis were used.

To determine the cytotoxicity of the compounds in the H295R steroidogenesis assay, an MTT cytotoxicity assay was used at BDS. In brief, 3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) was added to the cells. Viable cells are able to convert MTT into formazan, which can be measured at 595nm using a spectrophotometer. Relevant BDS protocol numbers: P-BDS-123b (available on request). The average of the triplicate below 80% (<20% decrease in absorbance) was considered cytotoxic.

3.7 Aquatic toxicity

3.7.1 *Daphnia Magna*

Aquatic toxicity, using *Daphnia magna* as model organism, was assessed following the OECD Test Guideline 202 (OECD, 2004; with slight modifications) which describes a standardized acute toxicity test to assess the effects of chemical substances on the mobility of *Daphnia magna* neonates (Figure 1.1-1Figure 3.7-1). The goal is to evaluate the percentage of immobilization following exposure to various concentrations of a test substance over 24 and 48 hours. Immobilization is defined as the inability of the daphnids to swim within 15 seconds after gentle agitation of the test vessel, even though they may still show slight movement of antennae or appendages.

Materials and method

Newborn *Daphnia magna* individuals (<24 hours old) were collected from healthy cultures maintained in ASTM hard water (see section 2.2 for more information) the same day of the experiment. Organisms were randomly assigned to treatment groups consisting of different concentrations of the test substances of CS1, CS2 and CS3, and a control group (ASTM hard water). Test solutions were made freshly and gently mixed before adding the organisms. Maximum limit of the test is established as 100 mg/L of a substance. The pH of each stock solution was measured to assure that it was on acceptable range (6.0 - 9.0) and adjusted with diluted NaOH or HCl if necessary. The exposures were performed

in 24 multi-well plates with a unique neonate and 2 ml of the respective treatment per plate, in static conditions, without aeration, without feeding, and in dark conditions. A minimum of 20 individuals were used per experimental condition. At 24 and 48 hours, each multi-well plate was gently agitated, and daphnids were observed under visible light to assess their mobility. Immobilization was recorded manually, and the percentage of immobilized organisms was calculated for each concentration. Results were statistically analysed to determine the EC₅₀ values (concentration causing immobilization in 50% of the test organisms), according to a sigmoidal regression model.

For reference, different thresholds of toxicity are expressed below:

- Acute Toxicity I: 48h EC₅₀ (*Daphnia magna*) ≤ 1 mg/L
- Acute Toxicity II: 48h EC₅₀ (*Daphnia magna*) > 1 – ≤10 mg/L
- Acute Toxicity III: 48h EC₅₀ (*Daphnia magna*) > 10 – ≤100 mg/L

3.7.2 Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET)

The Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test was performed as a measure of aquatic toxicity. To do so, zebrafish embryos were exposed to the SURPASS test compounds at subtoxic concentrations following an exposure protocol adapted from the OECD Test Guideline 236 (OECD, 2013; Hermsen et al., 2011). The aim is to score the embryo development at 3- and 5 days post fertilization.

Material and method

For breeding purposes, females were separated in a 3.5 L tank and fed frozen artemia three times a day for a period of 4 days, to stimulate egg production. The evening prior to mating, four females and four males were joined in a 1.7 L sloped breeding tank. Spawning was triggered by the onset of light, and eggs were collected within 30 min. after spawning. Eggs were transferred to Petri dishes and successfully fertilized eggs of good quality (symmetrical development; ≤10 % coagulated eggs in total), as evaluated under a stereomicroscope (Leica M8), kept for further use. Eggs at cleavage stage were exposed in 24-well plates containing one egg in 2 mL of test medium (E3) with 0.1 % DMSO (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) (Staal et al., 2018).

Development and teratology of exposed embryos were assessed at both 3- and 5-dpf (day post-fertilization) under the stereomicroscope in a zebrafish embryo toxicity test (ZFET), as previously described (Hermsen et al., 2011). In brief, embryo development was scored on the following endpoints: tail detachment, somite formation, eye development, movement of the embryo, heartbeat, blood circulation, embryo pigmentation, pectoral fin, protruding mouth and hatching. Next, teratological effects were recorded based on presence of pericardial edema, yolk sac edema, eye edema, head malformation, absence/malformation of sacculi/otoliths, tail malformations, heart malformations, modified chorda structure, scoliosis, rachischisis, and yolk deformation. These developmental and teratological scores were used to determine non-embryotoxic concentration ranges for the subsequent experimentation.

For the purpose of concentration-response analysis, data in the ZFET (morphology and teratology scores) were analysed using the PROAST software tool (v70.0; RIVM, Bilthoven, the Netherlands, <https://www.rivm.nl/en/proast/>), as a package in R statistical software v3.6.0–4.0.0 (RIVM, Bilthoven,

the Netherlands) (Slob, 2002). The PROAST tool analyses the input data for the optimal fit using an exponential function from a nested family of 1–4 parameter models and their variants. A benchmark concentration (BMC or critical effect dose (CED)) can be derived from the dose-response fit at a defined critical effect size (CES). To compare the potency of the individual compounds, a CED₂₀ was used (CED at CES = 20 %) which was used here as a measure of aquatic toxicity.

3.8 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed to meet two objectives: first to assess if the observed effect differs from the solvent control and can be used for the toxicity scoring, and, where possible, to assess a difference in response between the reference and the alternative substances within each group of substances (such as hardeners, polyols etc) for the performance scoring (Chapter 7, Hazard scoring, p. 146).

Replicates

Unless otherwise stated, experiments were designed with ≥ 3 technical replicates for each condition and were carried out in minimum 3 biological replicates. All treated results for each condition were analyzed with GraphPad Prism software, using the ROUT method (Q = 1%). Number of cleaned replicates kept are indicated for each assay in the figure legend.

For endocrine disruption on ER α and AR CALUX[®] cells, only one assay with triplicates was performed, based on the pre-test assay, as mentioned in the OECD guidelines (Section 3.6.1, ER α and AR assessment, p. 36). The Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity test and the thyroid disruption assay were performed in duplicate.

Data types

Two types of data have been collected in the SURPASS hazard assessment (Figure 3.8-1).

Figure 3.8-1: Two different types of data collected in SURPASS hazard assessment. (A) Determination of a EC₅₀ or a IC₅₀ over a range of concentration. (B) Evaluation of a biological response at specific concentrations.

In the case of assay over a range of concentrations (for cytotoxicity, endocrine disruption CALUX[®] assays, *Daphnia* immobilization, Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity test), no assessment of the statistical significance of the differences between the products was done. The EC₅₀ and IC₅₀ values were calculated using the GraphPad Prism software, by fitting the curves with 4PL models. In some cases, the 4PL fit did not give an acceptable trend curve and another model was used (Quadratic, for example). The fitting method is specified in the results sections and EC₅₀ or IC₅₀ were reported in the corresponding scoring table.

Note: For ER α and AR CALUX[®] analysis for case study 1 and 2, 4PL model was used for all EC₅₀ / IC₅₀ determinations.

Note2: For Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity test the EC₂₀ was determined using the PROAST software tool, as described in Section 3.7.2, Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET), p. 40.

In the case of the evaluation of a biological response at specific concentrations (for oxidative stress, epigenetics, cytokine responses, genotoxicity assays, and thyroid disruption), a series of statistical analysis were carried out, to compare the responses of:

- The negative and positive control to the solvent control.
*Statistical differences are marked with * if p value < 0.05*
- The tested products to the solvent control
*Statistical differences are marked with * if p value < 0.05*
- The tested products to the reference substance for specific group of substances
Statistical differences are marked with # if p value < 0.05

Note: If different concentrations were tested, analysis are performed for both conditions separately.

Note2: Negative control = cells that have not received anything

Solvent control = cells only exposed to the solvent of the specific substance (to correct for potential solvent effects)

Positive control = cells exposed to a substance that should give a response in the specific assay, used to determine whether the assay performed well.

Note3: For thyroid disruption the tested products were not compared to the reference substance for the specific groups of substances.

Statistical analysis performed

After identification of the outliers, data sets were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis with Dunn's multiple comparison test. If the Kruskal-Wallis test is not significant, no comparison between the products is possible, as the difference between the groups are not significant.

For the CS1 disulfide which has no substitute in the reference route, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used as the disulfide was compared only to the solvent control.

For the epigenetic modifications with HPLC-MS/MS assay, comparison between the positive control and its solvent control was performed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

4 Results CS1

In this chapter the results for case study 1 are described.

4.1 CS1 SSbD routes and tested substances

The SSbD routes of case study 1 and indicates which substances are part of which route are shown in Table 4.1-1. The case study substances and/or materials are divided into the different substance groups, namely polyols (Section 4.2), catalysts (Section 4.3), and the disulfide (Section 4.4). Table 4.1-2 indicates which assays were conducted for which substances.

Table 4.1-1: SSbD routes for hazard assessment of CS1. The routes correspond to those described in D4.2. An x indicates that the substance is part of this route.

SSbD Route number	Details	Catalysts			Disulfide	Polyols				
		CS1_16	CS1_26	CS1_18	CS1_08	CS1_05	CS1_01	CS1_02	CS1_03	CS1_04
		Bi-Cat	Cystamine	THEED	Disulfide	Polyol I	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D
Reference						x				
SSbD#0							x	x	x	x
N/A	SSbD#2 fossil based polyol				x	x				
SSbD#2					x		x	x	x	x
N/A	SSbD#1 fossil based polyol + Bi-Cat	x				x				
N/A	SSbD#1 fossil based polyol + Cystamine		x			x				
N/A	SSbD#1 fossil based polyol + THEED			x		x				
SSbD#1 Bi-Cat		x					x	x	x	x
SSbD#1 Cystamine			x				x	x	x	x
SSbD#1THEED				x			x	x	x	x

Table 4.1-2: Overview of assays conducted for the various CS1 substances. x = this assay was conducted for this substance; N/A = not applicable.

Health hazard	Endpoint	Assay	Exposure route	Bi-Cat	Cystamine	THEED	Disulfide	Polyol I	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	WST-1	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	WST-1	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Inhalation	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Inhalation	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	Alamar blue	Inhalation				x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	Alamar blue	Inhalation				x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Oxidative stress	CM-H2DCFDA	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Oxidative stress	CM-H2DCFDA	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Oxidative stress	ROS	Inhalation	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Oxidative stress	Protein carbonylation	Inhalation	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Epigenetic changes	Epigenetic changes	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Inflammation	Cytokine release	Inhalation	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Inflammation	Cytokine release	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Inflammation	Cytokine release	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	COMET	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	COMET	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	53BP1	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	53BP1	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Endocrine disruption	N/A	Calux battery AR/ER	N/A	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x
Endocrine disruption	N/A	Thyroid	N/A	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Ecotoxicity	N/A	Daphnia	N/A	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Ecotoxicity	N/A	Zebrafish	N/A	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

4.2 CS1 Polyols

The following polyols were tested in all test systems: polyol A, polyol B, polyol C, polyol D, and polyol I. Polyol I is the (fossil-based) reference material and the other four polyols are (bio-based) alternatives.

4.2.1 ECHA data

ECHA data were retrieved from the ECHA database of the ingredients of case study 1. For missing information, data were searched for in suppliers Safety Data Sheets (SDS) and / or literature.

Collected hazard data are presented in Table 4.2-1, Table 4.2-2 , and Table 4.2-3.

MISS = missing information, no data available.

NC = not classified as hazardous.

NA = not applicable

1, 2, 3 = ECHA hazard categories for substances classification.

Table 4.2-1: CS1 polyols ECHA data for human health hazards.

* = applicable to one of the ingredients.

	SURPASS ID	CS1_01	CS1_02	CS1_03	CS1_04	CS1_05
	Substance name	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D	Polyol I
Human health endpoint	Carcinogenicity	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Mutagenicity	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Reproduction toxicity	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Endocrine disruption (human)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Respiratory sensitization	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Specific organ toxicity Repeated exposure	NC	NC	NC	2 (H317)*	NC
	Skin Sensitization	NC	NC	NC	1 (H317)*	NC
	Acute toxicity oral	NC	NC	NC	4 (H302)	NC
	Acute toxicity dermal	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Acute toxicity inhalation	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Skin corrosion / irritation	NC	NC	NC	2 (H319)	NC
	Eye damage / irritation	NC	NC	NC	2 (H319)	NC
	Aspiration hazard	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Specific organ toxicity Single exposure	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC

Table 4.2-2: CS1 polyols ECHA data for environmental hazards.

	SURPASS ID	CS1_01	CS1_02	CS1_03	CS1_04	CS1_05
	Substance name	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D	Polyol I
Environmental Endpoint	persistence and bioaccumulation (PBT/vPvB)	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS
	persistence and mobility (PMT/vPvM)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	endocrine disruption (environment)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Ozone	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS
	Chronic aquatic toxicity	NC	NC	NC	MISS	MISS
	Acute aquatic toxicity	NC	NC	NC	MISS	MISS

Table 4.2-3: CS1 polyols ECHA data for physical hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS1_01	CS1_02	CS1_03	CS1_04	CS1_05
	Substance name	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D	Polyol I
Physical Endpoint	Explosives	MISS	NC	NC	MISS	NC
	Flammable	NA	NC	NC	MISS	NC
	Flammable aerosols	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS
	Oxidizing	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
	Gases under pressure	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS
	Self-reactive	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS
	Pyrophoric liquids, solids	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS
	Self-heating	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
	Emits flammable gas	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS
	Organic peroxides	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
	Corrosivity	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
	Desensitized explosives	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS

4.2.2 General human health

The assessment of human health hazard is based first on testing the cytotoxicity of the products in our models (Section 2.1). Indeed, cytotoxicity assays are used to select concentrations for the other in vitro assays. Those include oxidative stress evaluation, cytokine release and DNA methylation.

4.2.2.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity data from WST-1 assay with CS1 Polyols are presented below. HaCaT (dermal model) and Caco-2 (oral model) cells were tested with a wide concentration range of polyols. Cell viability results are shown in % with 100% being the non-treated cell viability (Figure 4.2-1).

Figure 4.2-1: Cytotoxicity results using WST-1 assay. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the reference polyol I and the alternative polyols A to D, on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 9$).

Results showed a higher cytotoxic effect with the alternative polyols A and C than with the reference polyol I. The ranking remained unchanged for both cell types. IC_{50} could be calculated by fitting the curves with a 4PL model and are listed in Table 4.2-4.

Table 4.2-4: IC_{50} values for cytotoxicity WST-1 assay (Fit with 4PL model)

Cell line	Polyol I	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D
HaCaT (skin cells)	2560 µg/mL	578 µg/mL	2675 µg/mL	26 µg/mL	2504 µg/mL
Caco-2 (gut cells)	1744 µg/mL	369 µg/mL	2261 µg/mL	28 µg/mL	2329 µg/mL

According to the cytotoxicity results, two polyol concentrations were chosen for further testing. First, an equimolar non-toxic dose was identified to compare the products at same concentration. Then, 80% survival dose (or equi-toxicity concentration) was used to compare the products at same cytotoxic effect. Depending on the confluence and culture conditions specific to each test, the concentrations had to be slightly corrected for polyols A and C. These concentrations are shown in Table 4.2-5.

Note: For oxidative stress on HaCaT and Caco-2 cells, the equimolar concentrations were not tested. Indeed, large differences between the cytotoxicity responses of the products were observed (a factor

of >10 between IC₅₀ of polyols A and C, and a factor of >60 between IC₅₀ of polyols B,D,I compared to polyol C). The study of oxidative stress therefore focused on the worst-case scenario.

Table 4.2-5: CS1 Polyol working concentrations chosen for the oral and dermal models.

Cell line	Cell confluence during the treatment	Equimolar concentrations	Equi-toxicity concentrations
HaCaT (skin cells)	> 80% confluence	not tested	300 µg/mL Polyol A 25 µg/mL Polyol C 1000 µg/mL Polyols B,D,I
	< 80% confluence	15 µg/mL	150-200 µg/mL Polyol A 15-30 µg/mL Polyol C 1000 µg/mL Polyols B,D,I
Caco-2 (gut cells)	> 80% confluence	not tested	200 µg/mL Polyol A 5 µg/mL Polyol C 1000 µg/mL Polyols B,D,I
	< 80% confluence	15 µg/mL	100-300 µg/mL Polyol A 15-30 µg/mL Polyol C 1000 µg/mL Polyols B,D,I

LDH Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay measuring the LDH release in cell supernatant was performed in parallel to the WST-1 assay (oral and dermal model) or Alamar Blue (inhalation models).

For the polyol products, the results of this method assessing cytotoxicity for the oral and dermal model were very consistent with those obtained with WST-1 assay: the decline in cell viability occurred at the same polyol concentrations in both assays (Figure 4.2-2). This may be an indication that the polyols have an effect on membrane integrity and that their respective cytotoxicity is due to their detergent-like effect.

However, for all other SURPASS products, it appears that the LDH assay is less sensitive than the WST-1 assay: with the WST-1 test, the decrease in cell viability is observed earlier than with the LDH test, meaning that the metabolic activity of the mitochondria is affected before the increase in permeability of the cell membranes. LDH assay was therefore used as a control for cytotoxicity results but IC₅₀ were not calculated for this assessment method.

Figure 4.2-2: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the reference polyol I and the alternative polyols A to D, on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 9$).

In the inhalation cell models, cytotoxic effects of the polyols were measured using the LDH assay after 24h exposure to a range of concentrations (Figure 4.2-3). Similar results were obtained for the two cell lines used, A549 alveolar epithelial cells and dTHP-1 macrophage-like cells. Polyols D and A showed the higher cytotoxic potential, followed by the reference polyol I, and polyols B and C showed no effects on cell survival at the tested concentration. IC₅₀ could be calculated by fitting the curves and are listed in Table 4.2-6.

Figure 4.2-3: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Percentage of cell viability compared to the non-treated cells with the reference polyol I and the alternative polyols A to D, on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are mean \pm SEM ($n=3$).

Table 4.2-6: IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity LDH assay in the inhalation models

Cell line	Polyol I	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D
A549	1401 µg/mL	224.4 µg/mL	>1000 µg/mL	>1000 µg/mL	35.3 µg/mL
THP-1	992.9 µg/mL	219.4 µg/mL	>1000 µg/mL	>1000 µg/mL	42.6 µg/mL

AlamarBlue

In the inhalation cell models, cytotoxic effects of the polyols were also measured using the AlamarBlue assay after 24h exposure to a range of concentration (Figure 4.2-4). The results obtained are very

similar to the ones from the LDH assay, maintaining the toxicity ranking unchanged for both cell. IC₅₀ could be calculated by fitting the curves and are listed in Table 4.2-7.

Figure 4.2-4: Cytotoxicity results using AlamarBlue measurement. Percentage of cell viability compared to the non-treated cells with the reference polyol I and the alternative polyols A to D, on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are mean ± SEM (n=3).

Table 4.2-7: IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity AlamarBlue assay in the inhalation models

Cell line	Polyol I	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D
A549	1461 µg/mL	342.8 µg/mL	>1000 µg/mL	>1000 µg/mL	37.9 µg/mL
THP-1	>1000 µg/mL	227.9 µg/mL	>1000 µg/mL	>1000 µg/mL	46.1 µg/mL

4.2.2.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay

All CS1 polyols were tested for oxidative stress simultaneously, at equitoxic concentrations, for the oral and dermal model.

CM-H₂DCFDA results showed a significant induction of oxidative stress with Polyol A on both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells with a response reaching respectively 84% and 41% of the positive control value (Figure 4.2-5). A slight response (26% of the positive control value) was also observed with the reference polyol I on Caco-2 cells, however, this increase was not statistically significant compared to the solvent control. Polyols B, C and D showed for their part not variation of oxidative stress compared to the solvent control at the tested concentrations in either HaCaT or Caco-2 cell lines.

Figure 4.2-5: CM-H₂DCFDA assay comparing CS1 polyols on HaCaT cells (A) and on Caco-2 cells (B). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥9).

Cellular ROS assay

In the inhalation A549 cell model, ROS production as a measure of oxidative stress was assessed after exposure to the polyol compounds at equitoxic concentrations corresponding to the calculated IC₅₀ and IC₂₀ (Figure 4.2-6). As no IC₅₀ could be calculated for them, Polyols B and C were tested at the maximum concentration tested in the cytotoxicity assays, which matches the IC₅₀ concentration for the reference Polyol I. Results showed significantly increased ROS levels after Polyol A exposure (IC₂₀ and IC₅₀) when compared to SC and also Polyol A produces significant higher levels of ROS than the reference substance Polyol I (comparing between equivalent doses). Polyol D showed significantly decreased ROS levels than both SC and Polyol I when treated at IC₅₀ concentration.

Figure 4.2-6. ROS levels after exposure to polyols. A549 cells were exposed to the polyol compounds and ROS production was assessed after 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h and 5h. Percentage of ROS production compared to the solvent control (SC) with the reference polyol I and the alternative polyols A to D and the positive control (PC). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to SC, and # indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to reference substance Polyol I.

Protein carbonylation

Effects of the exposure to the polyol compounds on protein carbonylation levels as an indication of oxidative stress was also assessed in the inhalation model using A549+dTHP-1 ALI co-cultures. Cells were exposed by nebulization to equivalent doses of each polyol ($30 \mu\text{g}/\text{insert} = 27 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) for 24h. The exact deposited dose was determined based on the collected QCM signal along the sedimentation process, and calculated as the mean value of the 30 last seconds collected (Figure 4.2-7A). Although the nebulised solutions were prepared at the same final volume and at the same concentration, the Polyol D showed a much higher deposited dose, almost double than the rest of compounds, that might be due to a technical problem during the deposition recording or to a higher density of the polyol D solution.

Cytotoxicity and monolayer integrity after the exposures were assessed as supplementary information of the state of the co-cultures. Analysis of the cytotoxicity levels achieved after the exposure showed significant differences between the Polyol D and the reference substance Polyol I, which might be due to the higher deposited dose detected (Figure 4.2-7B). No significant differences in cytotoxicity were detected between the treated conditions and the solvent control, although the deposited dose was equivalent to the IC₂₀ calculated in the monocultures. Effect of the exposures on the transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) was also assessed. The TEER value expressed as $\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$ can be used to monitor the formation of tight junctions and evaluate the integrity of cell monolayers. TEER was measured before and after the exposure to polyols to calculate the difference (Figure 4.2-7C), therefore positive values indicate a decrease in the TEER value after treatment and affectation of the monolayer integrity. Results showed no significant differences between the conditions, with little variation between the TEER values recorded before and after treatment.

The analysis of protein carbonyl content informs about the oxidative stress produced by the compounds exposures. When comparing the treatment conditions with the polyols to the solvent control, no significant differences were observed (Figure 4.2-7D).

Figure 4.2-7. Polyols effect on protein carbonylation after 24h exposure in a co-culture inhalation model. **A)** Calculated deposited dose for each nebulised condition. **B)** Percentage of cytotoxicity obtained after polyols exposure in comparison to the SC = solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to solvent control, and # indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to reference substance Polyol I. **C)** Membrane integrity of the co-culture exposure in comparison to the solvent control, expressed as the difference between the TEER value before exposure – TEER value after exposure.

Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). **D)** Percentage of protein carbonylation compared to the solvent control after 24h exposure. Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3).

4.2.2.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS

Modulation of cytosine methylation in total DNA after treatment of Caco-2 cells with the CS1 polyols was assessed using HPLC-MS/MS. The percentage of 5-methylcytosine was divided by a factor 2 upon incubating the positive control (5 μ M of 5-Azaytidine). However, no change in methylation status was observed either with the reference polyol I or with the alternative polyols A to D at the tested concentrations (Figure 4.2-8).

For this assay, only the equitoxicity concentrations were tested. As no response was observed, assesment at the same, lower, concentrations was not necessary.

Figure 4.2-8: HPLC-MS/MS assay assessing the part of methylated Cytosine in total DNA after incubation with the reference and the alternative polyols, on Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values (n \geq 9).

4.2.2.4 Inflammation

Cytokine measurement of the inhalation model

The inhalation model using A549+dTHP-1 ALI co-cultures was used to measure the potential pro-inflammatory effect of the polyols. Medium samples after exposure to equitoxic concentrations of the polyols were collected to detect levels of secreted cytokines TNF- α and IL-6, which have been described relevant in the cell lines used. Very low levels of secreted cytokines were detected in the treated conditions or in the solvent control (below 20 pg/mL), only the LPS positive control showed high cytokine release (Figure 4.2-9). The percentages of secreted cytokines in the polyol conditions did not significantly differ from the solvent control.

Figure 4.2-9. Pro-inflammatory cytokines secreted 24h after the polyol exposures. Secreted TNF- α (A) and IL-6 (B) were detected by ELISA. Graphs show quantity of each cytokine in pg/mL (left panels) and the percentage of secreted cytokine compared to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to solvent control.

Cytokine measurement of the oral and dermal model

Also for the oral model (CaCo2 cells) and the dermal model (HaCat cells) the potential inflammatory response of the polyols was measured. Medium samples after exposure to the polyols were collected to detect levels of cytokines and chemokines (IFN- γ , IL-1b, IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL12p70, IL-17A, IP10, MCP-1, TGB- β 1, TNF- α).

In the oral model, secretion of most cytokines or chemokines were under the detection limit or showed no effect. Only the secretion of IL-8 was significantly different in the polyol C exposed samples compared to the levels in the solvent control (Figure 4.2-10).

Figure 4.2-10. IL-8 secretion in the CS1 polyols measured in medium samples of the oral model (CaCo2). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, *** indicates $p < 0.005$.

In the dermal model, secretion of IL-4, IL-6 and IL-8 were significantly different for polyol A compared to the solvent control (Figure 4.2-11). Additionally, MCP-1 was significantly decreased in polyol I exposed samples compared to the solvent control. The other 9 tested cytokines and chemokines did not show an effect or were below the detection limit.

Figure 4.2-11: Secretion of IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, and MCP-1 in the CS1 polyols measured in medium of the dermal model (HaCat). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, * indicates $p < 0.05$; *** indicates $p < 0.005$.

4.2.3 Genotoxicity

The assessment of genotoxicity is based on testing DNA damage in the dermal and oral model. To this end, two different assays were carried out. The induction of DNA strand breaks after cell treatment was assessed using the Comet assay, while the focus was on double strand breaks in 53BP1 assay.

Genotoxicity results showed no clear variation in the number of 53BP1 foci with the polyols, except for Polyol C at 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ on HaCaT cells (Figure 4.2-12, A) for which a decrease of 2-fold the solvent control in 53BP1 foci was observed. However, this has to be taken carefully as this treatment showed

larger cytotoxic effect as expected (about 60% instead of 80% survival). Accordingly, no decrease in 53BP1 value was observed at 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in the same cell line.

Figure 4.2-12: 53BP1 assay comparing reference polyol I and alternative polyols A to D, on HaCaT cells (A) and on Caco-2 cells (B). Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values ($n \geq 12$).

No induction of single and double-strand breaks was observed in cells exposed to CS1 polyols (Figure 4.2-13). Altogether, the genotoxic stress can be considered as negligible for the tested polyols.

Figure 4.2-13: Comet assay comparing reference polyol I and alternative polyols A to D, on HaCaT cells (A) and on Caco-2 cells (B). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥12).

4.2.4 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

Agonist test

The pre-test of the CALUX[®] agonist assay showed no binding of the polyols on the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α) and the Androgen Receptor (AR), in the investigated range of concentrations (Figure 4.2-14). CS1 polyols are not considered as agonist disruptors for ER α and AR.

Figure 4.2-14. AR agonist (A) and ER α agonist (B) assay with the CS1 Polyols. Reported values are means \pm SD (n \geq 3)

Antagonist test

Results showed no antagonist effect of CS1 polyols on the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α), except for polyol A which gave a slight inhibition (79% of relative induction at the highest tested concentration). However, its specific antagonist disruption potential on ER α was not confirmed by the complete testing with specificity test (Figure 4.2-15, B), as the inhibition remained identical despite the presence of the agonist reference in various concentration.

For the Androgen Receptor (AR), polyols A and C showed a clear effect (respectively 55% and 60% relative induction at highest tested concentration), whereas the other tested polyols were negative (Figure 4.2-15, A). A complete testing with specificity test was performed for polyols A and C. Comparison of the test to its specificity control ruled out an antagonist response for both polyols.

Figure 4.2-15. AR antagonist (A) and ER α antagonist (B) assay with the CS1 Polyols. Reported values are means \pm SD (n \geq 3)

Thyroid disruption assay

Assessment of thyroid disruption potential of the polyols using the transgenic zebrafish line *tg(tg:mCherry)* are shown below. Based on the performed ZFET (Section 4.2.5) subtoxic concentrations were selected: polyol A, B, and C were tested at 3 μ g/ml, polyol D at 600 μ g/ml and polyol I at 300

µg/ml. No induction of the fluorescent signal was observed in the transgenic zebrafish line for the tested polyols (Figure 4.2-16).

Figure 4.2-16: Thyroid disruption assay for CS1 polyols. Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, * indicates $p < 0.05$; **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

4.2.5 Aquatic toxicity

Daphnia magna

Immobilization data in *Daphnia magna* individuals following OECD 202 test guideline assessing CS1 Polyols are presented below. Maximum tested concentration of all test substances was 100 mg/L, as indicated in the OECD 202 guideline and mentioned before. Immobilization data results are shown in % of motility (mobile *daphnias*), being 100% no effects (no toxicity) and 0% being complete immobilization (maximum toxicity) (Figure 4.2-17).

Figure 4.2-17: 24 (A) and 48h (B) immobilization results in *Daphnia magna* (OECD 202) for the CS1 polyols. Reported values are expressed as means \pm SEM ($n \geq 3$).

Alternative polyols A and C showed higher toxic effects (in the motility of daphnids) than the reference polyol I. Although $EC_{50,48h}$ of polyol B is >100 mg/L its toxicity can be observed at the highest

concentration. In case of polyol D, it is statistically equal to the reference polyol (polyol I), and it did not present any toxicity effects up to 100 mg/L, the limit of the test. EC₅₀ values were calculated both at 24 and 48h by fitting the curves to a sigmoidal regression and are listed in Table 4.2-8.

Table 4.2-8: EC₅₀ immobilization values at 24 and 48h for acute aquatic toxicity test (OECD 202) in CS1 polyols.

Timepoint	Polyol I (reference)	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D
24h	> 100 mg/L	> 100 mg/L	> 100 mg/L	15.2 mg/L	> 100 mg/L
48h	> 100 mg/L	65.1 mg/L	> 100 mg/L	10.2 mg/L	> 100 mg/L

Zebrafish

As a measure for aquatic toxicity, and as range finding experiment for the thyroid disruption assay, a Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test was performed. The maximum tested concentrations was 30 µg/ml for polyol A, B, and C, and 600 µg/ml for polyol D and I.

Figure 4.2-18: Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test for CS1 polyols. Reported values represent a single zebrafish embryo.

For polyol D no effect on zebrafish embryo morphology was observed (Figure 4.2-18). Alternative polyols A, B, and C showed higher effects to embryonic morphology and development than the reference polyol I. EC₂₀s were calculated using the PROAST software, as described in Section 3.7.2, and shown in the Table 4.2-9.

Table 4.2-9: EC₂₀ values determined by ZFET for the CS1 polyols.

Polyol I (reference)	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D
313.2 µg/mL	10.02 µg/mL	7.629 µg/mL	12.37 µg/mL	> 600 µg/mL

4.2.6 Short summary

Polyol I is the fossil-based reference substance, whereas Polyols A, b, C and D are the bio-based alternative substances. In summary, polyol A induces cytotoxicity in all cell models used, whereas polyol C (dermal and oral models) and polyol D (inhalation model) induce cytotoxicity in specific models only. In addition, polyol A also induces an oxidative stress response in all assays. Polyol I (dermal model), Polyol A (dermal model), polyol C (oral model) were found to affect cytokine secretion. Aquatotoxic effects are consistently found for polyols A, B and C in both models used. No further hazards were identified for the polyols.

4.3 CS1 Catalysts

Three different compounds are tested within the group of the catalysts of case study 1: Bi-Cat, cystamine and THEED. Here, Bi-Cat is the reference substance and the other two are alternatives.

4.3.1 ECHA data

ECHA data were retrieved from the ECHA database of the ingredients. For missing information, data were searched for in suppliers Safety Data Sheets (SDS) and / or literature.

Collected hazard data are presented in Table 4.3-1, Table 4.3-2, Table 4.3-3.

MISS = missing information, no data available.

NC = not classified as hazardous.

NA = not applicable

1, 2, 3 = ECHA hazard categories for substances classification.

Table 4.3-1: CS1 catalysts ECHA data for human health hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS1_16	CS1_18	CS1_26
	Substance name	Bismuth neodecanoate	N,N,N',N'-Tetrakis-(2-hydroxyethyl)-ethylenediamine (THEED)	Cystamine
Human health endpoint	Carcinogenicity	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Mutagenicity	NC	MISS	MISS
	Reproduction toxicity	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Endocrine disruption (human)	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Respiratory sensitization	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Specific organ toxicity Repeated exposure	NC	MISS	MISS
	Skin Sensitization	NC	MISS	MISS
	Acute toxicity oral	NC	MISS	4 (H302)
	Acute toxicity dermal	NC	MISS	MISS
	Acute toxicity inhalation	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Skin corrosion / irritation	NC	2 (H315)	MISS
	Eye damage / irritation	NC	1 (H318)	MISS
	Aspiration hazard	NC	MISS	MISS
Specific organ toxicity Single exposure	NC	MISS	MISS	

Table 4.3-2: CS1 catalysts ECHA data for environmental hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS1_16	CS1_18	CS1_26
	Substance name	Bismuth neodecanoate	N,N,N',N'-Tetrakis-(2-hydroxyethyl)-ethylenediamine (THEED)	Cystamine
Environmental Endpoint	persistence and bioaccumulation (PBT/vPvB)	NA	MISS	MISS
	persistence and mobility (PMT/vPvM)	MISS	MISS	MISS
	endocrine disruption (environment)	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Ozone	NC	MISS	MISS
	Chronic aquatic toxicity	NC	MISS	MISS
	Acute aquatic toxicity	NC	MISS	MISS

Table 4.3-3: CS1 catalysts ECHA data for physical hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS1_16	CS1_18	CS1_26
	Substance name	Bismuth neodecanoate	N,N,N',N'-Tetrakis-(2-hydroxyethyl)-ethylenediamine (THEED)	Cystamine
Physical Endpoint	Explosives	NC	NC	MISS
	Flammable	NC	NC	NC
	Flammable aerosols	NC	NC	NC
	Oxidizing	NC	NC	NC
	Gases under pressure	NC	NC	NC
	Self-reactive	NC	NC	MISS
	Pyrophoric liquids, solids	NC	NC	MISS
	Self-heating	NC	NC	MISS
	Emits flammable gas	NC	NC	MISS
	Organic peroxides	NC	NC	MISS
	Corrosivity	NC	MISS	MISS
	Desensitized explosives	NC	MISS	MISS

4.3.2 General human health

The assessment of the risks to human health is based first on testing the cytotoxicity of the products in our models (Section 2.1). Indeed, cytotoxicity assays are used to select concentrations for the other in vitro assays. Those include oxidative stress evaluation, cytokine release and DNA methylation.

4.3.2.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity data from WST-1 assay with CS1 catalysts for the dermal and oral model are presented in Figure 4.3-1. HaCaT (dermal model) and Caco-2 (oral model) cells were tested with a wide concentration range of catalysts. Cell viability results are shown in % with 100% being the non-treated cell viability.

Figure 4.3-1: Cytotoxicity results using WST-1 assay. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the reference catalyst Bi-Cat and the alternative products (Cystamine and THEED), on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 7$).

Results showed a higher cytotoxic effect with the reference substance Bi-Cat than with the alternative catalysts Cystamine and THEED. IC_{50} could be calculated by fitting the curves with a 4PL model for the reference catalyst Bi-Cat and with a quadratic model for the alternative products. Values are listed in Table 4.3-4.

Table 4.3-4: IC_{50} values for cytotoxicity in WST-1 assay. Fit with 4PL model for the reference catalyst Bi-Cat and with quadratic model for the alternative products.

Cell line	Bi-Cat	Cystamine	THEED
HaCaT (dermal model)	358 μ M	2257 μ M	4397 μ M
Caco-2 (oral model)	471 μ M	2524 μ M	2637 μ M

According to the cytotoxicity results, an 80% survival dose (or equi-toxicity concentration) was used to compare the products at same cytotoxic effect. As the results obtained for the CS1 Catalysts showed no effects at these equi-toxicity concentrations (following paragraphs), no testing at equimolar concentration (i.e. lower concentration) was considered necessary (Table 4.3-5).

Table 4.3-5: CS2 Hardener working concentrations chosen.

Cell line	Cell confluence during the treatment	Equi-toxicity concentrations
HaCaT (dermal model)	> 80% confluence	250 μ M Bi-Cat 1500 μ M Cystamine, THEED
	< 80% confluence	200 μ M Bi-Cat 1000 μ M Cystamine, THEED
Caco-2 (oral model)	> 80% confluence	400 μ M Bi-Cat 1500 μ M Cystamine, THEED
	< 80% confluence	100 μ M Bi-Cat 1000 μ M Cystamine, THEED

LDH Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay measuring the LDH release in cell supernatant was performed in parallel to the WST-1 assay (oral and dermal model) or Alamar Blue (inhalation models).

The results of this second method assessing cytotoxicity for the oral and dermal model confirmed those obtained with WST-1 assay, despite the more difficult analysis of the raw data (Figure 4.3-2). At high concentrations, the reference catalyst interfered with the assay method on Caco-2 cells, as microscopy observation shows a complete mortality of the cell culture wells. LDH assay was therefore used as a control for cytotoxicity results but IC₅₀ were not calculated for this assessment method.

Figure 4.3-2: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the reference catalyst Bi-Cat and the alternative products (Cystamine and THEED), on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians ± interquartile (n ≥ 9).

In the inhalation cell models, cytotoxic effects of the catalysts were measured using the LDH assay after 24h exposure to a range of concentrations (Figure 4.3-3). The low cytotoxicity values obtained for both A549 alveolar epithelial cells and dTHP-1, did not allow to obtain good curve fitting and IC₅₀ were estimated higher than 200 µg/mL for the three compounds tested (Table 4.3-6), which showed very similar cytotoxicity curves.

Table 4.3-6: IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity LDH assay in the inhalation models.

Cell line	Bi-Cat	Cystamine	THEED
A549	> 200 µg/mL	> 200 µg/mL	> 200 µg/mL
THP-1	> 200 µg/mL	> 200 µg/mL	> 200 µg/mL

Figure 4.3-3. Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Percentage of cell viability compared to the non-treated cells with the reference Bi-Cat and the alternative Cystamine and THEED, on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3).

4.3.2.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay

Reference and alternative catalysts were tested for oxidative stress simultaneously, at one single concentration corresponding the equi-toxicity concentration defined in WST-1 assay (Section 4.3.2.1, Cytotoxicity, p. 64).

CM-H₂DCFDA results showed an induction of oxidative stress with the reference catalyst Bi-Cat at 60% and 83% in respectively HaCaT and Caco-2 cells. For alternative catalysts Cystamine and THEED, no significant increase of oxidative stress was observed (Figure 4.3-4).

Figure 4.3-4: CM-H₂DCFDA assay comparing CS1 catalysts on (A) HaCaT and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values (n \geq 8).

On Caco-2, the experimental window framed by the solvent and the positive control was smaller than with HaCaT cells, due to a lower response from the positive control. As a result, the test is less sensitive

than with the HaCaT cells, and the differences in the induction of oxidative stress are more difficult to assess.

Cellular ROS assay

In the inhalation A549 cell model, ROS production as a measure of oxidative stress was assessed after exposure to the catalyst compounds at equimolar concentrations corresponding to the maximum concentration tested in the cytotoxicity assays (200 µg/mL). Results after 2h exposure, showed significantly increased ROS levels for all the catalyst compounds when compared to solvent control. Cystamine also produces significantly higher levels of ROS than the reference substance Bi-Cat (Figure 4.3-5).

Figure 4.3-5. ROS levels after exposure to catalysts. A549 cells were exposed to the catalyst compounds and ROS production was assessed after 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h and 5h. Percentage of ROS production compared to solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC) with the reference Bi-Cat and the alternative Cystamine and THEED. Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to solvent control, and # indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to reference substance Bi-Cat.

Protein carbonylation

Effects of the exposure to the catalysts compounds on protein carbonylation levels as an indication of oxidative stress was also assessed in the inhalation model using A549+dTHP-1 ALI co-cultures. Cells were exposed to equivalent doses of each catalyst (70 µg/insert) for 24h. The required concentrations to reach EC20 were not compatible with the VitroCell system due to the high concentration of DMSO in the final solution. Therefore, instead of nebulizing the compounds they were applied in a semi-ALI setting using a 100 µL volume per insert.

Cytotoxicity and monolayer integrity after the exposures were assessed as supplementary information of the state of the co-cultures. Analysis of the cytotoxicity levels achieved after the exposure showed no significant differences between the catalysts and the solvent control (Figure 4.3-6, B). TEER was measured before and after the exposure to calculate the difference (Figure 4.3-6, A), therefore positive values indicate a decrease in the TEER value after treatment and affection of the monolayer integrity. Results showed no significant differences between the conditions, with little variation between the TEER values recorded before and after treatment.

The analysis of protein carbonyl content showed that, when comparing the treatment conditions with the catalysts to the solvent control, no significant differences were observed (Figure 4.3-6, C). Furthermore, little effect was obtained with the positive control.

Figure 4.3-6. Catalysts effect on protein carbonylation after 24h exposure in a co-culture inhalation model. **A)** Membrane integrity of the co-culture exposure in comparison to the NTC, expressed as the difference between the TEER value before exposure – TEER value after exposure. Reported values are mean ± SEM (n=3). **B)** Percentage of cytotoxicity obtained after catalysts exposure in comparison to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC). Reported values are mean ± SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed, * indicates p < 0.05 compared to solvent control, and # indicates p < 0.05 compared to reference substance Bi-Cat. **D)** Percentage of protein carbonylation compared to the solvent control after 24h exposure. Reported values are mean ± SEM (n=3).

4.3.2.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS

Modulation of cytosine methylation in total DNA after treatment of Caco-2 cells with the CS1 catalysts was assessed using HPLC-MS/MS. The percentage of 5-methylcytosine was divided by a factor 2 upon incubating the positive control (5µM of 5-Azaytidine). However, no change in methylation status was observed either with the reference catalyst or with the alternative products (Figure 4.3-7).

Figure 4.3-7: HPLC-MS/MS assay assessing the part of methylated Cytosine in total DNA after incubation with the reference and the alternative catalysts, on Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values (n \geq 9).

4.3.2.4 Inflammation

Cytokine measurement of the inhalation model

The inhalation model using A549+dTHP-1 ALI co-cultures was used to measure the potential pro-inflammatory effect of the CS1 catalysts. After exposure, medium samples were collected to detect levels of secreted cytokines TNF- α and IL-6. Very low levels of secreted cytokines were detected in the treated conditions or in the solvent control and only the LPS positive control showed high cytokine expression. The percentages of secreted cytokines after exposure to any of the catalysts did not significantly differ from the solvent control (Figure 4.3-8).

Figure 4.3-8. Pro-inflammatory cytokines secreted 24h after the catalysts exposure. Secreted TNF- α (A,B) and IL-6 (C,D) were detected by ELISA. Graphs show quantity of each cytokine in pg/mL (A and C panels) and the percentage of secreted cytokine compared to the SC = solvent control and the positive control (PC) (B and D panels). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed.

Cytokine measurement of the oral and dermal model

The oral model (CaCo2 cells) and the dermal model (HaCat cells) were used to measure the potential inflammatory response of the catalysts Bi-Cat, cystamine and THEED. After exposure of the cells to the catalysts, medium samples were collected to detect levels of cytokines and chemokines (IFN- γ , IL-1b, IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL12p70, IL-17A, IP10, MCP-1, TGB- β 1, TNF- α).

In the oral model, secretion of most cytokines or chemokines were under the detection limit or showed no effect. Only the secretion of IL-8 was significantly different in samples exposed to cystamine compared to the levels in the solvent control (Figure 4.3-9).

Figure 4.3-9. IL-8 secretion in the CS1 catalysts measured in medium samples of the oral model (CaCo2 cells). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, * indicates $p < 0.05$

In the dermal model, secretion of IL-8 and MCP-1 was significantly different for both Bi-Cat and cystamine compared to the solvent control (Figure 4.3-10). IL-8 secretion was significantly increased, where MCP-1 secretion was significantly decreased. Additionally, IL-6 was significantly different in samples exposed to cystamine compared to the solvent control (Figure 4.3-10). The other 10 measured cytokines and chemokines did not show an effect or were below the detection limit (data not shown).

Figure 4.3-10. IL-6, IL-8, and MCP-1 secretion in the CS1 catalysts measured in medium samples of the dermal model (HaCat cells). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, * indicates $p < 0.05$; ** indicates $p < 0.01$; *** indicates $p < 0.005$; **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

4.3.3 Genotoxicity

The assessment of genotoxicity is based on testing DNA damage in the oral and dermal model. To this end, two different assays were carried out. The induction of DNA strand breaks after cell treatment was assessed using comet assay, while the focus was on double strand breaks in 53BP1 assay.

Genotoxicity results showed an increase in the number of 53BP1 foci with cystamine at the tested concentration (2.77 foci per cell) compared to the solvent control (1.25 foci per cell) in HaCaT cells (Figure 4.3-11, A₁). The observation of cystamine response in Caco-2 (Figure 4.3-11, A₂), however, did

not show a similar effect. It may be added that small and non-significant variations compared to the solvent control, most of the times decreases, were observed in comet assays on both cell lines (Figure 4.3-11, B). Further tests should be conducted to determine whether cystamine is a genotoxicant. However, a decreased response is not considered a potential genotoxic hazard.

Figure 4.3-11: 53BP1 assay (A) and comet assay (B) comparing the reference catalyst Bi-Cat with the alternative catalysts. Assays are done on HaCaT cells (A₁ and B₁) and on Caco-2 cells (A₂ and B₂). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥12).

4.3.4 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

Agonist test

The pre-tests of the CALUX[®] agonist assay showed no binding of the CS1 catalysts on the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α) and the Androgen Receptor (AR), in the investigated range of concentrations (Figure 4.3-12).

Figure 4.3-12: (A) AR and (B) ER α agonist assay with catalysts. Reported values are means \pm SD ($n \geq 3$).

Antagonist test

Results showed no antagonist effect of alternative catalysts on either the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α) or the Androgen Receptor (AR) (Figure 4.3-13). For the reference catalyst Bi-Cat, an inhibition was observed on both receptors, with a relative induction of 61% on ER α and of 19% on AR at highest concentration. A complete testing with specificity test was performed and the comparison of the test to its specificity control ruled out an antagonist response of Bi-Cat for the AR receptor, as both curves had a good correlation ($R^2 = 0.9825$). In contrast the specificity test confirmed the antagonist effect for Bi-Cat on ER α , with an observed shift of the two Bi-Cat curves ($R^2 = -6.707$).

B

	Disruption potential on ER α		Disruption potential on AR	
	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)
Reference control	5.77E-12 M	1.18E-08 M	2.58E-10 M	5.87E-05 M
Bi-cat	> 1E-04 M	7.69E-05 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-03 M
Cystamine	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M
THEED	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M

Figure 4.3-13: (A) ER α antagonist assay with the reference catalyst Bi-Cat. Reported values are means \pm SD ($n \geq 3$). (B) EC₅₀ and IC₅₀ values for ER α and AR assays. Curve fitting done with a 4PL model.

Thyroid disruption assay

Assessment of thyroid disruption potential of the catalysts using the transgenic zebrafish line *tg(tg:mCherry)* are shown in Figure 4.3-14. Based on the performed ZFET (Section 4.3.5) subtoxic

concentrations were selected: Bi-Cat was tested at 0.3 µg/ml, cystamine at 1 mM and THEED at 600 µg/ml. No induction of the fluorescent signal was observed in the transgenic zebrafish line for the tested catalysts.

Figure 4.3-14: Thyroid disruption assay for the CS1 catalysts. Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

4.3.5 Aquatic toxicity

Daphnia magna

Immobilization data in *Daphnia magna* individuals from OECD 202 assays with CS1 catalysts are presented below. Maximum tested concentration of all test substances was 100 mg/L, as indicated in the OECD 202 guideline and mentioned before. Immobilization data results are shown in % of motility (mobile daphnias), being 100% no effects (no toxicity) and 0% being complete immobilization (maximum toxicity).

Figure 4.3-15: 24 (A) and 48h (B) immobilization results in *Daphnia magna* (OECD 202) for the CS1 catalysts. Reported values are expressed as means \pm SEM ($n \geq 3$).

As observed, alternative catalyst THEED did not present any toxic effect up to 100 mg/L, similarly to the reference catalyst (Bi-cat), as shown in Figure 4.3-15. On the other hand, cystamine presented a moderate-high toxicity with an EC₅₀ value of 16.4 and 12.7 mg/L at 24h and 48h, respectively.

All EC₅₀ values both at 24 and 48h were obtained by fitting the curves to a sigmoidal regression and are listed in Table 4.3-7.

Table 4.3-7: EC₅₀ immobilization values at 24 and 48h for acute aquatic toxicity test (OECD 202) in CS1 catalysts.

Timepoint	Bi-cat (reference)	Cystamine	THEED
24h	> 100 mg/L	16.4 mg/L	> 100 mg/L
48h	> 100 mg/L	12.7 mg/L	> 100 mg/L

Zebrafish

As a measure for aquatic toxicity, and as range finding experiment for the thyroid disruption assay, a Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test was performed. The maximum tested concentrations was 30 µg/ml for Bi-Cat, 1 mM for cystamine and 600 µg/ml for THEED.

Figure 4.3-16: Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test for the CS1 catalysts.

For both cystamine and THEED no effect on zebrafish embryo morphology was observed (Figure 4.3-16). However, the reference substance Bi-Cat did show effects on embryonic morphology and development. EC₂₀ values were calculated using the PROAST software, as described in Section 3.7.2, and shown in Table 4.3-8.

Table 4.3-8: Established EC₂₀ values in the ZFET for the CS1 catalysts.

Bi-Cat (reference)	Cystamine	THEED
3.354 µg/mL	>1 mM	>600 µg/mL

4.3.6 Short summary

All catalysts are used in the alternative routes. Of the catalysts tested, Bi-Cat was most cytotoxic, but only in dermal and oral cell models, not inhalation models. Furthermore, Bi-Cat induced oxidative stress (all models), effects on cytokine secretion (dermal model only), potential endocrine disruption

and effects on zebrafish. Cystamine induced oxidative stress (inhalation model only), effects on cytokine secretion (dermal and oral models), potential genotoxicity (dermal model only, should be further assessed to confirm) and effects on Daphnia mobility. THEED was the least responsive catalysts in the assays used, only resulting in oxidative stress in the inhalation model. No further hazards were identified for the catalysts.

4.4 CS1 Disulfide

This 'group' contains one compound and does not have a reference material, as this compound could be an addition to the product. The related substances, iso-PDMI 92410 (all production routes), Niax catalyst A-1 (all production routes), Niax silicone L-6642 (biobased production routes) and FR CROS 484 (biobased production routes), were second priority (see 1.3) and therefore not included for in vitro testing. In vitro experimental data is therefore only available for 2-Hydroxyethyl disulfide (CS1_08)

4.4.1 ECHA data

ECHA data were retrieved from the ECHA database of the ingredients. For missing information, data were searched for in suppliers Safety Data Sheets (SDS) and / or literature.

Collected hazard data are presented in the following

Table 4.4-1, Table 4.4-2, Table 4.4-3.

MISS = missing information, no data available.

NC = not classified as hazardous.

NA = not applicable

1, 2, 3 = ECHA hazard categories for substances classification.

Table 4.4-1: CS1 disulfide and other substances ECHA data for human health hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS1_08	CS1_06	CS1_20	CS1_21	CS1_22
	Substance name	2-Hydroxyethyl disulfide	iso-PDMI 92410	Niax catalyst A-1	Niax silicone L-6642	FR CROS 484
Human health endpoint	Carcinogenicity	NC	2 (H351)	NC	MISS	NC
	Mutagenicity	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
	Reproduction toxicity	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
	Endocrine disruption (human)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Respiratory sensitization	NC	1 (H334)	MISS	MISS	NC
	Specific organ toxicity Repeated exposure	NC	2 (H373)	MISS	MISS	NC
	Skin Sensitization	1B (H317)	1 (H317)	NC	MISS	NC
	Acute toxicity oral	3 (H301)	MISS	4 (H302)	MISS	NC
	Acute toxicity dermal	3 (H311)	MISS	3 (H311)	MISS	NC
	Acute toxicity inhalation	NC	4 (H332)	4 (H332)	MISS	NC
	Skin corrosion / irritation	NC	2 (H315)	1B (H314)	MISS	NC
	Eye damage / irritation	2 (H319)	2 (H319)	1 (H318)	MISS	NC
	Aspiration hazard	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
	Specific organ toxicity Single exposure	NC	3 (H335)	NC	MISS	NC

Table 4.4-2: CS1 disulfide and other substances ECHA data for environmental hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS1_08	CS1_06	CS1_20	CS1_21	CS1_22
	Substance name	2-Hydroxyethyl disulfide	iso-PDMI 92410	Niax catalyst A-1	Niax silicone L-6642	FR CROS 484
Environmental Endpoint	persistence and bioaccumulation (PBT/vPvB)	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC
	persistence and mobility (PMT/vPvM)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	endocrine disruption (environment)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Ozone	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Chronic aquatic toxicity	2 (H411)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Acute aquatic toxicity	2 (H401)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS

Table 4.4-3: CS1 disulfide and other substances ECHA data for physical hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS1_08	CS1_06	CS1_20	CS1_21	CS1_22
	Substance name	2-Hydroxyethyl disulfide	iso-PDMI 92410	Niax catalyst A-1	Niax silicone L-6642	FR CROS 484
Physical Endpoint	Explosives	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Flammable	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Flammable aerosols	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Oxidizing	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Gases under pressure	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Self-reactive	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Pyrophoric liquids, solids	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Self-heating	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Emits flammable gas	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Organic peroxides	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Corrosivity	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
	Desensitized explosives	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS

4.4.2 General human health

The assessment of human health hazard is based first on testing the cytotoxicity of the products in our models (Section 2.1). Indeed, cytotoxicity assays are used to select concentrations for the other in vitro assays. Those include oxidative stress evaluation, cytokine release and DNA methylation.

4.4.2.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity data from WST-1 assay with the CS1 disulfide on HaCaT (dermal model) and Caco-2 (oral model) cells are presented below (Figure 4.4-1). Cell viability results are shown in % with 100% being the non-treated cell viability.

No cytotoxicity was observed in HaCaT cells, even at the highest concentration tested (7.5 mM). On Caco-2 cells, cell viability decreased slowly and reached 78.8% at highest disulfide concentration.

Figure 4.4-1: Cytotoxicity results using WST-1 assay. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the CS1 Disulfide on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 9$).

IC₅₀ could be calculated by fitting the curves with a quadratic model and are listed in Table 4.4-4.

Table 4.4-4: IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity in WST-1 assay. Fit with a quadratic model.

Cell line	Disulfide
HaCaT (dermal model)	7853 µM
Caco-2 (oral model)	7958 µM

LDH Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay measuring the LDH release in cell supernatant was performed in parallel to the WST-1 assay (oral and dermal model) or Alamar Blue (inhalation models).

This second method assessing cytotoxicity in the oral and dermal model gave inconsistent results with the WST-1 assay, as the viability with disulfide dropped in both cell lines (Figure 4.4-2). Furthermore, these results should be treated with caution, as microscopic observations of the cells showed them to

be normal in shape and appearance. Therefore, an interference of disulfide with the LDH assay is suspected.

According to these cytotoxicity results, a concentration of 1mM of CS1 disulfide was chosen for further testing. This concentration corresponds to a non-toxic dose, according to the WST-1 assay, before the decrease of viability in both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells.

Figure 4.4-2: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the CS1 disulfide on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 9$).

In the inhalation cell models, cytotoxic effects of the polyols were measured using the LDH assay after 24h exposure to a range of concentrations (Figure 4.4-3). Similar results were obtained for the two cell lines used, A549 alveolar epithelial cells and dTHP-1 macrophage-like cells. IC_{50} could be calculated by fitting the curves and are listed in Table 4.4-5. In A549, disulfide had an IC_{50} of 248.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, and similarly, the calculated IC_{50} in dTHP-1 was 194.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.

Table 4.4-5. IC_{50} values for cytotoxicity LDH assay in the inhalation models

Cell line	Disulfide
A549	248.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
THP-1	194.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$

Figure 4.4-3. Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Percentage of cell viability compared to the non-treated cells of the CS1 disulfide, on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3).

AlamarBlue

In the inhalation cell models, cytotoxic effects of the polyols were also measured using the AlamarBlue assay after 24h exposure to a range of concentration (Figure 4.4-4). The results obtained are very similar to the ones from the LDH assay, and practically identical in both cell lines. IC₅₀ could be calculated by fitting the curves and are listed in Table 4.4-6.

Figure 4.4-4. Cytotoxicity results using AlamarBlue measurement. Percentage of cell viability compared to the non-treated cells of the CS1 disulfide, on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3).

Table 4.4-6. IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity AlamarBlue assay in the inhalation models

Cell line	Disulfide
A549	235.2 µg/mL
THP-1	234.9 µg/mL

4.4.2.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay

No clear oxidative stress induction was observed for the disulfide at the tested concentrations on both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells (Figure 4.4-5). As for the catalysts, the experimental window framed by the solvent and the positive control was smaller for Caco-2 than for HaCaT cells, due to a lower response of the positive control. As a result, the test is less sensitive than for HaCaT cells, and the differences in the induction of oxidative stress are more difficult to assess.

Figure 4.4-5: CM-H₂DCFDA assay with the CS1 disulfide on (A) HaCaT and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥8).

Cellular ROS assay

In the inhalation A549 cell model, ROS production as a measure of oxidative stress was assessed after exposure to the CS1 disulfide at IC₂₀ and IC₅₀ concentrations. Results showed significantly increased ROS levels after exposure to IC₅₀ when compared to solvent control (Figure 4.4-6).

Figure 4.4-6. ROS levels after exposure to CS1 disulfide. A549 cells were exposed to the disulfide compound and ROS production was assessed after 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h and 5h. Percentage of ROS production was compared to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC). A) Time course of ROS levels after exposure to IC20 and IC50 concentrations. B) ROS levels after 5h exposure to IC20 and IC50 concentrations. One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Tukey post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to solvent control.

4.4.2.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS

Results are presented below for the dermal model (Figure 4.4-7). The percentage of 5-methylcytosine was divided by a factor 2 upon incubating the positive control (5 μ M of 5-Azacytidine). However, no change in methylation status was observed by disulfide.

Figure 4.4-7: HPLC-MS/MS assay assessing the part of methylated Cytosine in total DNA after incubation with the disulfide, on Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values ($n \geq 9$).

4.4.2.4 Inflammation

Cytokine measurement of the inhalation model

The inhalation model using A549+dTHP-1 ALI co-cultures was used to measure the potential pro-inflammatory effect of the CS1 disulfide. After exposure to disulfide, medium samples were collected to detect levels of secreted cytokines TNF- α and IL-6. Very low levels of secreted cytokines were detected in the treated conditions or in the solvent control and only the LPS positive control showed

high cytokine expression (Figure 4.4-8). The percentages of secreted cytokines after disulfide exposure didn't significantly differ from the solvent control.

Figure 4.4-8. Pro-inflammatory cytokines secreted 24h after disulfide exposure. Secreted TNF- α (A,B) and IL-6 (C,D) were detected by ELISA. Graphs show quantity of each cytokine in pg/mL (A and C panels) and the percentage of secreted cytokine compared to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC) (B and D panels). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed.

Cytokine measurement of the oral and dermal model

The oral model (CaCo2 cells) and the dermal model (HaCat cells) were used to measure the potential inflammatory response of disulfide. After exposure to disulfide, medium samples were collected to detect levels of cytokines and chemokines (IFN- γ , IL-1b, IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL12p70, IL-17A, IP10, MCP-1, TGB- β 1, TNF- α).

In the oral model, secretion of most cytokines or chemokines were under the detection limit or showed no effect. Only the secretion of IL-8 and IP-10 were significantly different in samples exposed to the disulfide compared to the levels in the solvent control (Figure 4.4-9).

Figure 4.4-9. IL-8, and IP-10 secretion in the CS1 disulfide measured in medium samples of the oral model (CaCo2 cells). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, * indicates $p < 0.05$.

In the dermal model, secretion of IL-6 and MCP-1 were significantly different in samples exposed to the disulfide compared to the solvent control (Figure 4.4-10). IL-6 secretion was significantly increased, where MCP-1 secretion was significantly decreased. The other 11 measured cytokines and chemokines did not show an effect or were below the detection limit.

Figure 4.4-10. IL-6 and MCP-1 secretion in the CS1 disulfide measured in medium samples of the dermal model (HaCat cells). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, ** indicates $p < 0.01$; *** indicates $p < 0.005$.

4.4.3 Genotoxicity

The assessment of genotoxicity is based on testing DNA damage in the oral and dermal model. To this end, two different assays were carried out. The induction of DNA strand breaks after cell treatment was assessed using comet assay, while the focus was on double strand breaks in 53BP1 assay.

On HaCaT cells, the genotoxicity results of 1mM disulfide treatment showed no important increase in the number of 53BP1 foci and no variation of global DNA damage (single and double strand breaks) in comet assay (Figure 4.4-11, A₁ and B₁).

On Caco-2 cells, a small decrease in the number of 53BP1 foci and of global DNA damage was observed, indicating that the disulfide may have a protective role, but it is not considered as genotoxic (Figure 4.4-11, A₂ and B₂).

Figure 4.4-11: 53BP1 assay (A) and comet assay (B) with disulfide, on HaCaT cells (A₁ and B₁) and on Caco-2 cells (A₂ and B₂). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥12).

4.4.4 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

Section 11.2 of the Safety data sheet for CAS number 1892-29-1 indicates: “The substance/mixture does not contain components considered to have endocrine disrupting properties according to REACH Article 57(f) or Commission Delegated regulation (EU) 2017/2100 or Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/605 at levels of 0.1% or higher” (<https://www.sigmaaldrich.com/NL/en/sds/aldrich/380474?userType=anonymous> and <https://www.tcichemicals.com/OP/en/p/B4263#documentsSectionPDP>). Therefore, no *in vitro* testing was performed with this product.

Thyroid disruption assay

Assessment of thyroid disruption potential of the disulfide using the transgenic zebrafish line *tg(tg:mCherry)* is shown below. Based on the performed ZFET (Section 4.4.5), disulfide was tested at

30 µg/ml for thyroid disruption. Induction of the fluorescent signal was observed in the transgenic zebrafish line comparable to the positive control (Figure 4.4-12).

Figure 4.4-12: Thyroid disruption assay for the CS1 Disulfide. Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

An additional experiment was performed to test lower concentrations. Since there are no reference or alternative compounds to compare the effect of the disulfide to, a 10x dilution range was prepared. This showed that also exposure to 3 µg/ml disulfide resulted in an induction of the fluorescent signal, significant compared to the solvent control (Figure 4.4-13).

Figure 4.4-13: Additional concentrations tested for thyroid disruption for the CS1 Disulfide. Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, ** indicates $p < 0.01$; **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

4.4.5 Aquatic toxicity

Daphnia magna

Immobilization data in *Daphnia magna* individuals from OECD 202 assays with CS1 disulfide are presented below. Maximum tested concentration of all test substances was 100 mg/L, as indicated in the OECD 202 guideline and mentioned before. Immobilization data results are shown in % of motility (mobile *daphnias*), being 100% no effects (no toxicity) and 0% being complete immobilization (maximum toxicity).

As observed, CS1 disulfide presented a moderate-high acute aquatic toxicity with an EC₅₀ value of 95.6 and 10.5 mg/L at 24h and 48h, respectively (both EC₅₀ values both at 24 and 48h were obtained by fitting the curves to a sigmoidal regression) (Figure 4.4-14).

Figure 4.4-14: 24 and 48h immobilization results in *Daphnia magna* (OECD 202) for the CS1 disulfide. Reported values are expressed as means \pm SEM ($n \geq 3$).

Zebrafish

As a measure for aquatic toxicity, and as range finding experiment for the thyroid disruption assay, a Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test was performed. The maximum tested concentration was 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for the disulfide. No toxicity was observed for the tested concentration range (Figure 4.4-15). The EC₂₀ is therefore higher than 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Figure 4.4-15: Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test for the CS1 Disulfide.

4.4.6 Short summary

Disulfide exposure of the cell models resulted in cytotoxicity at the highest concentrations tested. These results were used to select concentrations for further testing. Disulfide induced oxidative stress (inhalation model only), cytokine responses (dermal and oral models) and affected *Daphnia* mobility. Most notably is the effect on thyroid hormone disruption found for disulfide, which contradicts the statement in the safety data sheet. No further hazards were identified for the disulfide.

5 Results CS2

In this chapter the results for case study 2 are described.

5.1 CS2 SSbD routes and tested substances

The SSbD routes of case study 2 and indicates which substances are part of which route are shown in Table 5.1-1. The case study 2 substances and/or materials are divided into three groups of substances: hardeners (Section 5.2), A-parts (Section 5.3) and leachates of composites (Section 5.4).

Table 5.1-2 indicates which assays were conducted for which substances.

Table 5.1-1: SSbD routes for hazard assessment of CS2. The routes correspond to those described in D4.2. An x indicates that the substance is part of this route.

SSbD Route number	Details	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD	AP-CL	AP1	AP2	AP3	AP4	Leach-TCPP	Leach-SP1	Leach-SP2	Leach-SP3	Leach-SP4
SSbD#0	including leachate	x			x					x				
SSbD#0	without leachate	x			x									
N/A	SSbD#1, Araldite LY1564, without leachate, MDA	x				x								
N/A	SSbD#1, Polyphlox 3742, without leachate, MDA	x					x							
N/A	SSbD#1, Exolit EP 360, without leachate, MDA	x						x						
N/A	SSbD#1, Exolit OP 930, without leachate, MDA	x							x					
SSbD#1	Araldite LY1564, without leachate		x			x								
N/A	SSbD#1, Polyphlox 3742, without leachate		x				x							
SSbD#1	Exolit EP 360, without leachate		x					x						
N/A	SSbD#1, Exolit OP 930, without leachate		x						x					
SSbD#1	Araldite LY1564, including leachate		x			x					x			
N/A	SSbD#1, Polyphlox 3742, including leachate		x				x					x		
SSbD#1	Exolit EP 360, including leachate		x					x					x	
N/A	SSbD#1, Exolit OP 930, including leachate		x						x					x
N/A	SSbD#1, Araldite LY1564, without leachate, 2-AFD			x		x								
N/A	SSbD#1, Polyphlox 3742, without leachate, 2-AFD			x			x							
N/A	SSbD#1, Exolit EP 360, without leachate, 2-AFD			x				x						
N/A	SSbD#1, Exolit OP 930, without leachate, 2-AFD			x					x					

Table 5.1-2: Overview of assays conducted for the various CS2 substances. x = this assay was conducted for this substance; N/A = not applicable.

Health hazard	Endpoint	Assay	Exposure route	AP-CL	AP1	AP2	AP3	AP4	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD	Leach-TCPP	Leach-SP1	Leach-SP2	Leach-SP3	Leach-SP4
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	WST-1	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	WST-1	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Inhalation	x	x		x		x	x	x					
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Inhalation	x	x		x		x	x	x					
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	Alamar blue	Inhalation	x	x		x		x	x	x					
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	Alamar blue	Inhalation	x	x		x		x	x	x					
Human health general	Oxidative stress	CM-H2DCFDA	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Oxidative stress	CM-H2DCFDA	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Oxidative stress	ROS	Inhalation	x	x		x		x	x	x					
Human health general	Oxidative stress	Protein carbonylation	Inhalation	x	x		x		x	x	x					
Human health general	Epigenetic	Epigenetic changes	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x					
Human health general	Inflammation	Cytokine release	Inhalation	x	x		x		x	x	x					
Human health general	Inflammation	Cytokine release	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x					
Human health general	Inflammation	Cytokine release	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x					
Genotoxicity	N/A	COMET	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	COMET	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	53BP1	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	53BP1	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Endocrine disruption	N/A	Calux battery AR/ER	N/A	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Endocrine disruption	N/A	Thyroid	N/A	x	x		x		x	x	x	x	x		x	
Ecotoxicity	N/A	Daphnia	N/A	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Ecotoxicity	N/A	Zebrafish	N/A	x	x		x		x	x	x					

5.2 CS2 Hardeners

Hardeners are chemical substances that are used for vitrimer preparation, in combination with epoxy resin and any additives like flame retardants or colouring agents.

For toxicological assessments, 4,4'-Diaminodiphenylmethane (MDA) was identified as the reference hardener. Two other substances, the 4-Aminophenyl disulfide (4-AFD) and the 2-Aminophenyl disulfide (2-AFD) were assessed as SSbD alternatives (Table 5.2-1).

4-AFD, 2-AFD and MDA were dissolved in DMSO. A concentration up to 100 mM for 4-AFD, 60 mM for 2-AFD and 1 M for MDA was tested. After two weeks at room temperature, the stock solutions were still clear, without visual deposition. Stock solutions were kept for a maximum of 1 week before using them for cell exposures.

Table 5.2-1: Received substances for CS2 Hardeners

Product name	SURPASS code	CAS number	Supplier
MDA, reference hardener	CS2_14	101-77-9	Sigma, 32950
4-AFD, alternative hardener	CS2_02	722-27-0	Sigma, 369462
2-AFD, alternative hardener	CS2_15	1141-88-4	CS2 team - Cidetec

5.2.1 ECHA data

ECHA data were retrieved from the ECHA database. For missing information, data were searched for in suppliers Safety Data Sheets (SDS) and / or literature. Collected hazard data are presented in

Table 5.2-2, Table 5.2-3, and Table 5.2-4.

MISS = missing information, no data available.

NC = not classified as hazardous.

1, 2, 3 = ECHA hazard categories for substances classification.

Table 5.2-2: CS2 Hardeners ECHA data for human health hazards

Human health Endpoint	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD
Carcinogenicity	1B	MISS	MISS
Mutagenicity	2	MISS	MISS
Reproduction toxicity	MISS	MISS	MISS
Endocrine disruption (human)	NC	MISS	NC
Respiratory sensitization	MISS	MISS	MISS
Specific organ toxicity Repeated exposure	2	MISS	MISS
Skin Sensitization	1	MISS	NC
Acute toxicity oral	3	MISS	3
Acute toxicity dermal	NC	MISS	MISS
Acute toxicity inhalation	NC	MISS	MISS
Skin corrosion / irritation	NC	2	NC
Eye damage / irritation	NC	2	1
Aspiration hazard	NC	MISS	MISS
Specific organ toxicity Single exposure	1	3	MISS

Table 5.2-3: CS2 Hardeners ECHA data for environmental hazards

Environmental Endpoint	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD
persistence and bioaccumulation (PBT/vPvB)	NC	MISS	NC
persistence and mobility (PMT/vPvM)	MISS	MISS	MISS
endocrine disruption (environment)	NC	MISS	NC
Ozone	NC	MISS	MISS
Chronic aquatic toxicity	2	MISS	1
Acute aquatic toxicity	1	MISS	1

Table 5.2-4: CS2 Hardeners ECHA data for physical hazards

Physical Endpoint	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD
Explosives	NC	MISS	MISS
Flammable	NC	MISS	MISS
Flammable aerosols	NC	MISS	MISS
Oxidizing	NC	MISS	NC
Gases under pressure	NC	MISS	MISS
Self-reactive	NC	MISS	MISS
Pyrophoric liquids, solids	NC	MISS	MISS
Self-heating	NC	MISS	MISS
Emits flammable gas	NC	MISS	MISS
Organic peroxides	NC	MISS	MISS
Corrosivity	NC	MISS	MISS
Desensitized explosives	NC	MISS	MISS

5.2.2 General human health

The assessment of human health hazard is based first on testing the cytotoxicity of the products in our models (Section 2.1). Indeed, cytotoxicity assays are used to select concentrations for the other in vitro assays. Those include oxidative stress evaluation, cytokine release and DNA methylation.

5.2.2.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity data from WST-1 assay with CS2 hardeners for the dermal and oral model are presented below. HaCaT (dermal model) and Caco-2 (oral model) cells were tested with a wide concentration range of hardeners. Cell viability results are shown in % with 100% being the non-treated cell viability.

Results showed a higher cytotoxic effect with the alternative compounds 4-AFD and 2-AFD than with the reference hardener MDA (Figure 5.2-1). The IC₅₀ could be calculated by fitting the curves with a

4PL model for all products, except for MDA on HaCaT cells. Indeed, the 4PL was not adapted for the MDA curve shape and a linear model was chosen. The IC₅₀ values are listed in Table 5.2-5.

Figure 5.2-1: Cytotoxicity results using WST-1 assay. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the reference hardener (MDA) and the alternative products (4-AFD and 2-AFD), on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians ± interquartile (n ≥ 11).

Table 5.2-5: IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity WST-1 assay. * Fit done with 4PL model, except for MDA on HaCaT cells (linear fit).

Cell line	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD
HaCaT (dermal model)	2844 µM*	83 µM	161 µM
Caco-2 (oral model)	3342 µM	139 µM	170 µM

Note: An increased viability was observed with 2-AFD and 4-AFD at low concentrations, especially in HaCaT cells. This 3-fold to 5-fold increase, compared to the basal viability, was not due to a higher cell proliferation but to an enhanced metabolic activity as the assay is based on mitochondrial activity. Further testing could help to better understand these data but will not be investigated as part of the SURPASS project as it does not impact the cytotoxic results for the CS2 hardeners.

According to the cytotoxicity results, two concentrations were chosen for further testing (Table 5.2-6). First, an equimolar non-toxic dose was identified to compare the products at same concentration. Then, 80% survival dose (or equi-toxicity concentration) was used to compare the products at same cytotoxic effect.

Table 5.2-6: CS2 Hardener working concentrations chosen

Cell line	Cell confluence during the treatment	Equimolar concentrations	Equi-toxicity concentrations
HaCaT (skin cells)	> 80% confluence	50 μ M	500 μ M MDA 80 μ M 4-AFD 200 μ M 2-AFD
	< 80% confluence	30 μ M	500 μ M MDA 60 μ M 4-AFD 60 μ M 2-AFD
Caco-2 (oral model)	> 80% confluence	60 μ M	1500 μ M MDA 115 μ M 4-AFD 150 μ M 2-AFD
	< 80% confluence	30 μ M	750 μ M MDA 60 μ M 4-AFD 60 μ M 2-AFD

LDH Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay measuring the LDH release in cell supernatant was performed in parallel to the WST-1 assay (oral and dermal model) or Alamar Blue (inhalation models).

The results of this second method assessing cytotoxicity confirmed those obtained with WST-1 assay for the oral and dermal model, despite the more difficult analysis of the raw data (Figure 5.2-2). At high concentrations, the alternative products interfered with the assay method, as microscopy observation shows a complete mortality of the cell culture wells. Furthermore, it appears that the LDH assay is less sensitive than the WST-1 assay: with the WST-1 test, a decline in cell viability was observed at lower concentrations than with the LDH test, meaning that the metabolic activity of the mitochondria was affected before the increase in permeability of the cell membranes. LDH assay was therefore used to confirm cytotoxicity results but IC₅₀ were not calculated for this assessment method.

Figure 5.2-2: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the reference hardener (MDA) and the alternative products (4-AFD and 2-AFD), on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 10$).

In the inhalation cell models, cytotoxic effects of the hardeners were measured using the LDH assay after 24h exposure to a range of concentrations (Figure 5.2-3). Similar results were obtained for the two cell lines used, A549 alveolar epithelial cells and dTHP-1 macrophage-like cells. 4-AFD showed the

higher cytotoxic potential, especially in the dTHP-1 cell line, followed by 2-AFD, that was only cytotoxic in the dTHP-1 cells. The reference MDA showed no effects on cell survival at the tested concentrations. IC₅₀ could be calculated by fitting the curves and are listed in Table 5.2-7.

Table 5.2-7: IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity LDH assay in the inhalation models

Cell line	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD
A549	> 200 µM	49,63 µM	> 200 µM
dTHP-1 cells	> 200 µM	5,04 µM	4,99 µM

Figure 5.2-3: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Percentage of cell viability compared to the non-treated cells with the reference MDA and the alternative 2-AFD and 4-AFD, on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are mean ± SEM (n=3).

AlamarBlue

In the inhalation cell models, cytotoxic effects of the hardeners were also measured using the AlamarBlue assay after 24h exposure to a range of concentration (Figure 5.2-4). The results obtained are very similar to the ones from the LDH assay, maintaining the toxicity ranking unchanged for both cell lines. IC₅₀ could be calculated by fitting the curves and are listed in Table 5.2-8.

Figure 5.2-4: Cytotoxicity results using AlamarBlue measurement. Percentage of cell viability compared to the non-treated cells with the reference MDA and the alternative 2-AFD and 4-AFD, on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are mean ± SEM (n=3).

Table 5.2-8: IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity AlamarBlue assay in the inhalation models

Cell line	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD
A549	> 200 µM	18,49 µM	32,31 µM
dTHP-1 cells	> 200 µM	11,74 µM	9,90 µM

5.2.2.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay

The second CS2 alternative hardener (2-AFD) was added to the project after the oxidative stress assays for the first two substances (MDA and 4-AFD) was finished. Therefore, a second set of exposures, consisting of MDA and 2-AFD was performed. Consequently, two sets of results were obtained, one for 4-AFD and MDA, and a second for 2-AFD and MDA (Figure 5.2-5).

Figure 5.2-5: CM-H₂DCFDA assay comparing MDA and 4-AFD (A) and comparing MDA and 2-AFD (B). Assessments were done on HaCaT cells (A₁ and B₁) and on Caco-2 cells (A₂ and B₂). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥8).

CM-H₂DCFDA results showed an induction of oxidative stress with MDA at higher concentration, with values between 33% and 75% of the positive control values, on both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells. Some slight inductions could also be observed with 4-AFD and 2-AFD at the highest concentrations on HaCaT cells (A₁ and B₁). However, the increase for 2-AFD was not statistically significant compared to the solvent control. In all cases, MDA induced the strongest response.

Cellular ROS assay

In the inhalation A549 cell model, ROS production as a measure of oxidative stress was assessed after exposure to the hardener compounds at equitoxic concentrations corresponding to the calculated IC₅₀ and IC₂₀. Results showed significantly increased ROS levels after 2-AFD and 4-AFD exposure (IC₂₀ and IC₅₀) when compared to solvent control (Figure 5.2-6). Also, both 2-AFD and 4-AFD produced significantly higher levels of ROS than the reference substance MDA (comparing between equivalent doses).

Figure 5.2-6: ROS levels after exposure to CS₂ hardeners. A549 cells were exposed to the hardener compounds and ROS production was assessed after 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h and 5h. Percentage of ROS production compared to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC) with the reference MDA and the alternative 4-AFD and 2-AFD. A) Time course of ROS levels after exposure to IC₂₀ concentrations of hardeners. B) ROS levels after 5h exposure to IC₂₀ concentrations of hardeners. C) Time course of ROS levels after exposure to IC₅₀ concentrations of hardeners. D) ROS levels after 5h exposure to IC₅₀ concentrations of hardeners. Reported values are mean ± SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Tukey post-hoc test was performed, * indicates p < 0.05 compared to solvent control, and # indicates p < 0.05 compared to reference substance MDA.

Protein carbonylation

Effects of the exposure to the hardener compounds on protein carbonylation levels as an indication of oxidative stress was also assessed in the inhalation model using A549+dTHP-1 ALI co-cultures. Cells were exposed to equivalent doses of each hardener by nebulization (3.5 µg/insert) for 24h. The analysis of protein carbonyl content showed that, when comparing the conditions exposed to the

hardeners with the solvent control, no increase was observed, even for the positive control the effect was limited. No significant differences were observed (Figure 5.2-7).

Figure 5.2-7: Hardeners effect on protein carbonylation after 24h exposure in a co-culture inhalation model. A) Quantity of protein carbonylation in nmol/mg after 24h exposure. Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). B) Percentage of protein carbonylation compared to the solvent control SC and the positive control (PC) after 24h exposure. Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed.

5.2.2.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS

Modulation of cytosine methylation in total DNA after treatment of the oral model (Caco-2 cells) with the CS2 Hardeners was assessed using HPLC-MS/MS. The percentage of 5-methylcytosine was divided by a factor 2 upon incubating the positive control (5 μ M of 5-Azaytidine). However, no change in methylation status was observed either with the reference hardener or with the alternative products (Figure 5.2-8).

Figure 5.2-8: HPLC-MS/MS assay assessing the part of methylated Cytosine in total DNA after incubation with the reference and the alternative hardeners, on Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values (n \geq 9).

5.2.2.4 Inflammation

Cytokine measurement of the inhalation model

The inhalation model using A549+dTHP-1 ALI co-cultures was used to measure the potential pro-inflammatory effect of the hardeners. Medium samples after exposure to equimolar concentrations of

the hardeners were collected to detect levels of secreted cytokines TNF- α and IL-6. Very low levels of secreted cytokines were detected in the treated conditions or in the solvent control (below 20 pg/mL), only the LPS positive control showed high cytokine expression. The percentages of secreted TNF- α in the alternative conditions 2-AFD and 4-AFD didn't significantly differ from the solvent control, but were significantly lower than for the reference MDA. In the case of IL-6, all three compounds showed reduced levels of cytokines when compared to the solvent control, being significantly lower for 2-AFD and 4-AFD. Results are shown in Figure 5.2-9.

Figure 5.2-9: Pro-inflammatory cytokines secreted 24h after the hardener's exposures. Secreted TNF- α (left) and IL-6 (right) were detected by ELISA. Graphs show the percentage of secreted cytokine compared to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Tukey's post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to solvent control; # indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to MDA.

Cytokine measurement of the oral and dermal model

The oral model (CaCo2 cells) and the dermal model (HaCat cells) were used to measure the potential inflammatory response of the hardeners: MDA, 4-AFD and 2-AFD. After exposure to the hardeners, medium samples were collected to detect levels of cytokines and chemokines (IFN- γ , IL-1b, IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL12p70, IL-17A, IP10, MCP-1, TGB- β 1, TNF- α).

In the oral model, secretion of most cytokines or chemokines were under the detection limit or showed no effect. Only the secretion of IP-10 was significantly different in samples exposed to MDA at equitoxic levels (750 μ M) compared to the solvent control (Figure 5.2-10). No significantly different effect in cytokine and chemokine secretion were observed in samples exposed to 2-AFD and 4-AFD in the oral model.

Figure 5.2-10. IP-10 secretion in the CS2 hardeners measured in medium samples of the oral model (CaCo2 cells).
Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, * indicates $p < 0.05$.

In the dermal model, secretion of IL-6 and IL-8 were significantly different in samples exposed to 2-AFD compared to the solvent control both for the tested equitoxic (60 µM) and equimolar (30 µM) concentrations (Figure 5.2-11). Samples exposed to 2-AFD also showed significant different secretion of IP-10 and MCP-1 in the tested equitoxic concentration. MCP-1 and IFN- γ secretion was significantly different in samples exposed to 4-AFD, both in the tested equimolar (30 µM) and equitoxic (60 µM) concentration. In samples exposed to the equitoxic concentration of 4-AFD also significantly different levels of TGF- β 1 were found (Figure 5.2-11). The other cytokines and chemokines did not show an effect or were below the detection limit. No significant effect of samples exposed to MDA were observed in the dermal model.

Figure 5.2-11. IL-6, IL-8, IP-10, MCP-1, IFN- γ , and TGF- β 1 secretion in the CS2 hardeners measured in medium samples of the dermal model (HaCat cells). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test.

5.2.3 Genotoxicity

The assessment of genotoxicity is based on testing DNA damage in the oral and dermal model. To this end, two different assays were carried out. The induction of DNA strand breaks after cell treatment was assessed using comet assay, while the focus was on double strand breaks in 53BP1 assay.

Genotoxicity results showed an increase in the number of 53BP1 foci with 4-AFD at the largest concentration in HaCaT cells (Figure 5.2-12, A₁) with 6.87 foci per cell compared to 1.11 foci per cell for the solvent control. However, this has to be taken carefully as this treatment showed larger cytotoxic effect as expected (about 50% instead of 80% survival). Accordingly, no increase in 53BP1 value was observed at the largest concentration in Caco-2 cells. No induction of single and double-strand breaks was observed in cells exposed to 4-AFD (Figure 5.2-12, B₁).

For MDA and 2-AFD, statistically significant but small variations compared to the solvent or to the reference substance, most of the times decreases, were observed in 53BP1 and comet tests. Altogether, the hardeners can be considered not to induce genotoxic stress in these assays.

Figure 5.2-12: 53BP1 assay (A) and comet assay (B) comparing MDA reference hardeners with the alternative hardeners. Tests are done on HaCaT cells (A₁ and B₁) and on Caco-2 cells (A₂ and B₂). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥9).

5.2.4 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

Agonist test

The pre-tests of the CALUX[®] agonist assay showed no binding of 4-AFD and 2-AFD on the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α) and the Androgen Receptor (AR), in the investigated range of concentrations. For the MDA, the reference hardener, an agonist effect was observed on the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α) with a relative induction of 145% at highest tested concentration (Figure 5.2-13). The binding was characterised with the complete assay protocol.

Figure 5.2-13: (A) ERα agonist assay with MDA reference hardener. Reported values are means ± SD (n≥3). (B) EC₅₀ values for ERα and AR agonist assays on the CS2 reference and alternative hardeners. Curve fitting done with a 4PL model.

Antagonist test

Results showed no antagonist effect of CS2 hardeners on the Estrogen Receptor α (ERα). For the Androgen Receptor (AR), MDA and 4-AFD showed respectively a clear and a slight effect, whereas 2-AFD was negative: MDA gave a relative induction of 52% at highest tested concentration; 4-AFD had a response of 64% relative induction at highest tested concentration (Figure 5.2-14).

A complete testing with specificity test was performed for MDA and 4-AFD. Comparison of the test to its specificity control ruled out an antagonist response of 4-AFD for the AR receptor. In contrast the specificity test confirmed the effect for MDA. Indeed, the correlation of the two 4-AFD curves was high ($R^2 = 0.9931$) indicating a non-specific effect, whereas the MDA curves correlation was low ($R^2 = 0.0536$) indicating a shift due to the agonist concentration change.

A

B

	ER α antagonist assay	AR antagonist assay
CALUX [®] Reference compound	1.35E-08 M	5.06E-07 M
MDA	> 1E-04 M	1.20E-04 M
4-AFD	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M
2-AFD	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M

Figure 5.2-14: (A) AR antagonist assay with MDA reference hardener and 4-AFD alternative hardener. Reported values are means \pm SD ($n \geq 3$). (B) IC₅₀ values for ER α and AR antagonist assays on the CS2 reference and alternative hardeners. Curve fitting done with a 4PL model.

Thyroid disruption assay

Assessment of thyroid disruption potential of the hardeners of case study 2 using the transgenic zebrafish line *tg(tg:mCherry)* are shown below. Based on the performed ZFET (Section 5.2.5) subtoxic concentrations were selected: MDA was tested at 100 μ M, 4-AFD at 1 μ M, and 2-AFD at 0.1 μ M. Induction of the fluorescent signal was observed in the transgenic zebrafish line for the MDA and 4-AFD (Figure 5.2-15).

Figure 5.2-15: Thyroid disruption assay for the CS2 Hardeners. Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, * indicates $p < 0.05$; **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

As a follow-up, for MDA and 4-AFD additional concentrations are tested comparable with the reference and/or alternative compounds. For MDA 100, 1.0 and 0.1 μM were tested, of which only exposure to the highest concentration resulted in an induced fluorescent signal. For 4-AFD 1, 0.1, and 0.01 μM were tested, where the two highest concentrations showed an induced signal significant compared to the solvent control (Figure 5.2-16).

Figure 5.2-16: Additional concentrations tested for the thyroid disruption assay for the CS2 Hardeners MDA and 4-AFD. Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, * indicates $p < 0.05$; **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

5.2.5 Aquatic toxicity

Daphnia magna

Immobilization data in *Daphnia magna* individuals from OECD 202 tests with CS2 hardeners are presented below. Maximum tested concentration of all test substances was 100 mg/L, as indicated in the OECD 202 guideline and mentioned before. Immobilization data results are shown in % of motility (mobile *daphnias*), being 100% no effects (no toxicity) and 0% being complete immobilization (maximum toxicity) (Figure 5.2-17).

Figure 5.2-17: 24 (A) and 48h (B) immobilization results in *Daphnia magna* (OECD 202) for the CS2 hardeners. Reported values are expressed as means \pm SEM ($n \geq 3$). Please, note that x-axis is in logarithmic form.

As observed, all hardeners used in CS2 presented very high acute toxicity in *Daphnia* ($EC_{50,48h} < 1$ mg/L). Although, in general, EC_{50} values of both alternatives products 4-AFD and 2-AFD are slightly lower than the reference hardener (MDA) (i.e., more toxic than the reference), there are no statistical differences among them.

All EC_{50} values both at 24 and 48h were obtained by fitting the curves to a sigmoidal regression and are listed in Table 5.2-9.

Table 5.2-9: EC_{50} immobilization values at 24 and 48h for acute aquatic toxicity test (OECD 202) in CS2 hardeners.

Timepoint	MDA (reference)	4-AFD	2-AFD
24h	1.51 mg/L	0.51 mg/L	0.53 mg/L
48h	0.63 mg/L	0.40 mg/L	0.30 mg/L

Zebrafish

As a measure for aquatic toxicity, and as range finding experiment for the thyroid disruption assay, a Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test was performed. The maximum tested concentration was 500 μ M for MDA, and 3 μ M for both 4-AFD and 2-AFD (Figure 5.2-18).

Figure 5.2-18: Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test for the CS2 Hardeners.

EC20s were established within the tested range for the three compounds, showing that the reference substance MDA is the least toxic to morphological development of the zebrafish embryo (Table 5.2-10).

Table 5.2-10: Established EC₂₀ values for the CS2 Hardeners.

MDA (reference)	4-AFD	2-AFD
340.6 µM	2.492 µM	0.6118 µM

5.2.6 Short summary

The reference hardener, MDA, showed lowest levels of cytotoxicity, however, MDA was found to induce oxidative stress (dermal and oral models), cytokine release (oral model only), potentially induce endocrine disruption and, although the least of the three, affected Daphnia mobility but not zebrafish morphology. 4-AFD also induced oxidative stress (dermal and inhalation model), cytokine release (dermal model), affected thyroid hormone balance, Daphnia mobility and zebrafish toxicity. The effects of 2-AFD were generally comparable to those of 4-AFD, but 2-AFD induced less effects in the assays. 2-AFD was found to induce oxidative stress (inhalation model only), cytokine release (dermal model) and affected Daphnia mobility and zebrafish toxicity.

5.3 CS2 A-Parts

A-Parts are chemical mixtures that are used for vitrimer preparation, in combination with hardeners. They are made of an epoxy resin combined with additives like flame retardants or colouring agents.

For toxicological assessments of CS2 A-Parts, the pure epoxy resin (without any additives) was tested alongside the A-Parts containing different types of flame retardants. In addition, a halogenated flame retardant, Tris(2-chloro-1-methylethyl) phosphate (TCPP) was mixed with resin to obtain the reference A-Part. Tested A-parts are listed in Table 5.3-1.

Table 5.3-1: Received substances for CS2 A-Parts.

Product name	SURPASS code	CAS number	Description
AP-CL , reference A-Part	CS2_20	1675-54-3 2425-79-8 13674-84-5	A-Part with TCPP
AP1 , pure resin	CS2_01	1675-54-3 2425-79-8	A-Part without flame retardant
AP2 , alternative A-Part	CS2_17	1675-54-3 2425-79-8 300371-38-4 9003-36-5	A-Part with DOPO modified epoxy resin
AP3 , alternative A-Part	CS2_18	1675-54-3 2425-79-8 NA	A-Part with Phosphorous modified epoxy resin (Exolit EP 360)
AP4 , alternative A-Part	CS2_19	1675-54-3 2425-79-8 225789-38-8	A-Part with Aluminium diethyl phosphinate (as flame retardant)

TCPP: Tris(1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate; DOPO: 9,10-Dihydro-9-oxa-10-phosphaphenanthrene-10-oxide

All A-Parts were dissolved in DMSO with a concentration up to 40 mg/mL. The obtained solutions were clear and homogenous for all A-Parts, except for AP4. Indeed, AP4 is made with aluminium diethyl phosphinate that is mixed with the resin but not bound to it (like the flame retardant are in AP3 and AP2). When the product is dissolved, the salt remains in suspension and gives the mixture its heterogeneity.

After two weeks at room temperature, the stock solutions were still clear, without visual deposition, except for AP4. Stock solutions were kept for a maximum of 1 week before testing them on cells.

After the in vitro assessment had started, it was decided to discontinue AP2 and AP4. Therefore, some in vitro assay results contain results for these A-parts, whereas other assays focussed on AP-CL, AP1 and AP3 only.

5.3.1 ECHA data

No safety data are available for the CS2 A-Parts themselves. But as they are mixtures of resin and flame retardants, ECHA data for each of the A-Part components were retrieved from the ECHA database. For missing information, data were searched for in suppliers Safety Data Sheets (SDS) and / or literature.

Collected hazard data are presented in the following tables.

MISS = missing information, no data available.

NC = not classified as hazardous.

1, 2, 3 = ECHA hazard categories for substances classification.

Table 5.3-2: CS2 A-Parts ECHA data for human health hazards. FR = flame retardant.

Human health Endpoint	AP1 & all A-Parts		AP-CL	AP2		AP3	AP4
	Resin 1675-54-3	Resin 2425-79-8		FR 13674-84-5	FR 300371-38-4		
Component and CAS number	Resin 1675-54-3	Resin 2425-79-8	FR 13674-84-5	FR 300371-38-4	FR 9003-36-5	FR N/A	FR 225789-38-8
Carcinogenicity	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
Mutagenicity	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
Reproduction toxicity	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
Endocrine disruption (human)	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
Respiratory sensitization	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
Specific organ toxicity Repeated exposure	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
Skin Sensitization	1	1	MISS	1	1	1	NC
Acute toxicity oral	NC	4	4	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
Acute toxicity dermal	NC	4	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
Acute toxicity inhalation	NC	4	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC
Skin corrosion / irritation	2	2	MISS	MISS	2	2	NC
Eye damage / irritation	2	1	MISS	MISS	2	2	NC
Aspiration hazard	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
Specific organ toxicity Single exposure	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC

Table 5.3-3: CS2 A-Parts ECHA data for environmental hazards. FR = flame retardant

Environmental Endpoint	AP1 & all A-Parts		AP-CL	AP2		AP3	AP4
Component and CAS number	Resin 1675-54-3	Resin 2425-79-8	FR 13674-84-5	FR 300371-38-4	FR 9003-36-5	FR N/A	FR 225789-38-8
persistence and bioaccumulation (PBT/vPvB)	NC	NC	NC	MISS	NC	NC	NC
persistence and mobility (PMT/vPvM)	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
endocrine disruption (environment)	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Ozone	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Chronic aquatic toxicity	2	3	MISS	2	2	2	NC
Acute aquatic toxicity	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC

Table 5.3-4: CS2 A-Parts ECHA data for physical hazards. FR = flame retardant

Physical Endpoint	AP1 & all A-Parts		AP-CL	AP2		AP3	AP4
Component and CAS number	Resin 1675-54-3	Resin 2425-79-8	FR 13674-84-5	FR 300371-38-4	FR 9003-36-5	FR N/A	FR 225789-38-8
Explosives	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	1 (dust)
Flammable	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Flammable aerosols	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Oxidizing	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Gases under pressure	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Self-reactive	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Pyrophoric liquids, solids	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Self-heating	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Emits flammable gas	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Organic peroxides	NC	NC	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Corrosivity	NC	MISS	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	NC
Desensitized explosives	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS

5.3.2 General human health

The assessment of human health hazard is based first on testing the cytotoxicity of the products in our models (Section 2.1). Indeed, cytotoxicity assays are used to select concentrations for the other in vitro assays. Those include oxidative stress evaluation, cytokine release and DNA methylation.

5.3.2.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity data from WST-1 assay with CS2 hardeners are presented below. HaCaT (skin) and Caco-2 (gut) cells were tested with a wide concentration range of A-Parts. Cell viability results are shown in % with 100% being the non-treated cell viability.

Figure 5.3-1: Cytotoxicity results using WST-1 assay. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the A-Parts, on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 9$).

Results showed a similar effect with the A-Part containing no flame retardant (AP1), the reference flame retardant (AP-CL) and the alternative ones (AP2, AP3 and AP4) (Figure 5.3-1). IC_{50} could be calculated by fitting the curves with a 4PL model and are listed in Table 5.3-5.

Table 5.3-5: IC_{50} values for cytotoxicity WST-1 assay. 4PL fit chosen for all conditions.

Cell line	AP-CL	AP1	AP2	AP3	AP4
HaCaT (skin cells)	34 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	37 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	36 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	37 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Caco-2 (gut cells)	44 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	51 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	43 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	42 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

Based on the cytotoxicity results, a single concentration was chosen for further testing. Since the A-Parts have similar effect, this unique concentration will be used to assess equimolarity and equitoxicity effects.

For both cell lines (HaCaT and Caco-2 cells), A-Parts will be tested at 33 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, for assays with respectively $>80\%$ and $<80\%$ cell confluence during the treatment.

LDH Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay measuring the LDH release in cell supernatant was performed in parallel to the WST-1 assay.

The results of this second method assessing cytotoxicity confirmed those obtained with WST-1 assay, despite a lower sensitivity of the LDH assay: with the WST-1 test, a decline in cell viability was observed at lower concentrations than with the LDH test for all A-parts, meaning that the metabolic activity of the mitochondria was affected before the increase in permeability of the cell membranes (Figure 5.3-2). LDH assay was therefore used as a control for cytotoxicity results but IC₅₀ were not calculated for this assessment method.

Figure 5.3-2: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the A-PArts, on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians ± interquartile (n≥9).

In the inhalation cell models, cytotoxic effects of the A-parts were measured using the LDH assay after 24h exposure to a range of concentrations (Figure 5.3-3). A-parts showed higher cytotoxicity in the dTHP-1 cell line than in the A549. In dTHP-1 cells, similar IC₅₀ values were obtained for the three tested compounds, being the AP1 the one with higher cytotoxic potential, followed by the reference AP-CL and the AP3. In the case of the epithelial A549 cells, again the IC₅₀ values were similar for the three compounds, AP3 was the compound showing higher cytotoxicity, followed by AP1 and AP-CL. IC₅₀ could be calculated by fitting the curves and are listed in Table 5.3-6.

Table 5.3-6: IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity LDH assay in the inhalation models

Cell line	AP-CL	AP1	AP3
A549	229.4 µM	178.1 µM	142.5 µM
dTHP-1 cells	80.59 µM	77.99 µM	95.72 µM

Figure 5.3-3: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Percentage of cell viability compared to the non-treated cells with the reference AP-CL and the alternatives AP1 and AP3, on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3).

AlamarBlue

In the inhalation cell models, cytotoxic effects of the A-parts were also measured using the AlamarBlue assay after 24h exposure to a range of concentration (Figure 5.3-4). In both cell lines used, AP1 was the compound resulting in a higher cytotoxicity, followed by AP3 and AP-CL, both with very similar IC₅₀ values. IC₅₀ could be calculated by fitting the curves and are listed in Table 5.3-7.

Figure 5.3-4: Cytotoxicity results using AlamarBlue measurement. Percentage of cell viability compared to the non-treated cells with the reference AP-CL and the alternatives AP1 and AP3, on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3).

Table 5.3-7: IC₅₀ values for cytotoxicity AlamarBlue assay in the inhalation models

Cell line	AP-CL	AP1	AP3
A549	95.68 μ M	67.42 μ M	91.30 μ M
dTHP-1 cells	97.81 μ M	72.69 μ M	98.45 μ M

5.3.2.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay

All CS2 A-Parts were tested for oxidative stress simultaneously, at a single concentration corresponding to both equi-dose and equi-toxicity concentration, set at 33 µg/mL.

In the CM-H₂DCFDA experimental window framed by the solvent control set at 0% and the positive control set at 100%, the A-Parts showed an induction of oxidative stress on both cell lines between 6% and 17% (Figure 5.3-5).

Figure 5.3-5: CM-H₂DCFDA assay with the CS2 A-Parts. Assessments were done on HaCaT cells (A) and on Caco-2 cells (B). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥9).

In both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells, the flame retardant-free resin (AP1) induced the strongest response with respectively 17% and 12% of the positive control response. As the products containing flame retardant are mixtures made from the AP1 resin, the observed induction of oxidative stress is explained by the response of AP1 itself. The slight differences between the A-Part responses are due to variations in the percentage flame retardant in the A-Part compositions and therefore also the percentage of resin (although the basic resin is the same).

Cellular ROS assay

In the inhalation A549 cell model, ROS production as a measure of oxidative stress was assessed after exposure to the A-parts at equitoxic concentrations corresponding to the calculated IC₅₀ and IC₂₀. Results showed significantly increased ROS levels after AP3 exposure when compared to solvent control and to the reference AP-CL (comparing between equivalent IC₂₀ doses) (Figure 5.3-6).

Figure 5.3-6: ROS levels after exposure to CS2 A-parts. A549 cells were exposed to the hardener compounds and ROS production was assessed after 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h and 5h. Percentage of ROS production compared to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC) with the reference AP-CL and the alternative AP1 and AP3. A) Time course of ROS levels after exposure to IC20 concentrations. B) ROS levels after 5h exposure to IC20 concentrations. C) Time course of ROS levels after exposure to IC50 concentrations. D) ROS levels after 5h exposure to IC50 concentrations. Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Tukey post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to solvent control, and # indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to reference substance AP-CL.

Protein carbonylation

Effects of the exposure to the CS2 A-Parts on protein carbonylation levels as an indication of oxidative stress was also assessed in the inhalation model using A549+dTHP-1 ALI co-cultures. Cells were exposed to equivalent doses of each A-part (25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{insert}$) for 24h. The required concentrations to reach EC20 were not compatible with the VitroCell system due to the high concentration of DMSO in the final solution. Therefore, instead of nebulizing the compounds they were applied in a semi-ALI setting using 100 μL volume per insert. The analysis of protein carbonyl content showed that, when comparing the conditions exposed to the A-parts with the solvent control, no increase was observed, even for the positive control the effect was limited. No significant differences were observed (Figure 5.3-7).

Figure 5.3-7: A-parts effect on protein carbonylation after 24h exposure in a co-culture inhalation model. **A)** Quantity of protein carbonylation in nmol/mg after 24h exposure. Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). **B)** Percentage of protein carbonylation compared to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC) after 24h exposure. Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed.

5.3.2.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS

Modulation of cytosine methylation in total DNA after treatment of Caco-2 cells with the CS2 A-Parts was assessed using HPLC-MS/MS.

The percentage of 5-methylcytosine was divided by a factor 2 upon incubating the positive control (5 μ M of 5-Azaytidine). However, no change in methylation status was observed with the tested A-Parts at the tested concentration (20 μ g/mL) (Figure 5.3-8).

Figure 5.3-8: HPLC-MS/MS assay assessing the part of methylated Cytosine in total DNA after incubation with the CS2 A-Parts, on Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values (n \geq 8).

5.3.2.4 Inflammation

Cytokine measurement of the inhalation model

The inhalation model using A549+dTHP-1 ALI co-cultures was used to measure the potential pro-inflammatory effect of the A-parts. After exposure to equimolar concentrations, medium samples were collected to detect levels of secreted cytokines TNF- α and IL-6. Very low levels of secreted cytokines were detected in the treated conditions or in the solvent control (below 20 pg/mL), only the

LPS positive control showed high cytokine expression. The percentages of secreted cytokines in the three tested compounds did not significantly differ from the solvent control (Figure 5.3-9).

Figure 5.3-9: Pro-inflammatory cytokines secreted 24h after the hardener's exposures. Secreted TNF- α (left) and IL-6 (right) were detected by ELISA. Graphs show the percentage of secreted cytokine compared to the solvent control SC and the positive control (PC). Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Tukey's post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to solvent control.

Cytokine measurement of the oral and dermal model

The oral model (CaCo2 cells) and the dermal model (HaCat cells) were used to measure the potential inflammatory response of the A-parts. After exposure to the A-parts, medium samples were collected to detect levels of cytokines and chemokines (IFN- γ , IL-1b, IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL12p70, IL-17A, IP10, MCP-1, TGB- β 1, TNF- α).

In the oral model, all measured cytokines and chemokines were below the detection limit in all samples. In the dermal model, a statistical significant decrease in MCP-1 levels compared to the solvent control was observed for AP1 and AP3 (Figure 5.3-10).

Figure 5.3-10: MCP-1 measurements in medium samples of the CS2 A-parts in the dermal model (HaCat). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, ** indicates $p < 0.01$.

5.3.3 Genotoxicity

The assessment of genotoxicity is based on testing DNA damage in the oral and dermal model. To this end, two different assays were carried out. The induction of DNA strand breaks after cell treatment was assessed using comet assay, while the focus was on double strand breaks in 53BP1 assay.

Genotoxicity results showed a large increase in the number of 53BP1 foci with all A-Parts with values higher than 5-fold and 2.5-fold the solvent control in respectively HaCaT and Caco-2 cells (Figure 5.3-11, A). As for the oxidative stress results, the AP1 (flame retardant (FR) free resin) induced a slightly stronger response than the A-Parts containing FR. However, no significant difference was observed between the AP-CL and the A-Part containing no or alternative FR.

Figure 5.3-11: 53BP1 assay (A) and comet assay (B) comparing the A-Parts. Tests are done on HaCaT cells (A₁ and B₁) and on Caco-2 cells (A₂ and B₂). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥14 for 53BP1 assay, n≥10 for comet assay).

The comet assay showed no induction of DNA damage (single and double strand breaks) in either HaCaT and Caco-2 cells with the A-Parts (Figure 5.3-11, B). In Caco-2 cells, significant differences

between the AP-CL and AP1, AP4 were observed, but these response variations were small and with higher deviations.

Altogether, the results showed no induction of overall DNA damage with the comet assay. However, a clear increase in double-strand breaks was observed in 53BP1, similar for all tested A-Parts.

5.3.4 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

Agonist test

The pre-tests and a complete testing of the CALUX[®] agonist assay showed no binding of the A-Parts on the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α) and the Androgen Receptor (AR), in the investigated range of concentrations (Figure 5.3-12). A-Parts are not considered as agonist disruptors for ER α and AR.

Figure 5.3-12: AR agonist (A) and ER α agonist (B) assay with the CS2 A-Parts. Reported values are means \pm SD (n \geq 9)

Antagonist test

Pre-test results show no antagonist effect of CS2 A-Parts on the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α) and the Androgen Receptor (AR), in the investigated range of concentrations (Figure 5.3-13). A-Parts are not considered as antagonist disruptors for ER α and AR.

Figure 5.3-13: AR antagonist (A) and ER α antagonist (B) assay with the CS2 A-Parts. Reported values are means \pm SD (n \geq 3)

Thyroid disruption assay

Assessment of thyroid disruption potential of the A-parts AP-CL, AP1, and AP3 using the transgenic zebrafish line *tg(tg:mCherry)* are shown below. Based on the performed ZFET (Section 5.3.5) subtoxic concentrations were selected: the three A-parts AP-CL (reference), AP1, and AP3 were tested at 1 µg/ml. No induction of the fluorescent signal was observed in the transgenic zebrafish line for the tested A-parts (Figure 5.3-14).

Figure 5.3-14: Thyroid disruption assay for CS2 A-parts. Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

5.3.5 Aquatic toxicity

Daphnia magna

Immobilization data in *Daphnia magna* individuals from OECD 202 tests with CS2 A-parts are presented below. Maximum tested concentration of all test substances was 100 mg/L, as indicated in the OECD 202 guideline and mentioned before. Immobilization data results are shown in % of motility (mobile *daphnias*), being 100% no effects (no toxicity) and 0% being complete immobilization (maximum toxicity).

As observed, all A-parts used in CS2 presented moderate-high acute toxicity in *Daphnia* ($EC_{50,48h}$ between 1 and 10 mg/L) (Figure 5.3-15). Both at 24 and 48h, alternatives products AP1 and AP3 presented similar or higher toxicity as the reference A-part while alternative products AP2 and AP4 presented slighter lower toxicity.

Figure 5.3-15: 24 (A) and 48h (B) immobilization results in *Daphnia magna* (OECD 202) for the CS2 A-parts. Reported values are expressed as means \pm SEM (n \geq 3). Please, note that x-axis is in logarithmic form.

All EC₅₀ values both at 24 and 48h were obtained by fitting the curves to a sigmoidal regression and are listed in Table 5.3-8.

Table 5.3-8: EC₅₀ immobilization values at 24 and 48h for acute aquatic toxicity test (OECD 202) in CS2 A-parts.

Timepoint	AP-CL	AP1	AP2	AP3	AP4
24h	13.1 mg/L	8.80 mg/L	36.7 mg/L	10.8 mg/L	17.0 mg/L
48h	5.57 mg/L	3.98 mg/L	9.99 mg/L	6.06 mg/L	9.14 mg/L

Zebrafish

As a measure for aquatic toxicity, and as range finding experiment for the thyroid disruption assay, a Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test was performed. Only AP-CL, AP1, and AP3 were tested in the zebrafish. The maximum tested concentration was 3 μ g/ml for AP-CL (reference) and AP-1, and 30 μ g/ml for AP-3 (Figure 5.3-16).

Figure 5.3-16: Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET) test for CS2 A-parts.

For AP-CL no toxicity was observed and therefore the EC₂₀ is > 3 μ g/ml. AP-3 was slightly more toxic for embryo development than AP-1, with EC₂₀s of respectively 1.831 and 2.811 μ g/ml (Table 5.3-9).

Table 5.3-9: Established EC₂₀ values for the CS2 A-parts.

AP-CL (reference)	AP-1	AP-3
> 3.0/ml	2.811 µg/ml	1.831 µg/ml

5.3.6 Short summary

Cytotoxicity of A-parts was found to be low, however, more specific toxicity was found on the other parameters assessed. All A-parts were found to induce oxidative stress, although there were some differences between the cell models and effect of specific A-parts. Cytokine responses were found for AP1 and AP3 in dermal models only. However, all A-parts induced genotoxicity. AP1 and AP3 affected Daphnia mobility and AP3 was most toxic to the zebrafish.

5.4 CS2 Leachates from composites

During the last steps of vitrimer preparation, Hardeners and A-Parts were mixed together to produce cured resins, and glass fibers were then added to form composites (Table 5.4-1). To assess toxicity of these final composites, produced by the CS2 team in Cidetec (Spain), leachates were prepared by IPC (France).

Leaching solutions were prepared by dipping the samples in Ethanol 95% during 10 days at 40°C. At the end of the contact, leachates were concentrated to 3% of their initial volume.

For the cytotoxicity tests, the leachates were tested while using Ethanol 95% as a solvent control. Ethanol was first tested on the HaCaT and Caco-2 cells to ensure that the solvent concentrations were non-toxic to the cells.

Table 5.4-1: Received substances for CS2 Leachates.

Leachate name	SURPASS code	Composition of the sample used for leachate production	Flame retardant incorporated into the A-Part
Leach-TCPP	CS2_40	4-AFD + AP-CL + Fibers	TCPP
Leach-SP1	CS2_36	4-AFD + AP1 + Fibers	none
Leach-SP2	CS2_37	4-AFD + AP2 + Fibers	DOPO modified epoxy resin
Leach-SP3	CS2_38	4-AFD + AP3 + Fibers	Phosphorous modified epoxy resin
Leach-SP4	CS2_39	4-AFD + AP4 + Fibers	Aluminium diethyl phosphinate

4-AFD: Alternative hardener, see Section 5.2 CS2 Hardeners

AP: A-Part, see Section 5.3 CS2 A-Parts

5.4.1 ECHA data

As the leachate composition is not known, no safety data could be retrieved from the ECHA database or any Safety Data Sheets (SDS).

5.4.2 General human health

The assessment of the risks to human health is based first on testing the cytotoxicity of the products in our models (Section 2.1). Indeed, cytotoxicity assays are used to select concentrations for the other in vitro assays. Those include oxidative stress evaluation, cytokine release and DNA methylation.

5.4.2.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity data from WST-1 assay with CS2 Leachates are presented below.

Leachates were tested with a concentration range up to the highest non-toxic concentration of solvent (Ethanol 95%), being 0.2% and 2% dilution in culture medium for HaCaT and Caco-2 cells respectively. Cell viability results are shown in % with 100% being the non-treated cell viability (Figure 5.4-1).

Figure 5.4-1: Cytotoxicity results using WST-1 assay. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the CS2 Leachates, on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 7$).

On HaCaT cells, no cytotoxic effect could be observed with the leachates. As Ethanol 95% is toxic from 0.2% dilution in culture medium, higher percentages of leachate dilutions could not be tested. However, on Caco-2 cells, dilutions up to 2% could have been assessed and a cell viability decrease starting from 1% dilution could be observed with the Leach-TCPP (leachate from the composite containing the reference flame retardant) which reached 54% for 2% dilution point.

Based on the cytotoxicity results, a single concentration was chosen for further testing. This concentration will be used to assess equimolarity and equi-toxicity effects and is set respectively at 0.2% and 1% in HaCaT and Caco-2 cells.

LDH Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay measuring the LDH release in cell supernatant was performed in parallel to the WST-1 assay.

The results of this second method assessing cytotoxicity showed no effect of the CS2 leachates at the concentrations tested (Figure 5.4-2). However, a lower sensitivity of the LDH assay compared to the WST-1 assay was observed with other products (as CS2 hardeners and CS2 A-Parts). Consequently, the results obtained do not contradict those of the WST-1 test, and will not be considered for further conclusions.

Figure 5.4-2: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the CS2 Leachates on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 8$).

5.4.2.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay

All CS2 Leachates from composite were tested for oxidative stress at one single dilution in culture medium corresponding to both equi-dose and equi-toxicity dilution (set respectively at 0.2% and 1% in Hacat and Caco-2 cells).

CM-H₂DCFDA results showed no induction of oxidative stress with Leachates at the dilutions tested, on both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells (Figure 5.4-3). On this latter, the experimental window framed by the solvent and the positive control was smaller than with HaCaT cells, due to a lower response from the positive control. As a result, the test is less sensitive than with the HaCaT cells, and the differences in the induction of oxidative stress are more difficult to assess.

Figure 5.4-3: CM-H₂DCFDA assay comparing the CS2 Leachates on HaCaT cells (A) and on Caco-2 cells (B). Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values ($n \geq 9$).

5.4.2.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS

No epigenetic modifications assessment was performed with the CS2 Leachates. Indeed, the volumes of leachate available were not sufficient to carry out this type of experiment.

5.4.2.4 Inflammation

No cytokine and chemokine measurements were performed for the CS2 leachates for any of the exposure route (inhalation, oral and dermal) as the volumes provided were not sufficient.

5.4.3 Genotoxicity

The assessment of genotoxicity is based on testing DNA damage in the oral and dermal model. To this end, two different assays were carried out. The induction of DNA strand breaks after cell treatment was assessed using comet assay, while the focus was on double strand breaks in 53BP1 assay.

Leachates were tested at the percentage of dilution defined by the WST-1 as non toxic (Section 5.4.2.1 Cytotoxicity, p. 125), set respectively at 0.2% and 1% in Hacat and Caco-2 cells.

Genotoxicity results showed an increase in the number of 53BP1 foci with the CS2 Leachates compared to the solvent control (except for Leach-TCPP) in Caco-2 cells (Figure 5.4-4, A₂) but not in HaCaT cells (Figure 5.4-4 **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**, A₁). However, this has to be taken carefully as the leachates are 5x more diluted in the culture medium for HaCaT cells than for Caco-2 cells. Statistically significant but small variations were also observed in Caco-2 cells with the reference leachate Leach-TCPP compared to Leach-SP3 and Leach-SP4.

Looking at the global DNA damage (single and double strand breaks) in both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells showed slight decreased with all leachates compared with the solvent control.

Taken together, the incubation with the CS2 leachates showed no induction of overall DNA damage with the comet assay. However, a slight increase in double-strand breaks was observed in the Caco-2 cells with the 53BP1 assay (from 1.2 to 1.4-fold the solvent control values).

These results are consistent with those observed for the composite ingredients: the genotoxic stress could be considered as negligible for the 4-AFD hardener (Section 5.2.3 Genotoxicity, p.103), whereas the A-Parts showed a clear induction of foci in 53BP1 but no effect on overall DNA damage in comet assay (Section 5.3.3 Genotoxicity, p.120).

Figure 5.4-4: 53BP1 assay (A) and comet assay (B) comparing the CS2 Leachates on HaCaT cells (A₁ and B₁) and on Caco-2 cells (A₂ and B₂). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥14 for 53BP1 assay, n≥11 for comet assay).

5.4.4 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

As no information about the composition and the substances concentration of the leachates is available, the response can only be represented according to the percentage of leachate in culture medium. Thus, a direct comparison with the CALUX[®] reference substance is not possible. Therefore, the reference product results are presented below as a positive control for the assay, but no conclusion can be done on the leachate absolute disruption potential.

Leachates could be tested up to 1% dilution in culture medium, as this is the upper limit for ethanol on CALUX cells, identified with a WST-1 assay.

Agonist test

The pre-tests of the CALUX[®] agonist assay showed no binding of the CS2 leachates Androgen Receptor (AR) in the investigated dilution range. On the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α), an agonist effect was observed with Leach-SP3 and Leach-TCPP, inducing respectively at 54% and 126% at highest tested concentration (Figure 5.4-5). Only the leachates giving an effect are shown. The binding was characterised with the complete assay protocol.

Figure 5.4-5: ER α agonist assay with the CALUX[®] reference substance, Leach-TCPP and Leach-SP3. Reported values are means \pm SD (n \geq 9).

At highest percentage of leachates Leach-SP3 and Leach-TCPP in the culture medium, the observed response was not reaching the maximal response level. Thus, EC₁₀ were calculated to characterize and compare both products (Table 5.4-2).

Table 5.4-2: (A) EC₅₀ and EC₁₀ values for ER α and AR agonist assays on the reference product as a positive control. (B) EC₁₀ values for ER α and AR agonist assays on the leachates. Curve fitting done with a 4PL model. Curve fitting done with 4PL model.

A	ER α agonist assay	AR agonist assay
CALUX [®] reference substance - EC ₅₀	1.03E-11 M	2.22E-10 M
CALUX [®] reference substance - EC ₁₀	2.05E-12 M	6.55E-11 M

B	ER α agonist assay	AR agonist assay
Leach-TCPP - EC ₁₀	3.96E-01 %	> 1 %
Leach-SP1 - EC ₁₀	> 1 %	> 1 %
Leach-SP2 - EC ₁₀	> 1 %	> 1 %
Leach-SP3 - EC ₁₀	3.99E-01 %	> 1 %
Leach-SP4 - EC ₁₀	> 1 %	> 1 %

Leach-SP3 and Leach-TCPP showed a response as ER α agonists, with a similar EC₁₀. The other leachates are not considered as agonist disruptors for ER α and AR.

Antagonist test

Results show no antagonist effect of CS2 leachates on the Estrogen Receptor α (ER α). For the Androgen Receptor (AR), Leach-SP3 and Leach-TCPP showed a clear inhibition (respectively 13% and 3% of

relative induction at highest tested concentration), whereas the other tested leachates were negative (Figure 5.4-6). A complete testing with specificity test was performed for Leach-SP3 and Leach-TCPP. Comparison of the test to its specificity control ruled out an antagonist response of Leach-SP3 for the AR receptor, as a good correlation is observed between the two curves ($R^2 = 0.9613$). In contrast, a shift was observed for the Leach-TCPP curves ($R^2 = 0.4352$) and thus the specificity test confirmed the effect for Leach-TCPP.

Figure 5.4-6: AR antagonist assay with the CALUX® reference substance, Leach-TCPP and Leach-SP3. Reported values are means \pm SD ($n \geq 3$).

EC_{50} were calculated for the reference substance and the Leach-TCPP. However, no conclusion can be done on the Leach-TCPP absolute disruption potential as the concentration units are different (Table 5.4-3).

Table 5.4-3: (A) IC_{50} values for $ER\alpha$ and AR antagonist assays on the reference product as a positive control. (B) EC_{50} values for $ER\alpha$ and AR antagonist assays on the leachates. Curve fitting done with 4PL model.

A	$ER\alpha$ antagonist assay	AR antagonist assay
CALUX® reference substance - IC_{50}	1.02E-08 M	5.07E-07 M

B	$ER\alpha$ antagonist assay	AR antagonist assay
Leach-TCPP - IC_{50}	> 1 %	1.26E-01 %
Leach-SP1 - IC_{50}	> 1 %	> 1 %
Leach-SP2 - IC_{50}	> 1 %	> 1 %
Leach-SP3 - IC_{50}	> 1 %	> 1 %
Leach-SP4 - IC_{50}	> 1 %	> 1 %

Thyroid disruption assay

Assessment of thyroid disruption potential of the leachates from composites of case study 2 using the transgenic zebrafish line *tg(tg:mCherry)* are shown below. Only Leach-TCPP, Leach-SP1, and Leach-SP3 were tested for thyroid disruption. The leachates were tested at two concentrations: 0.1% and 0.25%. No induction of the fluorescent signal was observed in the transgenic zebrafish line for the tested leachates from composites (Figure 5.4-7).

Figure 5.4-7: Thyroid disruption for the CS2 leachates. The leachates were tested at two concentrations: 0.1% (A) and 0.25% (B). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

5.4.5 Aquatic toxicity

Daphnia magna

Immobilization data in *Daphnia magna* individuals from OECD 202 tests with CS2 leachates (from composites) are presented below. In this case, the concentrations were not expected to be expressed in mg/L but rather in % of the maximum allowed concentration. Considering that the solvent of the leachates' concentrates is EtOH 95%, maximum allowed concentration in *Daphnia magna* is 0.1% of ethanol. Therefore, the samples were diluted 1000 times (0.1%) to obtain the maximum allowed concentration, and dilutions from this stock sample were carried out. Immobilization data results were obtained as % of motility (mobile *daphnias*), being 100% no effects (no toxicity) and 0% being complete immobilization (maximum toxicity).

No figure is presented since no toxicity was found in any of the leachates (motility of the *Daphnia* neonates = 100% in any of the dilutions of all substances) and reported in Table 5.4-4.

Table 5.4-4: EC₅₀ immobilization values at 24 and 48h for acute aquatic toxicity test (OECD 202) in CS2 leachates from composites. 100% refers to the maximum allowed concentration of ethanol in the *Daphnia magna* medium (i.e., 0.1% from the original leachates' concentrates).

Timepoint	Leach-TCPP	Leach-SP1	Leach-SP2	Leach-SP3	Leach-SP4
24h	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %
48h	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %

Zebrafish

Aquatic toxicity was not tested for the leachates of case study 2 in the zebrafish due to the low sample quantity.

5.4.6 Short summary

Composite leachates were tested in a limited number of assays, due to the limited quantity of material available and as these were considered a second priority. Effects were found on genotoxicity, corresponding to the effects also observed for A-parts and, for Leach-TCPP on endocrine disruption potential.

6 Results CS3

In this chapter the results for case study 3 are described.

6.1 CS3 SSbD routes

Case study 3 focused on the development of food packaging materials. In addition to a commercial reference film, three alternatives were developed:

- PE/EVOH without compatibilizer A=mLLDPE (47,5%wt) / B=mLLDPE (47,5%wt)/ C=EVOH (5%wt)
- PE/EVOH with compatibilizer A=mLLDPE (80%wt) /B=Comp (3%wt)/ C=EVOH (6%wt)
- PE/PA with compatibilizer A=mLLDPE (70%wt)+Comp (15%wt) / B=PA(15%wt)

These are listed in Table 6.1-1.

Table 6.1-1: SSbD routes for hazard assessment of CS3. The routes correspond to those described in D4.2

SSbD route	Description	Abbreviation
reference	PO/PA with compatibilizer 11 layers	Ref PO/PA/compat 11 layers
SSbD#1	PE/EVOH without compatibilizer A=mLLDPE (47,5%wt) / B=mLLDPE (47,5%wt)/ C=EVOH (5%wt)	PE/compat/PA 65 layers
SSbD#1	PE/EVOH with compatibilizer A=mLLDPE (80%wt) /B=Comp (3%wt)/ C=EVOH (6%wt)	PE/compat/EVOH 129 layers
SSbD#1	PE/PA with compatibilizer A=mLLDPE (70%wt)+Comp (15%wt) / B=PA(15%wt)	PE/EVOH 129 layers

6.2 CS3 Migration samples

The ingredients for the films were polymeric materials that come in pellets, which cannot be tested with *in vitro* assays. Alternatively, migration samples were used for hazard assessment. The migration samples were prepared in two different solvents, namely 3% acetic acid and 95% ethanol for the reference product and 3 alternatives. Migrations tests are fully described in paragraph 1.2.3.3.3 of Deliverable 4.2. Samples from the overall migration tests are used for hazard assessment. Table 6.2-1 indicates which assays were conducted for which migration samples.

Table 6.2-1: Overview of assays conducted for the CS3 migration samples. x = this assay was conducted for this substance; N/A = not applicable.

Health hazard	Endpoint	Assay	Exposure route	PO/PA/compat 11 B	PE/compat/PA 65 B	PE/EVOH 129 B	PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	PO/PA/compat 11 E95	PE/compat/PA 65 E95	PE/EVOH 129 E95	PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	WST-1	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	WST-1	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Inhalation	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	LDH	Inhalation	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	Alamar blue	Inhalation								
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	Alamar blue	Inhalation								
Human health general	Oxidative stress	CM-H2DCFDA	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Oxidative stress	CM-H2DCFDA	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Oxidative stress	ROS	Inhalation	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Oxidative stress	Protein carbonylation	Inhalation								
Human health general	Epigenetic changes	Epigenetic changes	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Inflammation	Cytokine release	Inhalation								
Human health general	Inflammation	Cytokine release	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Human health general	Inflammation	Cytokine release	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	COMET	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	COMET	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	53BP1	Dermal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Genotoxicity	N/A	53BP1	Oral	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Endocrine disruption	N/A	Calux battery AR/ER	N/A	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Endocrine disruption	N/A	Thyroid	N/A	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Ecotoxicity	N/A	Daphnia	N/A	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Ecotoxicity	N/A	Zebrafish	N/A								

6.2.1 ECHA data

ECHA data were retrieved from the ECHA database of the ingredients. For missing information, data were searched for in suppliers Safety Data Sheets (SDS) and / or literature.

Collected hazard data are presented in Table 6.2-2, Table 6.2-3 and Table 6.2-4. The substances in this table are used in all SSbD routes, as there is no difference in substances used between the routes.

MISS = missing information, no data available.

NC = not classified as hazardous.

NA = not applicable

1, 2, 3 = ECHA hazard categories for substances classification.

Table 6.2-2: CS3 ECHA data for human health hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS3_1	CS3_3	CS3_4	CS3_5	CS3_15
	Substance name	Exceed XP8318ML	Bynel 41E410DOW	Soarnol DC3203RB	Ultramid B36 LN	Orevac 18341
	Monomer or main substance	LDPE ethylene	Ethylene	Vinyl alcohol	Caprolactam	Maleic Anhydride
Human health endpoint	Carcinogenicity	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Mutagenicity	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Reproduction toxicity	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Endocrine disruption (human)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Respiratory sensitization	NC	NC	NC	NC	1
	Specific organ toxicity Repeated exposure	NC	NA	NC	NC	1
	Skin Sensitization	NC	NC	NC	NC	1A
	Acute toxicity oral	NC	NC	3	4	4
	Acute toxicity dermal	H066	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Acute toxicity inhalation	NC	NC	NC	4	NC
	Skin corrosion / irritation	NC	NC	NC	2	1B
	Eye damage / irritation	NC	NC	NC	2	1
	Aspiration hazard	1	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Specific organ toxicity Single exposure	NC	NA	NC	3	4

Table 6.2-3: CS3 ECHA data for environmental hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS3_1	CS3_3	CS3_4	CS3_5	CS3_15
	Substance name	Exceed XP8318ML	Bynel 41E410DOW	Soarnol DC3203RB	Ulramid B36 LN	Orevac 18341
	Monomer or main substance	LDPE ethylene	Ethylene	Vinyl alcohol	Caprolactam	Maleic Anhydride
Environmental Endpoint	persistence and bioaccumulation (PBT/vPvB)	NC	NC	MISS	NC	NC
	persistence and mobility (PMT/vPvM)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	endocrine disruption (environment)	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS	MISS
	Ozone	MISS	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS
	Chronic aquatic toxicity	NC	NC	MISS	NC	NC
	Acute aquatic toxicity	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC

Table 6.2-4: CS3 ECHA data for physical hazards

	SURPASS ID	CS3_1	CS3_3	CS3_4	CS3_5	CS3_15
	Substance name	Exceed XP8318ML	Bynel 41E410DOW	Soarnol DC3203RB	Ulramid B36 LN	Orevac 18341
	Monomer or main substance	LDPE ethylene	Ethylene	Vinyl alcohol	Caprolactam	Maleic Anhydride
Physical Endpoint	Explosives	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Flammable	2	1A	NC	NC	NC
	Flammable aerosols	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Oxidizing	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Gases under pressure	NC	H280	NC	NC	MISS
	Self-reactive	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Pyrophoric liquids, solids	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Self-heating	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Emits flammable gas	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Organic peroxides	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Corrosivity	NC	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Desensitized explosives	NC	MISS	NC	MISS	MISS

6.2.2 General human health

The assessment of the risks to human health is based first on testing the cytotoxicity of the products in our models (Section 2.1). Indeed, cytotoxicity assays are used to select concentrations for the other in vitro assays. Those include oxidative stress evaluation, cytokine release and DNA methylation.

6.2.2.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity data from WST-1 assay with CS3 migration samples are presented below.

Migration samples were tested at the highest non-toxic concentration of solvent. For Ethanol 95%, maximal percentage of dilution in culture medium was 0.2% and 2% for HaCaT and Caco-2 cells respectively. For Solvent B (3% acetic acid, concentrated with the same protocol as the leachates), maximal percentage of dilution in culture medium was 1% for both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells.

Cell viability results are shown in % with 100% being the non-treated cell viability.

Figure 6.2-1: Cytotoxicity results using WST-1 assay. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the migration samples, on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values ($n \geq 17$).

Despite fluctuations observed on HaCaT and Caco-2 cells with the highest possible percentages of migration samples, cell viability remained above 80% (Figure 6.2-1). Based on this result, the other endpoints will be investigated at this maximal percentage.

LDH Cytotoxicity assay

Cytotoxicity assay measuring the LDH release in cell supernatant was performed in parallel to the WST-1 assay.

Figure 6.2-2: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Cell viability compared to the solvent control with the migration samples on (A) HaCaT cells and (B) Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile ($n \geq 18$).

The results of this second method assessing cytotoxicity showed no effect of the migration samples at the concentrations tested and confirmed the WST-1 observations (Figure 6.2-2).

For the inhalation cell model, migration samples were tested in A549 and dTHP-1 monocultures, at a range of different concentrations starting from a 1:1000 dilution from the stocks. Solvent controls were

tested alongside at matching dilutions. None of the samples caused a significant effect on cell viability not even at the highest concentration tested (Figure 6.2-3). The largest effect was found in dTHP-1 cells exposed to the acetic acid samples where a non-significant 5% decrease in viability was found when exposed to PE/compat/EVOH 129B compared to the solvent control (Figure 6.2-4).

Figure 6.2-3: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Cell viability compared to the non-treated control with the migration samples on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are means \pm SEM (n=3).

Figure 6.2-4: Cytotoxicity results using LDH release measurement. Cell viability compared to the non-treated control with the migration samples on A549 cells (left panel) and dTHP-1 cells (right panel). Reported values are means \pm SEM (n=3).

6.2.2.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay

The acetic acid samples were tested for oxidative stress at one single dilution in culture medium corresponding to both equi-dose and equi-toxicity dilution (set at 1% in both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells). For Ethanol samples, this dilution in culture was set respectively at 0.2% and 1% in Hacat and Caco-2 cells).

CM-H₂DCFDA results showed no induction of oxidative stress at the dilutions tested, on both HaCaT and Caco-2 cells (Figure 6.2-5). For the assay on Caco-2 cells, samples in Ethanol 95%, the experimental window framed by the solvent and the positive control was smaller than with HaCaT cells, due to a lower response from the positive control. As a result, the test is less sensitive than with the HaCaT cells, and the differences in the induction of oxidative stress are more difficult to assess.

However, taken together the oxidative stress can be considered negligible for the migration samples.

Figure 6.2-5: CM-H₂DCFDA assay comparing the migration samples on HaCaT cells (A) and on Caco-2 cells (B). Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values (n \geq 8).

Cellular ROS assay

In the inhalation A549 cell model, ROS production as a measure of oxidative stress was assessed after exposure to the migration samples at equimolar concentrations corresponding to 1:1000 dilution from the stocks. Samples in EtOH showed significant higher levels of ROS when compared to the solvent control in the case of the reference PO/PA/compat 11 (after 2h exposure) and the PE/compat/EVOH 129 (after 5h exposure). However, only the solvent control was already significantly higher than the solvent control, indicating an effect of the solvent in the ROS production. Both PE/compat/PA 65 and PE/EVOH 129 migration samples showed significantly lower ROS levels than the reference sample (Figure 6.2-6).

Figure 6.2-6: ROS levels after exposure to Ethanol migration samples. A549 cells were exposed to the EtOH migration samples and ROS production was assessed after 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h and 5h. Percentage of ROS production compared to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC) with the reference PO/PA/compat 11 and the alternative products. Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to solvent control, and # indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to reference substance PO/PA/compat 11.

Migration samples in Acetic acid showed significant higher levels of ROS when compared to the solvent control in the case of the reference PO/PA/compat 11 (after 5h exposure) and the PE/EVOH 129 (after 3h exposure) (Figure 6.2-7). However, the solvent control was already significantly higher than the negative control, indicating an effect of the acetic acid in the ROS production. The migration sample PE/compat/PA 65 showed significantly lower ROS levels than the reference.

Figure 6.2-7: ROS levels after exposure to Acetic Acid migration samples. A549 cells were exposed to the Acetic Acid samples and ROS production was assessed after 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h and 5h. Percentage of ROS production compared to the solvent control (SC) and the positive control (PC) with the reference PO/PA/compat 11 and the alternative products. Reported values are mean \pm SEM (n=3). One-way ANOVA analysis followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test was performed, * indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to solvent control, and # indicates $p < 0.05$ compared to reference substance PO/PA/compat 11.

6.2.2.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS

Modulation of cytosine methylation in total DNA after treatment of Caco-2 cells with the migration samples was assessed using HPLC-MS/MS.

The percentage of 5-methylcytosine was divided by a factor 2 upon incubating the positive control (5 μ M of 5-Azacytidine). However, no change in methylation status was observed with the migration samples at the tested dilution factor (Figure 6.2-8).

Figure 6.2-8: HPLC-MS/MS assay assessing the part of methylated Cytosine in total DNA after incubation with the migration samples, on Caco-2 cells. Reported values are medians \pm interquartile and highest/lowest values ($n \geq 8$).

6.2.2.4 Inflammation

Cytokine measurement of the inhalation model

For the inhalation model no data on potential inflammatory response of the migration samples was collected.

Cytokine measurement of the oral and dermal model

The oral model (CaCo2 cells) and the dermal model (HaCat cells) were used to measure the potential inflammatory response of migration samples. After exposure to the migration samples, medium samples were collected to detect levels of cytokines and chemokines (IFN- γ , IL-1b, IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL12p70, IL-17A, IP10, MCP-1, TGB- β 1, TNF- α). For both the migration samples in acetic acid and in ethanol the cytokines and chemokines were below detection limit and/or did not give a significantly different response compared to the solvent control (data not shown).

6.2.3 Genotoxicity

The assessment of genotoxicity is based on testing DNA damage in the oral and dermal model. To this end, two different assays were carried out. The induction of DNA strand breaks after cell treatment was assessed using comet assay, while the focus was on double strand breaks in 53BP1 assay.

Despite significant differences for some migration samples in Ethanol on Caco-2 cells, observations of the 53BP1 results showed no major effect on double-strand breaks, either for samples in ethanol or in acetic acid (Figure 6.2-9).

Figure 6.2-9: 53BP1 assay comparing the migration samples on HaCaT cells (A) and on Caco-2 cells (B). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥12).

The comet assay results showed that all samples in acetic acid or ethanol induce a reduction in total DNA damage, sometimes significantly (Figure 6.2-10). They may have a protective role, but they are not considered genotoxic.

Figure 6.2-10: Comet assay comparing the migration samples on HaCaT cells (A) and on Caco-2 cells (B). Reported values are medians ± interquartile and highest/lowest values (n≥11).

6.2.4 Endocrine disruption

ER α and AR CALUX assay and H295R Steroidogenesis assay

Assessment of the potential effect of the case study 3 migration samples on Estrogen receptor α (ER α), Androgen receptor (AR), and steroidogenesis was outsourced to BioDetection Systems. The samples, both in acetic acid and in ethanol, were tested at 0.1% in assay medium.

Prior to the H295R exposure, a pre-screening with ER α and AR CALUX[®] is performed to investigate if compound carry-over from the H295R shows activity in the CALUX[®] readouts. Very potent estrogenic or androgenic compounds or samples may give false positive results in the readout. To be certain both the ER α and AR agonistic and antagonistic modes are measured for all samples. No activity for any of

the extracts in both assays was observed for either the agonistic or the antagonistic modes (data not shown).

As part of the H295R steroidogenesis assay, cytotoxicity was determined for each compound (MTT assay), which showed that there was no impact on cell viability (data not shown). Moreover, none of the extracts tested showed an effect on steroidogenesis.

These results are based on only a single analysis per compound due to the low sample amount. To further meet the OECD criteria for testing in the H295R steroidogenesis assay, at least a second analysis would be needed.

Thyroid disruption assay

Assessment of thyroid disruption potential of the CS3 migration samples using the transgenic zebrafish line *tg(tg:mCherry)* are shown below. Due to the low sample volume, the samples in acetic acid (Figure 6.2-11A) were tested at 1000x dilution (0.1%) and the samples in ethanol (Figure 6.2-11B) at 0.5%. No induction of the fluorescent signal was observed in the transgenic zebrafish line for the tested migration samples.

Figure 6.2-11: Thyroid disruption assay for the migration samples in acetic acid (A) and ethanol (B). Significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis test, **** indicates $p < 0.001$.

6.2.5 Aquatic toxicity

Daphnia magna

Immobilization data in *Daphnia magna* individuals from OECD 202 tests with CS3 migration samples are presented below. Similarly to the CS2 leachates (see section 5.3.5 for more information), the concentrations are expressed in % of the maximum allowed concentration. Considering that the solvents of the samples were EtOH 95% and acetic acid, maximum allowed concentration in *Daphnia*

magna were 0.1% in both cases. Therefore, the samples were diluted 1000 times (0.1%) to obtain the maximum allowed concentration, and dilutions from both stock samples were carried out. In case of the acetic acid stock (100%) a pH adjustment was needed to maintain the pH inside the acceptable range for the exposures (pH of 6.0 – 9.0 approximately). Immobilization data results were obtained as % of motility (mobile *Daphnias*), being 100% no effects (no toxicity) and 0% being complete immobilization (maximum toxicity).

No figure is presented since no toxicity was found for any of the samples neither in ethanol nor in acetic acid (motility of the *Daphnia* neonates = 100% in any of the dilutions of all migration samples), as they are expressed in Table 6.2-5.

Table 6.2-5: EC₅₀ immobilization values at 24 and 48h for acute aquatic toxicity test (OECD 202) in CS3 migration samples. 100% refers to the maximum allowed concentration of acetic acid or ethanol respectively, in the *Daphnia magna* medium (i.e., 0.1% from the original migration samples' concentrates).

Time-point	PO/PA/c ompat 11 B	PE/com pat/PA 65 B	PE/EVO H 129 B	PE/com pat/EVO H 129 B	PO/PA/co mpat 11 E95	PE/compa t/PA 65 E95	PE/EVO H 129 E95	PE/comp at/EVOH 129 E95
24h	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %
48h	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %	> 100 %

Zebrafish

Aquatic toxicity was not tested for the migration samples of case study 3 in the zebrafish due to the low sample amount.

6.2.6 Short summary

None of the migration samples induced any response in the assays conducted. Toxicity testing was limited due to toxicity observed by the solvent. Likely, quantities of migrated substances in the samples are relatively low (see also D4.2 and D4.4), too low to induce any effect at the low concentrations tested and/or in comparison to the effects of the solvents used. Therefore, no conclusions can be drawn on a potential hazard of the substances migrating from the MultiNanoLayered films for either the reference or the alternative products.

7 Hazard scoring

7.1 Purpose and strategy

As proposed in the JRC framework, hazard scoring is used to compare an SSbD alternative option to a reference product. To allow comparison of the outcomes between a reference substance/product and a SSRbD alternative substance product, an approach, referred to as scoring strategy was developed to calculate a hazard score. This scoring strategy is based on calculation steps to obtain a hazard score for each of the substances and for the complete products.

As described in D5.1, hazard assessment results in four scores as scoring is based on four pillars: human health effects, genotoxicity, endocrine disruption (ED) potential and (fresh water) ecotoxicity. Exposure route specific human health effects can be subdivided into three categories, namely oral,

inhalation and dermal. This allows assessment of hazard and exposure in an exposure route dependent manner.

Hazard information is based on three types of data: available hazard data (ECHA database), QSAR modelling and *in vitro* assessment. As proposed in D5.1, the idea was to integrate all data into a single score, for each of the pillars. However, as the case studies work with new products and ingredients, the available hazard data contained many data gaps. In addition, available data in the ECHA database is generally a classification, not a concentration inducing a specific hazard.. As these classifications are not linear (going from a 2 to 1 classification does not mean that the hazard is twice as high), they do not allow calculating a score. As an alternative approach, we will use the available hazard data as an expert evaluation to evaluate the scores.

Calculation of scoring for the QSAR results follows the same approach as for the *in vitro* data. Results of QSAR scoring are described in D4.4.

7.2 Hazard scoring steps

Hazard scoring follows several steps, that are listed below and described in more detail in the following paragraphs. These steps are applied to *in vitro* assay outcomes and outcomes of QSAR modelling and follow a sequential order.

- Data for hazard scoring
- Setting a response for a no effect level and a low effect level
- Evaluation of statistical significance
- Normalization of the data
- Calculation of absolute differences
- Averaging of assay outcomes measuring the same health hazard
- Thresholds for substance hazard
- Combining ingredient scores into a product score and their thresholds

7.2.1 Data for hazard scoring

The data required for hazard scoring are the results of the *in vitro* assays described in this deliverable (Chapter 4 – 6) and QSAR modelling (D4.4). Information is required on the pillars (human health, genotoxicity, endocrine disruption or ecotoxicity), further specified for general human health (cytotoxicity, oxidative stress, epigenetic changes or cytokine response), the exposure route for which the model is representative (oral, dermal or inhalation), and the specific assay conducted.

Furthermore, information is required on the concentration at which the assay was conducted and the unit of the outcome. The assays described in this deliverable, were either conducted in a range of concentrations to obtain a concentration that results in a 20% (or 50%) response (A) or the assays were conducted at a single concentration and an assay response was measured (B). The important difference is that the assays A give a concentration as a result, whereas the assays B give a response (a value from the assay, e.g. µg/ml for cytokine responses) as a result.

Both types of results were used for hazard scoring but follow a slightly different calculation, as detailed later. For each of the substances tested, the mean or median results of the substance and the corresponding solvent control and, if available, the positive control is listed. Finally, information on statistical significance is added. The latter is important as scoring is calculated from means or medians only, not considering variation in the response. By including information on statistical significance, the variation in the response is included indirectly.

7.2.2 Setting a response for a no effect level and a low effect level

Each assay gives a different outcome in a different unit. Some assays have very large values as readout, whereas others are very small. To be able to compare the responses from different assays, two reference points on a dose response curve are needed. These reference points are used to normalize the data, to compare the scores between assays, and to add scores of the ingredients to obtain a product score in the end. As there are two types of data, (A) tested in a range, giving a concentration as outcome and (B) tested at a single concentration, giving a response as outcome, two types of setting reference points are required.

A: Tested in a range, resulting in a concentration as outcome

Figure 7.2-1 illustrates an example of a dose response curve for two substances (black and red lines), where the concentration is plotted on the x-axis and the response on the y-axis, for example for cytotoxicity. At low concentrations the cells do not die, but as the concentration increases, more and more cell death is observed. If the curves shift to the left, this is considered a higher toxicity, likewise, a shift to the right is a lower toxicity. The yellow line indicates the 50% effect level (EC50). A comparison of toxicity between substances is made on the x-axis, where the yellow line indicates a higher EC50 for the red substance compared to the black one. If the EC50 is above a certain level, it can be concluded that there is no toxicity. For comparison, using *in vivo* data as an example (as classification limits are generally based on *in vivo* data), this reference point can be considered the highest classification limit. Similarly, if the EC50 is somewhat lower, it can be considered a small effect. There is an obvious response, but the effect is still small. For comparison with *in vivo* data, this reference point can be considered the second highest classification limit (<https://reachonline.eu/clp/en/annex-i-3.html>). For normalization of the data, these two reference points are required and should be provided by an expert in the interpretation of the specific assay. The value for these reference points are the concentration on the x-axis, as the response for this type of data is also expressed as a concentration.

Figure 7.2-1: Example of a dose-response curve, with on the x-axis the concentration and on the y-axis the response. The yellow lines indicate the EC50, which is the concentration giving and effect of 50%.

B: Tested at a single concentration, resulting in a response as outcome

For substances tested at a single concentration, no full dose response curve is available. The outcome is one value on the dose-response curve, whereas the location on the curve and the full curve are unknown. The solvent control is assumed not have an effect on the parameter tested. The response of the solvent control is therefore the first reference point and corresponds to the blue line in Figure 7.2-2. A small effect on the dose response curve should be a response obviously higher (or lower, depending on the read-out) than the solvent control, but still a small effect. This difference can be expressed as a percentage difference from the solvent control. A value of 20% difference from the solvent control could be used as a default (response of the solvent only is the first reference point, response 20% higher or lower is the second reference point), but should be evaluated for each assay, as the sensitivity of biological organisms to different assay response parameters can be different.

Figure 7.2-2: Example of a dose-response curve, with on the x-axis the concentration and on the y-axis the response. The blue and green lines indicate a no effect and small effect level.

Note that for both A and B, the reference points are not set in stone. Instead, they are based on expert judgement. Although the reference points can be discussed, it is important to establish them early in the calculation, as at this stage, the assay responses and reference points have a meaning and are still understandable. Setting reference points avoids applying weighing factors later in the calculation of the score to align the variety of responses.

7.2.3 Evaluation of statistical significance

Evaluation of statistical significance (see chapter 3.8) is the first calculation step for hazard scoring. In this step, statistical significant effects are further calculated whereas non-significant effects are set equal to the effect of the solvent control. With the statistical significance, the variation in the outcomes is considered.

7.2.4 Normalization of the data

Normalization of the data is the main step in calculating hazard scores. Again, this is slightly different when multiple concentrations were tested per substance (A) than in case only a single concentration was assessed (B). For both types of data, normalization of the data is done towards the two reference points. The no effect reference point results in a score of 0; whereas the small effect reference point results in a score of 1. Also, both types of data include a logarithmic transformation due to the multiplicativity of biological effects. Each treatment with a substance causes a percentage change in the assay response parameter. The conversion to a logarithmic scale results in scores that can be added and subtracted instead of multiplied and divided. In the logarithmic scale, a treatment with a substance with a score of 2 has a biological effect of the same magnitude as two treatments with substances that each have a score of 1.

A: Tested in a range, resulting in a concentration as outcome

For substances tested in a range, the following normalization step is applied:

$$\text{Normalized result} = \frac{\log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{OutcomeSubstance}}{\text{NoEffectConc}} \right)}{\log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{SmallEffectConc}}{\text{NoEffectConc}} \right)}$$

Where:

OutcomeSubstance = the result of the test for a specific substance

NoEffectConc = the first reference point, which is considered no effect

SmallEffectConc = the second reference point, which is considered a small effect

In cases where the outcome for the substance (i.e. EC₂₀ or EC₅₀) is lower than the no effect concentration, the outcome of the substance is set to the value of the no effect concentration. This would mean that the specific substance is less toxic than the solvent control, which can be considered not toxic (applies to test data in a range only).

The following reference points were used to calculate the scores. For cytotoxicity, 1000 mg/L (or 1000M) was considered not toxic. At 100 mg/L (or 100M), the substance is considered slightly toxic. For endocrine disruption (CALUX assays), 0.0001M was considered not toxic and 0.00001M was considered slightly toxic. For Daphnia and Zebrafish data, the ecotoxicity classification limits of 1000mg/L (not toxic) and 100mg/L (slightly toxic) were used.

B: Tested at a single concentration, resulting in a response as outcome

For substances tested at a single concentration, the following normalization step is applied:

$$\text{Normalized result} = \frac{\log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{ResponseSubstance}}{\text{ResponseSolvent}} \right)}{\log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{SmallResponse}}{\text{ResponseSolvent}} \right)}$$

Where:

ResponseSubstance = the result of the test for a specific substance (at a single concentration)

ResponseSolvent = the first reference point, the response of the solvent, which is considered to have no effect

SmallResponse = the second reference point, which is considered a small effect

The following reference points were used to calculate the scores. For cytokine release (inflammation response) and oxidative stress a factor of 0.2 (20% increase or decrease) was used. For the thyroid assay a factor of 1.0 was used. For genotoxicity a factor of 0.5 or 2.0 was used for the 53BP1 assay and the comet assay respectively.

7.2.5 Calculation of absolute differences

The next step is to calculate absolute differences. Some assays give a lower outcome when a substance induces an effect (an exposure results in a lower response than the solvent). After normalization, this results in a negative score. Similarly to positive scores, in such cases an score of -1 means a small effect.

To be able to add effects of different assays in subsequent steps, the absolute values are determined. This results in a score for each (measured) substance in each (measured) assay.

7.2.6 Averaging of assay outcomes measuring the same health hazard

Subsequently, the scores of each substance for each assay can be averaged to obtain a score for each pillar.

Like for the pillar general human health effect, inhalation, oral and dermal scores are calculated by averaging the cytotoxicity score, oxidative stress score, epigenetic changes score and cytokine response score. The scores for specific exposure routes are calculated from the assays using cell models relevant for these exposure routes, so intestinal cells for the oral exposure route, dermal cells for the dermal exposure route and lung cells for the inhalation exposure route. The scores for cytotoxicity, oxidative stress, epigenetic changes and cytokine responses are averaged to obtain a human health score (general or route specific).

Genotoxicity was assessed using two assays and in dermal cells and intestinal cells. For each assay a score is calculated, based on the average of both cell models. These are averaged to obtain a score for genotoxicity.

For endocrine disruption a score is calculated for androgen activity, estrogen activity, thyroid activity and, if available, for steroidal effects. These are averaged to obtain a score for endocrine disruption.

Ecotoxicity was based on aquatic toxicity as assessed in Daphnia and Zebrafish. The scores of the two models were averaged to obtain a score for fresh water ecotoxicity.

Together this results in a hazard score for each ingredient on the four pillars, and for human health effects also for the three exposure routes.

7.2.7 Thresholds for substance hazard

The scores calculated can be used to compare hazard of the substances. To facilitate this, thresholds can be set to indicate a lower or higher hazard. A score of 0 means that there is no hazard based on the assay results. A score of 1 means that there is a small effect. A higher score corresponds to an increased hazard. This is a first hazard classification, based on the evaluation of a single substance, not a comparison with other substances.

Thresholds for hazard evaluation of the substances were set as follows:

Toxicity score	Hazard level
Score < 0.8	no hazard
0.8 < Score < 1.2	small effect
1.2 < Score < 1.6	some hazard
Score > 1.6	hazard

7.2.8 Combining ingredient scores into a performance score and their thresholds

A product score for the reference route and the alternative route was calculated by adding the scores of each of the ingredients of a production route.

In the final step, a Difference in Performance (DiP) is calculated, relative to the reference route. This DiP allows comparison of the alternative route with the reference route with respect to hazard. The following formula was used:

$$DiP = (reference - alternative)/reference$$

Where:

reference = the product score of the reference product

alternative = the product score of the alternative product.

Again, thresholds can be defined to aid interpretation of the scores. In this case, a DiP of 0 means that the alternative product has an equal hazard score as the reference product. Lower scores mean increased hazard, and higher scores imply less hazard. The following scores and categorization was used.

Category	Hazard of alternative in comparison to reference	Score
0	deterioration	Score < -0.2
1	equal	-0.2 < Score < 0.2
2	improvement	0.2 < Score < 0.5
3	substantial improvement	Score > 0.5

The categories indicated can be used to evaluate hazard in the context of exposure/release (D4.2), Life Cycle Analysis (D4.6) and Life Cycle Costing (D4.5).

7.2.9 Scoring considerations

Some considerations are important to mention with respect to hazard scoring, these are listed below.

- The scores are a simplified way of representing the data. They are based on averages and calculation steps. The assays used are developed to assess a specific hazard, with all calculation steps, the effects of an assay giving a response can be averaged with an assay not giving a response. This could result in a lower score, even though there could still be a relevant hazard. It is therefore important to evaluate the individual assay results as well.
- The scores are based on the assays conducted. Many of these assays give an indication of hazard, which should be further assessed to be able to draw conclusions on actual hazard. Nevertheless, the results can be used to get an indication of possible hazard in an early stage of development.

- The substances have been tested with *in vitro* assays, while for many substances the mechanisms of action are unknown. As there is currently no information on applicability of the assays to the specific substances assessed, we have no reason not to rely the data. Nevertheless, this is important to keep in mind when evaluating the outcomes.
- Hazard as such is only an indication of a possible risk and only relevant when exposure occurs. It is therefore important to evaluate hazard in combination with exposure, whether that be occupational, environmental, or consumer exposure.

7.3 CS1

7.3.1 Hazard scores

The assays measuring the same endpoint have been averaged to obtain a single score for each endpoint. Table 7.3-1 and Table 7.3-2 show the scoring outcomes for each of the substances tested, scores are summarized and color-coded in Table 7.3-3 and

Table 7.3-4. A score of 0 means that there is no hazard identified, a score of 1 means that there is a small hazard. Higher scores indicate increased hazard.

Table 7.3-1: Hazard scores of Bi-Cat, Cystamine, THEED and Disulfide. A score of 0 means that there is no hazard identified, a score of 1 means that there is a small hazard. Higher scores indicate increased hazard. Blank cells mean that no assay was conducted for this substance and this effect.

		Bi-Cat	Cystamine	THEED	Disulfide
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	0.26	0.00	0.00	0.21
	Oxidative stress	2.31	0.31	0.24	0.16
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.40	0.48	0.00	0.61
	Score	0.74	0.20	0.06	0.25
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	53BP1	0.60	1.07	0.28	1.37
	Score	0.30	0.53	0.14	0.69
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.23
	Score	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.41
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	1.00	1.90	1.00	1.98
	Zebrafish	2.47	0.00	0.00	0.00
	QSARs	n/a	4.27	3.00	2.94
	Score	1.74	2.05	1.33	1.64
Human health inhalation	Cytotoxicity	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.64
	Oxidative stress	0.64	0.94	0.73	0.49
	Inflammation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.21	0.31	0.24	0.38
Human health oral	Cytotoxicity	0.33	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Oxidative stress	3.58	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.74
	Score	0.98	0.03	0.00	0.19
Human health dermal	Cytotoxicity	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Oxidative stress	2.71	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	1.19	1.30	0.00	1.09
	Score	1.45	0.43	0.00	0.36

Table 7.3-2: Hazard scores for the polyols. A score of 0 means that there is no hazard identified, a score of 1 means that there is a small hazard. Higher scores indicate increased hazard. Blank cells mean that no assay was conducted for this substance and this effect.

		Polyol I	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	0.00	0.22	0.00	1.05	0.00
	Oxidative stress	0.00	3.03	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.24	0.84	0.00	0.41	0.00
	Score	0.06	1.02	0.00	0.36	0.00
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	53BP1	0.33	0.16	0.42	0.98	0.00
	Score	0.16	0.08	0.21	0.49	0.00
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	1.00	1.19	1.00	1.99	1.00
	Zebrafish	0.00	2.00	2.12	1.91	0.00
	QSARs	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1.78
	Score	0.50	1.59	1.56	1.95	0.93
Human health inhalation	Cytotoxicity	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Oxidative stress	0.00	1.29	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.00	0.43	0.00	0.00	0.00
Human health oral	Cytotoxicity	0.00	0.43	0.00	1.56	0.00
	Oxidative stress	0.00	3.28	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.23	0.00
	Score	0.00	0.93	0.00	0.70	0.00
Human health dermal	Cytotoxicity	0.00	0.24	0.00	1.59	0.00
	Oxidative stress	0.00	4.51	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.73	2.52	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.24	2.42	0.00	0.53	0.00

n/a = not available, this endpoint was not assessed for this substance

Table 7.3-3: Summary and color-coding for hazard scores of Bi-Cat, Cystamine, THEED and Disulfide.

	Bi-Cat	Cystamine	THEED	Disulfide
Human health general	0.74	0.20	0.06	0.25
Genotoxicity	0.30	0.53	0.14	0.69
Endocrine disruption	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.41
Ecotoxicity	1.74	2.05	1.33	1.64
Human health inhalation	0.21	0.31	0.24	0.38
Human health oral	0.98	0.03	0.00	0.19
Human health dermal	1.45	0.43	0.00	0.36

Table 7.3-4: Summary and color-coding for hazard scores of the polyols.

	Polyol I	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D
Human health general	0.06	1.02	0.00	0.36	0.00
Genotoxicity	0.16	0.08	0.21	0.49	0.00
Endocrine disruption	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	0.50	1.59	1.56	1.95	0.93
Human health inhalation	0.00	0.43	0.00	0.00	0.00
Human health oral	0.00	0.93	0.00	0.70	0.00
Human health dermal	0.24	2.42	0.00	0.53	0.00

Of the catalysts tested, Bi-Cat, the reference catalyst, overall has the highest hazard score, which is mainly due to the oxidative stress response it induces and the effects in zebrafish. In comparison, Cystamine and THEED, the two alternatives for Bi-Cat (SSbD#1 route), generally have lower hazard scores. However, Cystamine has a high ecotoxicological hazard score and genotoxicity score. The most important effects of the disulfide (SSbD#2 route) are its genotoxic and endocrine disruption potential and its aquatic toxicity in Daphnia.

Of the tested polyols, polyol A has the highest hazard score for human health effects, mainly relate to the effects in the dermal model. The genotoxic and endocrine disruption potential of all polyols is low. However, all bio-based polyols have a potential ecotoxicological hazard.

7.3.2 Differences in Performance (DiP)

The hazard scores of substances are added and a Difference in Performance (DiP) is calculated. For CS1, the SSRbD alternatives are composed of more ingredients than the reference product. By adding the scores of the ingredients, the DiP will inevitably be worse (=lower) than the score for the reference product. Nevertheless, the hazards of the products with catalysts and disulfide can be compared on a product level. A DiP of 0 means that the SSRbD alternative is equally hazardous as the reference product, this is also the reason that the reference product scores 0 on all endpoints. A lower DiP means a higher hazard and a higher score means a lower hazard. The product scores of CS1 are shown in Table 7.3-5 and Table 7.3-6.

Table 7.3-5: Product scores for fossil based products.

		Reference route	SSbD#2 with fossil based polyol	SSbD#1 with fossil based polyol + Bi-Cat	SSbD#1 with fossil based polyol + Cystamine	SSbD#1 with fossil based polyol + THEED
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	0.00	-0.21	-0.26	0.00	0.00
	Oxidative stress	0.00	-0.16	-2.31	-0.31	-0.24
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.00	-2.49	-1.63	-1.96	0.00
	Score	0.00	-4.03	-12.13	-3.24	-0.99
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	53BP1	0.00	-4.19	-1.83	-3.26	-0.86
	Score	0.00	-4.19	-1.83	-3.26	-0.86
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	-0.03	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	-1.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.00	-0.41	-0.01	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	0.00	-1.98	-1.00	-1.90	-1.00
	Zebrafish	0.00	0.00	-2.47	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.00	-3.28	-3.47	-4.11	-2.66

Table 7.3-6: Product scores for bio-based products.

		SSbD#0	SSbD#2	SSbD#1 + Bi-Cat	SSbD#1 + Cystamine	SSbD#1 + THEED
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	0.00	-0.17	-0.20	0.00	0.00
	Oxidative stress	0.00	-0.05	-0.76	-0.10	-0.08
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.00	-0.49	-0.32	-0.38	0.00
	Score	0.00	-0.18	-0.53	-0.14	-0.04
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	53BP1	0.00	-0.88	-0.38	-0.68	-0.18
	Score	0.00	-0.88	-0.38	-0.68	-0.18
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	-0.03	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	-1.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.00	-0.41	-0.01	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	0.00	-0.38	-0.19	-0.37	-0.19
	Zebrafish	0.00	0.00	-0.41	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.00	-0.27	-0.29	-0.34	-0.22

The fossil based routes result in lower DiP than the bio-based route. This can be explained by the higher scores of Polyols A, B, C and D versus Polyol I. Noteworthy are the higher scores for genotoxicity for the catalysts and disulfide (SSbD#2, SSbD#1 + Bi-Cat, SSbD#1 + Cystamine), the score for endocrine disruption for the SSbD#2 route and the high scores for ecotoxicological hazards for all alternative routes.

The DiPs should be evaluated with caution. Not all substances have been tested with all assays, for a more complete information on hazard, all assays should be included.

7.4 CS2

7.4.1 Hazard scores

The assays measuring the same endpoint have been merged to obtain a single score for each endpoint. Table 7.4-1, Table 7.4-2 and Table 7.4-3 show the scoring outcomes for each of the substances tested, scores are summarized and color-coded in Table 7.4-4, Table 7.4-5 and Table 7.4-6. A score of 0 means that there is no hazard identified, a score of 1 means that there is a small hazard. Higher scores indicate increased hazard.

Table 7.4-1: Hazard scores for the hardeners. A score of 0 means that there is no hazard identified, a score of 1 means that there is a small hazard. Higher scores indicate increased hazard. Blank cells mean that no assay was conducted for this substance and this effect.

		MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	0.00	1.25	0.90
	Oxidative stress	0.90	1.56	1.95
	Epigenetic changes	0.12	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.08	0.47	0.43
	Score	0.27	0.82	0.82
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.00	0.00
	53BP1	0.00	1.66	0.00
	Score	0.00	0.83	0.00
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	1.45	0.68	0.00
	Score	0.48	0.23	0.00
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	3.20	3.40	3.52
	Zebrafish	0.47	2.60	3.21
	QSARs	11.08	10.40	5.09
	Score	4.92	5.47	3.94
Human health inhalation	Cytotoxicity	0.00	1.80	1.15
	Oxidative stress	0.00	4.01	5.84
	Inflammation	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.00	1.94	2.33
Human health oral	Cytotoxicity	0.00	0.86	0.77
	Oxidative stress	0.85	0.00	0.00
	Epigenetic changes	0.12	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.24	0.21	0.19
Human health dermal	Cytotoxicity	0.00	1.08	0.79
	Oxidative stress	1.87	0.66	0.00
	Inflammation	0.23	1.41	1.28
	Score	0.70	1.05	0.69

Table 7.4-2: Hazard scores for the A-parts. A score of 0 means that there is no hazard identified, a score of 1 means that there is a small hazard. Higher scores indicate increased hazard. Blank cells mean that no assay was conducted for this substance and this effect.

		AP-CL	AP1	AP2	AP3	AP4
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	1.24	1.28	1.37	1.25	1.42
	Oxidative stress	1.20	0.95	0.43	0.92	1.38
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.17	0.28	0.35	0.28	0.35
	Score	0.65	0.63	0.54	0.61	0.79
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	53BP1	3.60	4.14	3.30	3.33	3.48
	Score	1.80	2.07	1.65	1.67	1.74
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.00	n/a
	Score	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	2.25	2.40	2.00	2.22	2.04
	Zebrafish	2.52	2.55	n/a	2.74	n/a
	QSARs	3.72	3.72	3.72	3.72	3.72
	Score	2.83	2.89	2.86	2.89	2.88
Human health inhalation	Cytotoxicity	0.88	0.93	n/a	0.93	n/a
	Oxidative stress	0.00	0.00	n/a	1.22	n/a
	Inflammation	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.00	n/a
	Score	0.29	0.31	0.00	0.72	0.00
Human health oral	Cytotoxicity	1.36	1.46	1.29	1.37	1.38
	Oxidative stress	1.63	1.40	0.00	1.55	1.57
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Score	1.00	0.95	0.43	0.97	0.98
Human health dermal	Cytotoxicity	1.47	1.44	1.45	1.44	1.46
	Oxidative stress	1.96	1.46	0.87	0.00	1.19
	Inflammation	0.35	0.56	0.35	0.56	0.35
	Score	1.26	1.15	0.89	0.66	1.00

n/a = not available, this endpoint was not assessed for this substance

Table 7.4-3: Hazard scores for the leachates. A score of 0 means that there is no hazard identified, a score of 1 means that there is a small hazard. Higher scores indicate increased hazard. Blank cells mean that no assay was conducted for this substance and this effect.

		Leach-TCPP	Leach-SP1	Leach-SP2	Leach-SP3	Leach-SP4
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	1.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Oxidative stress	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Epigenetic changes	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Inflammation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	0.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.48	0.58	0.49	0.47
	53BP1	0.00	0.21	0.22	0.47	0.37
	Score	0.00	0.35	0.40	0.48	0.42
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	0.00	n/a	0.00	n/a
	Score	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Zebrafish	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	QSARs	21.85	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Score	11.43	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Human health inhalation	Cytotoxicity	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Oxidative stress	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Inflammation	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Score	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Human health oral	Cytotoxicity	2.69	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Oxidative stress	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Epigenetic changes	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Inflammation	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Score	1.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Human health dermal	Cytotoxicity	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Oxidative stress	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Score	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

n/a = not available, this endpoint was not assessed for this substance

Table 7.4-4: Summary and color-coding for hazard scores of the hardeners.

Summary of scores	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD
Human health general	0.27	0.82	0.82
Genotoxicity	0.00	0.83	0.00
Endocrine disruption	0.48	0.23	0.00
Ecotoxicity	4.92	5.47	3.94
Human health inhalation	0.00	1.94	2.33
Human health oral	0.24	0.21	0.19
Human health dermal	0.70	1.05	0.69

Table 7.4-5: Summary and color-coding for hazard scores of the A-parts.

Summary of scores	AP-CL	AP1	AP2	AP3	AP4
Human health general	0.65	0.63	0.54	0.61	0.79
Genotoxicity	1.80	2.07	1.65	1.67	1.74
Endocrine disruption	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	2.83	2.89	2.86	2.89	2.88
Human health inhalation	0.29	0.31	0.00	0.72	0.00
Human health oral	1.00	0.95	0.43	0.97	0.98
Human health dermal	1.26	1.15	0.89	0.66	1.00

Table 7.4-6: Summary and color-coding for hazard scores of the leachates.

Summary of scores	Leach-TCPP	Leach-SP1	Leach-SP2	Leach-SP3	Leach-SP4
Human health general	0.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Genotoxicity	0.00	0.35	0.40	0.48	0.42
Endocrine disruption	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	11.43	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Human health inhalation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Human health oral	1.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Human health dermal	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

The strongest effects of the hardeners are on ecotoxicity. The effects on general human health are an average of the inhalation, dermal and oral effects and therefore less pronounced. Noteworthy are also the genotoxic potential of 4-AFD (SSbD#1 route), and possibly also the endocrine disruption potential of MDA (SSbD#0 route) and 4-AFD. The most obvious response of the A-parts is their genotoxic potential and ecotoxicological hazard, although the scores slightly differ between specific A-parts. The leachates have not been tested in all assays, therefore, the zero-scores do not necessarily represent an absence of hazard. The highest score is for the leach-TCPP (SSbD#0 route) on ecotoxicity, which is

related to the several substances detected in leachates, giving high potential hazards in QSAR modelling (D4.4). Similarly to the A-parts, also the leachates induce some genotoxic response.

7.4.2 Differences in Performance (DiP)

The hazard scores of substances are added and a Difference in Performance (DiP) is calculated. For CS2 these are combinations of hardeners and A-parts (Table 7.4-7, Table 7.4-8,

Table 7.4-9). As the leachates are from composites with 4-AFD, the leachate results are only used for products with 4-AFD (

Table 7.4-10). A score of 0 means that the SSRbD alternative is equally hazardous as the reference product, this is also the reason that the reference product scores 0 on all endpoints. A lower score means a higher hazard and a higher score means a lower hazard.

Table 7.4-7: Product scores for products with MDA.

		SSbD#0 excl leachate (reference)	SSbD#1, Araldite LY1564, without leachate, MDA	SSbD#1, Polyphlox 3742, without leachate, MDA	SSbD#1, Exolit EP 360, without leachate, MDA	SSbD#1, Exolit OP 930, without leachate, MDA
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	0.00	-0.03	-0.11	-0.01	-0.15
	Oxidative stress	0.00	0.12	0.36	0.13	-0.09
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Inflammation	0.00	-0.42	-0.70	-0.43	-0.70
	Score	0.00	0.03	0.12	0.04	-0.15
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	53BP1	0.00	-0.15	0.08	0.07	0.03
	Score	0.00	-0.15	0.08	0.07	0.03
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00
	Score	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	0.00	-0.03	0.05	0.01	0.04
	Zebrafish	0.00	-0.01	1.00	-0.07	1.00
	Score	0.00	-0.01	0.00	-0.01	-0.01

Table 7.4-8: Product scores for products with 4-AFD.

		SSbD#0 excl leachate (reference)	SSbD#1 Araldite LY1564, excl leachate	SSbD#1, Polyphlox 3742, excl leachate	SSbD#1 Exolit EP 360, excl leachate	SSbD#1, Exolit OP 930, excl leachate
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	0.00	-1.04	-1.12	-1.02	-1.16
	Oxidative stress	0.00	-0.19	0.05	-0.18	-0.40
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Inflammation	0.00	-2.01	-2.29	-2.02	-2.29
	Score	0.00	-0.56	-0.47	-0.55	-0.74
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	53BP1	0.00	-0.61	-0.38	-0.39	-0.43
	Score	0.00	-0.61	-0.38	-0.39	-0.43
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	0.53	1.00	0.53	1.00
	Score	0.00	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.53
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	0.00	-0.06	0.01	-0.03	0.00
	Zebrafish	0.00	-0.72	1.00	-0.79	1.00
	Score	0.00	-0.08	-0.07	-0.08	-0.08

Table 7.4-9: Product scores for products with 2-AFD.

		SSbD#0 excl leachate (reference)	SSbD#1, Araldite LY1564, excl leachate, 2-AFD	SSbD#1, Polyphlox 3742, excl leachate, 2-AFD	SSbD#1, Exolit EP 360, excl leachate, 2-AFD	SSbD#1, Exolit OP 930, excl leachate, 2-AFD
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	0.00	-0.76	-0.84	-0.74	-0.88
	Oxidative stress	0.00	-0.38	-0.13	-0.37	-0.58
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Inflammation	0.00	-1.84	-2.11	-1.84	-2.11
	Score	0.00	-0.56	-0.47	-0.55	-0.74
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	53BP1	0.00	-0.15	0.08	0.07	0.03
	Score	0.00	-0.15	0.08	0.07	0.03
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Score	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	0.00	-0.09	-0.01	-0.05	-0.02
	Zebrafish	0.00	-0.93	1.00	-0.99	1.00
	Score	0.00	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12

Table 7.4-10: Product scores for products with 4-AFD, including leachates.

		SSbD#0 incl leachate (reference)	SSbD#1 Araldite LY1564, incl leachate	SSbD#1, Polyphlox 3742, incl leachate	SSbD#1 Exolit EP 360, incl leachate	SSbD#1, Exolit OP 930, incl leachate
Human health general	Cytotoxicity	0.00	0.02	-0.01	0.03	-0.03
	Oxidative stress	0.00	-0.19	0.05	-0.18	-0.40
	Epigenetic changes	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Inflammation	0.00	-2.01	-2.29	-2.02	-2.29
	Score	0.00	0.10	0.15	0.10	-0.01
Genotoxicity	Comet	0.00	-0.48	-0.58	-0.49	-0.47
	53BP1	0.00	-0.67	-0.44	-0.52	-0.53
	Score	0.00	-0.80	-0.60	-0.65	-0.66
Endocrine disruption	AR/AR α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ER/ER α	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Thyroid	0.00	0.53	1.00	0.53	1.00
	Score	0.00	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.53
Ecotoxicity	Daphnia	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Zebrafish	0.00	-0.05	0.01	-0.02	0.00
	Score	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

The differences between the products with MDA (SSbD#0 route), 4-AFD and 2-AFD (both SSbD#1 route) mainly show that the hardeners have the largest contribution to the DiP. Potential genotoxicity is mainly found for products with 4-AFD. An important note is that AP2, AP4 and the leachates have not been assessed in all assays, meaning that there are data gaps, resulting in a zero score. The absence of data does, of course, not mean an absence of hazard.

7.5 CS3

The migration samples tested for CS3 did not respond in any of the assays due to the relatively high toxicity of the solvent and the probably low quantities of the migrated chemicals. Hazard assessment, up to concentrations inducing cytotoxicity of the migrated chemicals could therefore not be done. Scoring calculation for CS3 migration samples therefore results in tables with zeros for general human health effects, genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and on ecotoxicity tested with daphnia and zebrafish. However, this does not mean that there is no (potential) hazard.

Scoring for ecotoxicity was based on results of QSAR modelling of IAS and NIAS as described in D4.4. For completeness, the results are included here as well. Table 7.5-1 indicates which substances are relevant for each of the product routes. Table 7.5-2 indicates the DiP based on ecotoxicological hazards.

Table 7.5-1: IAS and NIAS identified for CS3. X indicates the product for which the IAS or NIAS is relevant.

SSbD route	abbreviation	CS3_17 Caprolactam	CS3_18 Undecanoic acid	CS3_21 Oleamide	CS3_22 Erucamide	CS3_19 2,4-di-tert-butylphenol	CS3_23 Irgafos 168	CS3_L10 Irgafos 1076	CS3_L11 Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate
reference	Ref PO/PA/compat 11 layers	x	x	x	x		x	x	x
SSbD#1	PE/compat/PA 65 layers	x					x	x	x
SSbD#1	PE/compat/PA 129 layers	x				x	x	x	x
SSbD#1	PE/PA 129 layers	x				x	x	x	x

Table 7.5-2: Performance score based on ecotoxicological hazard.

Reference: PO/PA/compat 11 layers	PE/compat/PA 65 layers	PE/compat/PA 129 layers	PE/PA 129 layers
0.00	0.76	0.40	0.40

8 Deviations from the workplan

No deviations from the workplan occurred.

9 Conclusions and perspectives

Our hazard assessment approach, giving information on potential hazard using *in vitro* assays, has shown to give valuable information on potential hazard of the ingredients of an SSbD product. Results can be used for considering replacement of an ingredient early in the production process. However, interpretation of the results should be done with caution.

- Many *in vitro* assays used, are not validated nor regulatory compliant (CALUX assays and Daphnia and Zebrafish test are exceptions). Although well conducted, the validity of the results for the specific substances has not been evaluated. Potential hazards may have been missed and assays may give a response that is not representative for *in vivo* effect. The results of all assays conducted should therefore be considered indicative for possible further testing.
- A nice feedback process was observed in the project: the results of the initial toxicological tests on the 4-AFD hardener were presented to the CS2 team, which reacted by proposing a second alternative product. This is the essence of a SSRbD project, where improvement loops and hazard assessment in parallel to the product development process are essential. The timetable did not allow us to work in this way with the other CSs: the list of ingredients for testing was completed too late to allow any further testing based on the results.
- ECHA data and other relevant product information is put forward by the project - and other SSbD European projects. However, it quickly becomes apparent that for alternative ingredients, which are recently developed and do not reach large production volumes, most of the time data is missing

or not available. Making decisions based on these data is therefore in many cases impossible. Nevertheless, the available data should be included in the evaluation.

- Scoring is not a fixed, rigid methodology, it only gives a quick overview of potential hazards. Evaluation of the results, by an expert, remains therefore essential. A scoring method should always allow to go back to the data and the actual results, for better interpretation
- The development of a method for scoring should be done early in the process, to be able to design experiments as effectively as possible, like the use of positive controls and consistency of testing. On the other hand, developing a scoring method without knowing the outcomes of the assays is also challenging. Therefore, this is a process that should go hand in hand, and allowing future efforts to build further on existing scoring methods.
- The accuracy of the scoring depends on the results obtained, and the more reliable and accurate these results, the more useful they will be. Increasing the number of replicates could help to reduce the variation. Also, as a relatively high number of substances were tested, we choose a pragmatic approach of testing one or two concentrations for each substance. Testing of more concentrations, to obtain a dose-response curve for all parameters, would increase confidence in the outcomes.
- The product score provides information on the evaluation of the alternative product compared to the reference substance. However, it is important to keep track of the original toxicity data. Indeed, a product hazard score must be interpreted with a critical eye. Possibly, the results could be used to guide further hazard testing.

10 References

Caldeira, C., Farcas, L. R., Garmendia Aguirre, I., Mancini, L., Tosches, D. et al., Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials – Framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/487955>

OECD (2004), *Test No. 202: Daphnia sp. Acute Immobilisation Test*, OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 2, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264069947-en>.

OECD (2013), *Test No. 236: Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity (FET) Test*, OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 2, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264203709-en>.

OECD (2022), Sustainability and Safe and Sustainable by Design: Working Descriptions for the Safer Innovation Approach. ENV/CBC/MONO(2022)30. Series on the Safety of Manufactured Nanomaterials, No. 105

OECD (2023), *Test No. 456: H295R Steroidogenesis Assay*, OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 4, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264122642-en>.

Hermesen SA, van den Brandhof EJ, van der Ven LT, Piersma AH. Relative embryotoxicity of two classes of chemicals in a modified zebrafish embryotoxicity test and comparison with their in vivo potencies. *Toxicol In Vitro*. 2011 Apr;25(3):745-53. doi: 10.1016/j.tiv.2011.01.005. Epub 2011 Jan 14. PMID: 21238576.

Slob W. Dose-response modeling of continuous endpoints. *Toxicol Sci*. 2002 Apr;66(2):298-312. doi: 10.1093/toxsci/66.2.298. PMID: 11896297.

Staal, Y.C.M., Meijer, J., van der Kris, R.J.C. *et al*. Head skeleton malformations in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) to assess adverse effects of mixtures of compounds. *Arch Toxicol* **92**, 3549–3564 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-018-2320-y>

11 Appendices

1. Introduction.....	15
1.1 Background.....	15
1.2 Sources of hazard data.....	16
1.2.1 ECHA database.....	17
1.2.2 QSAR modelling.....	17
1.2.3 <i>In vitro</i> testing.....	17
1.3 Selection of substances and concentrations.....	18
1.3.1 General approach.....	18
1.3.2 Case study specific choices in testing of substances.....	18
2 Selected models.....	20
2.1 Models representing exposure routes.....	20
2.2 Models for fresh water toxicity and endocrine disruption.....	22
3 Selected <i>in vitro</i> assays.....	22
3.1 Cytotoxicity assessment.....	24
3.1.1 WST-1 assay.....	24
3.1.2 LDH assay.....	24
3.1.3 Alamar Blue assay.....	26
3.2 Oxidative stress assessment.....	27
3.2.1 CM-H ₂ DCFDA assay.....	27

3.2.2	Cellular ROS Assay kit	28
3.2.3	Protein carbonylation	29
3.3	Epigenetics	30
3.3.1	Quantification of methylated cytosine in total DNA using HPLC-MS	30
3.4	Inflammation	31
3.4.1	Cytokine assessment of inhalation model	31
3.4.2	Cytokine assessment of dermal and oral model	32
3.5	Genotoxicity	32
3.5.1	53BP1 assay for double strand break assessment	32
3.5.2	Comet assay for DNA damage assessment	34
3.6	Endocrine disruption	36
3.6.1	ER α and AR assessment	36
3.6.2	Transgenic zebrafish line for thyroid disruption	38
3.6.3	H295R Steroidogenesis assay	38
3.7	Aquatic toxicity	39
3.7.1	<i>Daphnia Magna</i>	39
3.7.2	Zebrafish Embryo Toxicity (ZFET)	40
3.8	Statistical analysis	41
4	Results CS1	43
4.1	CS1 SSbD routes and tested substances	43
4.2	CS1 Polyols	44
4.2.1	ECHA data	44
4.2.2	General human health	47
4.2.3	Genotoxicity	56
4.2.4	Endocrine disruption	58
4.2.5	Aquatic toxicity	60
4.2.6	Short summary	62

4.3	CS1 Catalysts	62
4.3.1	ECHA data	62
4.3.2	General human health.....	64
4.3.3	Genotoxicity.....	72
4.3.4	Endocrine disruption	73
4.3.5	Aquatic toxicity	75
4.3.6	Short summary	76
4.4	CS1 Disulfide.....	77
4.4.1	ECHA data	77
4.4.2	General human health.....	80
4.4.3	Genotoxicity.....	86
4.4.4	Endocrine disruption	87
4.4.5	Aquatic toxicity	89
4.4.6	Short summary	90
5	Results CS2	90
5.1	CS2 SSbD routes and tested substances	90
5.2	CS2 Hardeners	92
5.2.1	ECHA data	93
5.2.2	General human health.....	94
5.2.3	Genotoxicity.....	103
5.2.4	Endocrine disruption	104
5.2.5	Aquatic toxicity	107
5.2.6	Short summary	109
5.3	CS2 A-Parts	109
5.3.1	ECHA data	110
5.3.2	General human health.....	113
5.3.3	Genotoxicity.....	120

5.3.4	Endocrine disruption	121
5.3.5	Aquatic toxicity	122
5.3.6	Short summary	124
5.4	CS2 Leachates from composites.....	124
5.4.1	ECHA data	124
5.4.2	General human health.....	124
5.4.3	Genotoxicity.....	127
5.4.4	Endocrine disruption	128
5.4.5	Aquatic toxicity	131
5.4.6	Short summary	132
6	Results CS3	132
6.1	CS3 SSbD routes	132
6.2	CS3 Migration samples.....	132
6.2.1	ECHA data	133
6.2.2	General human health.....	135
6.2.3	Genotoxicity.....	142
6.2.4	Endocrine disruption	144
6.2.5	Aquatic toxicity	145
6.2.6	Short summary	146
7	Hazard scoring.....	146
7.1	Purpose and strategy	146
7.2	Hazard scoring steps	147
7.2.1	Data for hazard scoring	147
7.2.2	Setting a response for a no effect level and a low effect level.....	148
7.2.3	Evaluation of statistical significance.....	150
7.2.4	Normalization of the data	150
7.2.5	Calculation of absolute differences.....	151

7.2.6	Averaging of assay outcomes measuring the same health hazard	152
7.2.7	Thresholds for substance hazard.....	152
7.2.8	Combining ingredient scores into a performance score and their thresholds.....	153
7.2.9	Scoring considerations.....	153
7.3	CS1.....	154
7.3.1	Hazard scores.....	154
7.3.2	Differences in Performance (DiP)	157
7.4	CS2.....	159
7.4.1	Hazard scores.....	159
7.4.2	Differences in Performance (DiP)	164
7.5	CS3.....	167
8	Deviations from the workplan.....	168
9	Conclusions and perspectives	168
10	References.....	169
11	Appendices	170
11.1	CS1 – Polyols	175
11.1.1	General human health	175
11.1.2	Genotoxicity	178
11.1.3	Endocrine disruption	180
11.2	CS1 – Catalysts	180
11.2.1	General human health	180
11.2.2	Genotoxicity	183
11.2.3	Endocrine disruption	184
11.3	CS1 – Disulfide (2-hydroxyethyl disulfide)	184
11.3.1	General human health	184
11.3.2	Genotoxicity	185
11.3.3	Endocrine disruption	186
11.4	CS2 - Hardeners.....	186

11.4.1	General human health	186
11.4.2	Genotoxicity	189
11.4.3	Endocrine disruption	190
11.5	CS2 – A-Parts	191
11.5.1	General human health	191
11.5.2	Genotoxicity	193
11.5.3	Endocrine disruption	194
11.6	CS2 – Leachates from composites	194
11.6.1	General human health	194
11.6.2	Genotoxicity	196
11.6.3	Endocrine disruption	197
11.7	CS3 – Migration samples	197
11.7.1	General human health	197
11.7.2	Genotoxicity	200
11.7.3	Endocrine disruption	202

11.1 CS1 – Polyols

11.1.1 General human health

11.1.1.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

Polyol A

Concentration (µg/mL)	0	17	28	47	78	130	216	360	600
Median	99,6	106,6	115,3	119,5	130,2	144,1	166,0	75,8	10,5
Interquartile range	7,9	16,6	24,3	25,9	26,1	27,6	72,6	95,0	19,1

Polyol C

Concentration (µg/mL)	0	7	12	19	32	54	90	150	250
Median	99,5	134,7	151,1	135,8	7,8	5,9	3,5	3,7	5,1
Interquartile range	11,2	45,8	55,9	92,1	7,6	7,5	14,2	8,0	5,4

Polyol B, D, I

	Concentration (µg/mL)	0	56	93	156	259	432	720	1200	2000
B	Median	99,6	99,2	102,9	99,7	105,8	111,6	115,1	119,0	98,5
	Interquartile range	6,8	14,0	12,3	16,4	8,5	16,3	70,5	100,0	99,5
D	Median	99,5	94,3	96,6	94,0	93,4	107,6	117,3	108,9	89,1
	Interquartile range	11,2	7,5	3,9	5,7	5,4	21,9	36,8	55,7	70,7
I	Median	99,8	127,3	120,4	118,5	119,3	121,1	119,8	124,3	102,9
	Interquartile range	10,2	39,4	23,0	38,3	34,5	33,0	32,6	57,5	58,8

On Caco-2 cells

Polyol A

Concentration (µg/mL)	0	25	42	70	117	194	324	540	900
Median	101,6	102,0	105,0	101,6	97,6	91,1	60,7	14,0	9,7
Interquartile range	9,0	14,6	13,3	24,2	20,7	20,8	23,2	26,9	31,6

Polyol C

Concentration (µg/mL)	0	8	14	23	39	65	108	180	300
Median	101,0	67,9	62,0	51,4	2,4	1,8	1,7	1,6	1,1
Interquartile range	6,6	8,1	10,9	6,4	14,0	1,0	1,5	2,1	1,8

Polyol B, D, I

	Concentration (µg/mL)	0	56	93	156	259	432	720	1200	2000
B	Median	101,6	94,3	96,4	97,3	91,7	82,0	79,4	73,7	58,7
	Interquartile range	9,0	6,1	8,3	16,1	16,3	17,4	13,9	16,1	15,3
D	Median	101,0	91,8	97,0	93,7	98,3	86,1	83,5	69,5	52,6
	Interquartile range	6,6	8,8	9,5	7,3	9,0	10,2	18,4	19,0	22,9
I	Median	100,3	101,7	94,1	89,1	91,7	94,5	90,5	72,5	35,4
	Interquartile range	13,2	5,5	17,5	14,9	9,9	11,4	11,6	16,0	12,1

LDH Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

Polyol A

Concentration (µg/mL)	0	17	28	47	78	130	216	360	600
Median	100,0	99,4	99,9	99,8	102,5	101,6	99,7	40,2	0,6
Interquartile range	2,5	4,6	5,4	4,1	8,1	3,2	7,3	57,0	23,9

Polyol C

Concentration (µg/mL)	0	7	12	19	32	54	90	150	250
Median	99,6	99,5	95,4	88,5	-8,0	-4,1	-3,9	2,0	0,5
Interquartile range	4,7	9,1	14,5	31,2	9,0	12,8	8,0	9,3	10,3

Polyol B, D, I

	Concentration (µg/mL)	0	56	93	156	259	432	720	1200	2000
B	Median	100,2	96,7	94,2	93,3	95,2	99,5	98,1	99,4	91,1
	Interquartile range	2,2	10,1	5,7	7,2	13,9	4,7	6,0	5,8	7,0
D	Median	99,6	97,2	97,2	95,7	95,3	99,1	100,1	97,6	90,5
	Interquartile range	4,7	3,3	6,0	8,0	4,0	5,8	10,7	11,1	14,4
I	Median	99,8	101,0	102,0	102,3	103,8	102,4	99,1	89,0	63,8
	Interquartile range	3,2	3,4	4,6	7,6	7,5	7,3	2,2	14,7	15,1

On Caco-2 cells

Polyol A

Concentration (µg/mL)	0	25	42	70	117	194	324	540	900
Median	99,9	105,8	106,3	109,1	104,3	89,7	88,8	40,1	45,4
Interquartile range	6,1	12,5	12,6	22,1	20,4	7,5	11,9	85,7	56,4

Polyol C

Concentration (µg/mL)	0	8	14	23	39	65	108	180	300
Median	99,8	95,4	93,5	82,3	-5,7	-9,5	-16,5	-15,8	-12,1
Interquartile range	2,8	13,6	5,8	17,9	25,8	55,6	50,8	27,4	36,8

Polyol B, D, I

	Concentration (µg/mL)	0	56	93	156	259	432	720	1200	2000
B	Median	99,9	109,2	106,0	106,7	107,1	97,5	97,2	92,9	93,7
	Interquartile range	6,1	7,9	8,0	25,8	24,7	18,5	8,9	8,1	16,1
D	Median	99,8	96,5	94,6	95,2	95,5	92,6	93,6	90,2	91,9
	Interquartile range	2,8	8,7	9,6	7,6	5,1	6,8	5,3	10,5	8,3
I	Median	100,4	100,3	97,2	104,6	100,8	97,3	97,5	102,1	89,1
	Interquartile range	5,1	9,5	14,3	13,9	7,9	27,8	24,3	9,8	14,3

11.1.1.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay – results in % of viability compared to the delta (positive control - solvent control)

On HaCaT cells

	Solvent control	Neg. Ctrl	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D	Polyol I	Pos. Ctrl
Concentration (µg/mL)	-	-	200	1000	5	1000	1000	-
Median	2,2	19,8	83,5	6,6	10,4	-0,8	15,9	105,0
Interquartile range	32,3	41,0	47,3	14,4	31,2	15,7	16,7	23,5

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent control	Neg. Ctrl	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D	Polyol I	Pos. Ctrl
Concentration (µg/mL)	-	-	300	1000	25	1000	1000	-
Median	-4,8	9,4	41,0	-11,8	2,5	-22,0	25,9	91,4
Interquartile range	42,4	34,0	24,7	31,0	44,8	45,9	90,2	76,2

11.1.1.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS – results in % of cytosine methylation

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent Ctrl for Ctrl+	Positive control	Solvent control	Polyol A	Polyol B	Polyol C	Polyol D	Polyol I
Concentration (µg/mL)	-	-	-	100	1000	15	1000	1000
Median	4,065	2,035	4,29	4,12	4,09	4,11	4,14	4,39
Interquartile range	0,4	0,3	0,4	0,3	0,1	0,9	0,2	0,5

11.1.2 Genotoxicity

53BP1 assay

On HaCaT cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,18	0,21	100,3	1,8
Negative control	1,26	0,35	113,5	23,6
Etoposide, 25 µM	20,95	7,26	40,7	15,0
Etoposide, 50 µM	19,60	6,09	35,0	9,9
Etoposide, 100 µM	21,45	8,00	30,1	7,4
Polyol A, 15µg/mL	1,14	0,22	115,8	11,8
Polyol A, 200µg/mL	1,15	0,30	88,9	16,6
Polyol B, 15µg/mL	1,14	0,14	111,3	10,5
Polyol B, 1000µg/mL	1,39	0,62	107,7	5,9
Polyol C, 15µg/mL	1,12	0,10	103,3	12,2

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Polyol C, 20µg/mL	0,61	0,43	58,1	48,6
Polyol D, 15µg/mL	1,21	0,04	97,0	4,8
Polyol D, 1000µg/mL	1,42	0,24	104,6	3,8
Polyol I, 15µg/mL	1,06	0,16	116,5	9,9
Polyol I, 1000µg/mL	1,04	0,28	72,7	6,6

On Caco-2 cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	3,59	0,74	100,8	6,9
Negative control	3,05	1,03	94,4	19,6
Etoposide, 6,5 µM	22,76	7,77	56,3	16,4
Etoposide, 12,5 µM	31,45	12,72	52,9	19,3
Etoposide, 25 µM	35,28	9,12	55,2	16,6
Polyol A, 15µg/mL	3,34	0,53	100,2	60,4
Polyol A, 150µg/mL	3,86	0,56	42,0	27,9
Polyol B, 15µg/mL	3,61	0,41	100,7	35,5
Polyol B, 1000µg/mL	3,07	0,40	93,5	3,5
Polyol C, 15µg/mL	3,52	0,41	102,0	32,8
Polyol C, 20µg/mL	3,10	1,03	52,8	32,9
Polyol D, 15µg/mL	3,66	0,24	96,2	11,9
Polyol D, 1000µg/mL	3,25	0,29	94,8	6,3
Polyol I, 15µg/mL	3,24	0,64	114,7	61,5
Polyol I, 1000µg/mL	3,08	0,28	63,9	7,7

Comet assay – results in % of tail intensity

On HaCaT cells

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,46	0,83
Negative control	1,34	1,50
H ₂ O ₂ control	50,40	12,49
MMS 2,2 µg/mL	21,45	6,74
MMS 3,3 µg/mL	30,39	11,92
Polyol A, 15µg/mL	1,59	0,84
Polyol A, 200µg/mL	1,75	2,60
Polyol B, 15µg/mL	0,94	0,87
Polyol B, 1000µg/mL	1,38	1,79
Polyol C, 15µg/mL	1,25	1,28
Polyol C, 30µg/mL	1,67	2,02
Polyol D, 15µg/mL	1,36	2,37
Polyol D, 1000µg/mL	1,19	1,02

On Caco-2 cells

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,20	1,93
Negative control	1,33	1,66
H ₂ O ₂ control	42,41	19,82
MMS 2,2 µg/mL	22,23	3,10
MMS 3,3 µg/mL	29,82	11,71
Polyol A, 15µg/mL	1,56	2,57
Polyol A, 300µg/mL	0,59	0,44
Polyol B, 15µg/mL	1,86	1,73
Polyol B, 1000µg/mL	0,55	1,04
Polyol C, 15µg/mL	1,78	1,31
Polyol C, 30µg/mL	0,91	0,93
Polyol D, 15µg/mL	2,26	1,28
Polyol D, 1000µg/mL	0,69	0,85

	Median	Interquartile range
Polyol I, 15µg/mL	1,32	1,37
Polyol I, 1000µg/mL	1,90	1,40

	Median	Interquartile range
Polyol I, 15µg/mL	1,21	1,94
Polyol I, 1000µg/mL	0,73	1,32

11.1.3 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

On U2OS CALUX[®] cells

	Disruption potential on ER α		Disruption potential on AR	
	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)
Reference control	1.42E-06 µg/mL	1.33E-01 µg/mL	9.09E-05 µg/mL	1.62E-01 µg/mL
Polyol A	> 5E+01 µg/mL	> 2E+02 µg/mL	> 5E+01 µg/mL	> 2E+02 µg/mL
Polyols C, B, D, I	> 5E+01 µg/mL	> 5E+01 µg/mL	> 5E+01 µg/mL	> 5E+01 µg/mL

Thyroid assay

11.2 CS1 – Catalysts

11.2.1 General human health

11.2.1.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

Bi-Cat, reference catalyst

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (µM)	0	28	47	78	130	216	360	600	1000
Median	101,6	93,7	107,7	120,2	137,4	191,8	16,8	19,6	6,1
Interquartile range	9,3	17,8	11,0	9,0	22,1	22,6	132,5	23,8	5,6

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (µM)	0	42	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500
Median	100,2	105,2	111,8	114,1	113,3	98,1	57,6	1,5	3,6
Interquartile range	8,0	4,1	7,2	7,6	24,0	7,9	77,3	2,2	37,2

Cystamine, alternative catalyst

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (µM)	0	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500	2500
Median	98,7	110,6	109,7	113,4	126,4	150,4	177,4	160,9	10,3
Interquartile range	9,0	32,9	48,1	22,3	9,3	23,9	16,4	122,6	128,7

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (μM)	0	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500	2500
Median	99,7	114,1	120,4	127,3	117,4	128,6	114,7	99,6	39,0
Interquartile range	14,5	9,5	16,9	17,2	19,8	20,9	23,8	36,3	38,0

THEED, alternative catalyst

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (μM)	0	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500	2500
Median	98,7	104,5	101,9	104,5	116,2	115,8	128,4	148,7	148,9
Interquartile range	9,0	8,7	7,7	29,2	3,9	12,9	12,6	62,1	90,7

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (μM)	0	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500	2500
Median	99,7	101,0	102,2	105,1	102,9	100,0	109,8	77,7	63,1
Interquartile range	14,5	5,0	5,8	7,2	9,6	4,1	26,8	12,6	17,7

LDH Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

Bi-Cat, reference catalyst

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (μM)	0	28	47	78	130	216	360	600	1000
Median	99,8	103,4	101,9	102,8	102,9	92,7	28,3	2,3	-6,6
Interquartile range	3,4	6,2	2,5	2,5	3,4	6,6	82,5	33,9	46,9

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (μM)	0	42	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500
Median	100,0	101,7	97,3	97,9	88,6	87,0	53,8	-10,3	38,4
Interquartile range	3,9	9,8	7,2	6,2	12,0	7,1	80,7	12,7	80,6

Cystamine, alternative catalyst

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (μM)	0	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500	2500
Median	100,0	97,4	96,0	97,8	95,3	94,4	91,4	47,9	30,6
Interquartile range	2,6	7,0	8,9	10,4	14,5	12,0	14,9	33,2	29,9

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (μM)	0	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500	2500
---------------------------------	---	----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	------	------

Median	99,1	97,0	99,7	96,9	91,7	88,0	89,5	81,9	77,2
Interquartile range	6,6	7,0	7,7	4,2	7,0	6,2	4,7	6,6	6,3

THEED, alternative catalyst

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (µM)	0	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500	2500
Median	100,0	98,9	94,6	95,2	97,2	98,6	99,8	100,2	95,9
Interquartile range	2,6	3,3	5,2	14,9	12,6	10,8	9,6	9,2	7,7

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (µM)	0	70	117	194	324	540	900	1500	2500
Median	99,1	101,0	102,7	101,3	100,8	101,2	89,8	96,0	93,7
Interquartile range	6,6	5,0	6,4	11,7	7,1	7,0	13,5	11,7	12,4

11.2.1.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay – results in % of viability compared to the delta (positive control - solvent control)

On HaCaT cells

	Solvent control	Negative control	Cystamine, 1500µM	THEED, 1500µM	Bi-Cat, 250µM	Positive control
Median	-0,39	7,48	7,28	-6,93	59,87	98,22
Interquartile range	13,76	19,75	20,03	20,38	42,08	21,51

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent control	Negative control	Cystamine, 1500µM	THEED, 1500µM	Bi-Cat, 400µM	Positive control
Median	-4,25	16,16	22,18	27,91	82,72	98,12
Interquartile range	95,00	39,63	112,15	61,67	110,38	22,89

11.2.1.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS – results in % of cytosine methylation

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent Ctrl for Ctrl+	Positive control	Solvent control	Cystamine 1000µM	THEED 1000µM	Bi-Cat 100µM
Median	4,17	2,05	3,98	4,21	4,08	4,05
Interquartile range	0,3	0,3	0,5	0,3	0,4	0,4

11.2.2 Genotoxicity

53BP1 assay – results in number of foci per cell

On HaCaT cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,25	0,11	99,9	4,3
Negative control	1,37	0,14	117,7	24,3
Etoposide 25 µM	23,20	6,31	36,7	9,9
Etoposide 50 µM	18,62	6,49	33,4	8,4
Etoposide 100 µM	20,80	6,39	28,2	8,1
CT1, 1000 µM	2,77	0,69	79,5	17,0
CT2, 1000µM	1,34	0,40	108,9	19,5
CT3, 100µM	1,42	0,13	94,2	12,5

On Caco-2 cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	2,06	0,37	100,6	3,6
Negative control	2,09	1,66	97,6	11,7
Etoposide 6,25 µM	16,28	5,90	59,6	14,2
Etoposide 12,5 µM	18,31	10,36	58,7	8,1
Etoposide 25 µM	16,02	12,96	60,9	7,7
CT1, 1000 µM	1,97	2,10	53,6	8,3
CT2, 1000µM	1,61	0,31	95,3	23,7
CT3, 100µM	1,58	0,54	86,6	12,2

Comet assay – results in % of tail intensity

On HaCaT cells

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,34	1,08
Negative control	1,09	1,11
H ₂ O ₂ control	48,21	7,71
MMS 20 µM	21,27	10,05
MMS 30 µM	42,17	10,56
Cystamine, 1000µM	0,62	0,90
THEED, 1000 µM	1,25	0,88
Bi-Cat, 200µM	0,94	0,71

On Caco-2 cells

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,63	1,74
Negative control	1,62	0,98
H ₂ O ₂ control	39,17	6,98
MMS 20 µM	24,86	23,92
MMS 30 µM	35,27	28,46
Cystamine, 1000µM	0,84	0,52
THEED, 1000 µM	0,67	1,69
Bi-Cat, 100µM	2,54	1,99

11.2.3 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

On U2OS CALUX[®] cells

	Disruption potential on ER α		Disruption potential on AR	
	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)
Reference control	5.77E-12 M	1.18E-08 M	2.58E-10 M	5.87E-05 M
Bi-cat	> 1E-04 M	7.69E-05 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-03 M
Cystamine	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M
THEED	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M

Thyroid assay

11.3 CS1 – Disulfide (2-hydroxyethyl disulfide)

11.3.1 General human health

11.3.1.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (μ M)	0	210	350	583	972	1620	2700	4500	7500
Median	100,2	143,5	249,0	492,9	604,9	533,2	373,2	350,8	163,7
Interquartile range	9,5	32,6	29,8	120,7	164,3	144,8	278,4	179,4	92,3

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (μ M)	0	210	350	583	972	1620	2700	4500	7500
Median	101,0	129,8	134,8	172,7	181,0	173,8	151,8	138,8	78,8
Interquartile range	8,1	32,2	18,2	50,6	53,4	47,4	32,2	22,7	9,1

LDH Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (μ M)	0	210	350	583	972	1620	2700	4500	7500
Median	99,8	88,7	75,1	58,2	31,6	-16,5	-29,2	-32,2	-31,0
Interquartile range	6,0	6,2	9,0	7,1	9,1	27,9	30,9	35,1	35,5

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (μ M)	0	210	350	583	972	1620	2700	4500	7500
Median	100,1	77,9	44,0	5,4	-21,1	-39,0	-87,6	-89,0	-99,5
Interquartile range	2,7	6,2	14,3	18,8	14,3	23,2	21,6	7,5	3,1

11.3.1.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay – results in % of viability compared to the delta (positive control - solvent control)

On HaCaT cells

	Solvent control	Negative control	Disulfide, 1mM	Positive control
Median	-0,4	7,5	3,2	98,2
Interquartile range	13,8	19,8	59,8	21,5

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent control	Negative control	Disulfide, 1mM	Positive control
Median	-4,3	16,2	-26,1	98,1
Interquartile range	95,0	39,6	114,3	22,9

11.3.1.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS – results in % of cytosine methylation

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent Ctrl for Ctrl+	Positive control	Solvent control	Disulfide, 1mM
Median	4,17	2,05	3,98	3,89
Interquartile range	0,3	0,3	0,5	0,4

11.3.2 Genotoxicity

53BP1 assay – results in number of foci per cell

On HaCaT cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,25	0,11	99,9	4,3
Negative control	1,37	0,14	117,7	24,3
Etoposide 25 µM	23,20	6,31	36,7	9,9
Etoposide 50 µM	18,62	6,49	33,4	8,4
Etoposide 100 µM	20,80	6,39	28,2	8,1
Disulfide 1000 µM	1,74	0,75	75,7	23,4

On Caco-2 cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	2,18	1,46	100,6	3,4
Negative control	2,09	1,66	95,6	17,0

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Etoposide 6,25 µM	16,28	5,90	58,3	11,0
Etoposide 12,5 µM	17,97	11,42	58,0	6,5
Etoposide 25 µM	15,67	15,02	60,2	5,0
Disulfide 1000 µM	1,01	1,02	71,4	19,0

Comet assay – results in % of tail intensity

On HaCaT cells

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,34	1,08
Negative control	1,09	1,11
H ₂ O ₂ control	48,21	7,71
MMS 20 µM	21,27	10,05
MMS 30 µM	42,17	10,56
Disulfide 1000 µM	1,26	1,19

On Caco-2 cells

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,63	1,74
Negative control	1,62	0,98
H ₂ O ₂ control	39,17	6,98
MMS 20 µM	24,86	23,92
MMS 30 µM	35,27	28,46
Disulfide 1000 µM	1,12	1,14

11.3.3 Endocrine disruption

Thyroid assay

11.4 CS2 - Hardeners

11.4.1 General human health

11.4.1.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

MDA, reference Hardener

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (µM)	0	233	389	648	1080	1800	3000	5000
Median	99,1	99,8	94,6	78,4	72,6	72,7	54,3	8,2
Interquartile range	25,4	33,9	22,6	26,0	22,5	19,5	10,0	2,4

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (µM)	0	233	389	648	1080	1800	3000	5000
Median	99,0	93,0	98,5	97,8	90,1	66,5	38,2	5,6
Interquartile range	6,0	28,8	37,0	34,8	37,5	37,0	27,8	4,9

4-AFD, reference Hardener

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (µM)	0	26	40	59	89	133	200	300
Median	100,4	242,8	305,4	291,9	87,2	6,4	6,8	2,2
Interquartile range	17,6	83,6	126,9	104,7	89,4	4,5	10,1	3,0

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (µM)	0	26	40	59	89	133	200	300
Median	99,8	112,7	119,6	122,4	106,0	53,6	8,2	1,4
Interquartile range	5,6	21,3	26,5	29,3	23,7	13,8	11,5	2,6

2-AFD, reference Hardener

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (µM)	0	26	40	59	89	133	200	300
Median	101,1	370,7	440,4	464,8	446,8	278,8	71,3	6,9
Interquartile range	10,6	186,4	200,1	245,2	194,1	116,3	83,8	2,6

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (µM)	0	26	40	59	89	133	200	300
Median	99,8	110,0	112,1	114,0	116,3	107,8	6,5	1,6
Interquartile range	6,2	3,1	2,2	3,3	18,1	21,3	2,4	1,3

LDH Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

MDA, reference Hardener

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (µM)	0	233	389	648	1080	1800	3000	5000
Median	104,7	115,5	115,9	115,5	111,1	100,5	79,1	48,2
Interquartile range	13,1	13,1	13,6	12,3	10,9	7,5	15,1	14,7

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (µM)	0	26	40	59	89	133	200	300
Median	100,1	100,8	99,4	94,1	97,9	96,2	75,7	114,5
Interquartile range	3,0	2,9	6,1	9,9	6,2	6,4	22,0	28,4

4-AFD, reference Hardener

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (µM)	0	26	40	59	89	133	200	300
Median	100,8	108,1	109,5	98,4	84,7	65,5	59,2	103,8
Interquartile range	6,0	8,2	11,7	19,8	30,1	21,8	12,6	7,3

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (µM)	0	233	389	648	1080	1800	3000	5000
Median	100,9	97,2	99,4	97,7	99,7	101,2	99,7	76,5
Interquartile range	3,2	6,4	13,2	8,1	10,0	10,8	11,0	18,4

2-AFD, reference Hardener

On HaCaT cells

Concentration (µM)	0	26	40	59	89	133	200	300
Median	99,7	103,7	103,2	101,6	94,8	69,4	21,9	124,8
Interquartile range	1,8	4,8	3,7	7,5	13,3	16,7	12,7	10,4

On Caco-2 cells

Concentration (µM)	0	26	40	59	89	133	200	300
Median	99,9	105,9	104,4	105,1	100,0	90,9	104,7	151,7
Interquartile range	2,5	2,9	5,3	4,6	5,1	2,3	55,6	15,1

11.4.1.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay – results in % of viability compared to the delta (positive control - solvent control)

4-AFD and MDA assessment

On HaCaT cells

	Solvent control	Negative control	4-AFD 50µM	4-AFD 80µM	MDA 50µM	MDA 500µM	Positive control
Median	0,4	0,4	7,6	13,6	6,4	32,5	100,3
Interquartile range	5,5	15,7	13,0	4,8	8,0	16,1	16,4

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent control	Negative control	4-AFD 60µM	4-AFD 115µM	MDA 60µM	MDA 1500µM	Positive control
Median	0,7	-2,6	6,4	-0,5	5,7	74,0	93,1
Interquartile range	4,3	17,6	9,8	17,4	7,6	25,4	25,8

2-AFD and MDA assessment

On HaCaT cells

	Solvent control	Negative control	2-AFD 50µM	2-AFD 200µM	MDA 50µM	MDA 500µM	Positive control
Median	7,8	1,0	7,3	47,8	26,5	74,8	105,5
Interquartile range	38,7	44,0	26,7	48,6	39,9	52,8	38,7

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent control	Negative control	2-AFD 60µM	2-AFD 150µM	MDA 60µM	MDA 1500µM	Positive control
Median	-4,8	-9,4	7,1	16,3	25,3	63,7	103,4
Interquartile range	66,6	31,9	84,6	43,7	58,8	70,8	52,7

11.4.1.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS – results in % of cytosine methylation

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent Ctrl for Ctrl+	Positive control	Solvent control	4-AFD 30 µM	4-AFD 60 µM	MDA 30 µM	MDA 750 µM	2-AFD 30 µM	2-AFD 60 µM
Median	3,88	1,96	3,92	3,93	4,01	3,97	3,93	4,01	4,06
Interquartile range	0,6	0,3	0,5	0,7	1,1	1,0	0,9	1,6	1,6

11.4.2 Genotoxicity

53BP1 assay – results in number of foci per cell

On HaCaT cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,11	0,38	100,1	2,3
Negative control	1,15	0,68	100,0	20,5
Etoposide, 25 µM	16,95	10,91	43,4	5,0
Etoposide, 50 µM	17,20	10,16	39,3	3,8
Etoposide, 100 µM	18,75	7,81	32,1	5,4
4-AFD, 30 µM	1,61	0,37	76,1	51,3
4-AFD, 60 µM	6,87	3,08	46,3	13,1
MDA, 30 µM	1,52	0,60	102,3	16,3
MDA, 500 µM	1,56	0,52	92,8	5,2
2-AFD, 30 µM	1,11	0,71	90,4	25,3
2-AFD, 60 µM	1,27	1,94	82,8	15,3

On Caco-2 cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	3,49	0,66	101,4	4,8
Negative control	2,16	1,16	93,5	23,3
Etoposide, 6.25 µM	14,74	8,84	72,7	21,8
Etoposide, 12.5 µM	20,80	12,85	73,1	12,0
Etoposide, 25 µM	20,76	19,66	72,2	9,8
4-AFD, 30 µM	2,25	0,94	82,8	71,4

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
4-AFD, 60 µM	2,17	0,66	77,7	39,2
MDA, 30 µM	2,93	0,77	97,4	25,0
MDA, 750 µM	3,22	0,77	86,0	7,2
2-AFD, 30 µM	3,38	0,31	102,7	87,7
2-AFD, 60 µM	3,29	0,35	112,5	77,4

Comet assay – results in % of tail intensity

On HaCaT cells

On Caco-2 cells

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,46	1,41
Negative control	1,73	2,77
H ₂ O ₂ control	47,86	14,56
MMS 20 µM	19,37	6,36
MMS 30 µM	28,97	13,76
4-AFD, 30µM	0,78	1,71
4-AFD, 60µM	1,01	1,68
MDA, 30µM	1,09	1,13
MDA, 500µM	0,99	0,75
2-AFD, 30µM	1,02	1,30
2-AFD, 60µM	0,62	0,47

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	0,90	0,69
Negative control	1,04	1,14
H ₂ O ₂ control	37,30	19,53
MMS 20 µM	21,30	3,38
MMS 30 µM	27,35	5,45
4-AFD, 30µM	0,75	1,10
4-AFD, 60µM	1,04	1,83
MDA, 30µM	0,81	1,20
MDA, 750µM	0,90	1,10
2-AFD, 30µM	0,62	0,58
2-AFD, 60µM	1,26	1,27

11.4.3 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

On U2OS CALUX[®] cells

	Disruption potential on ER α		Disruption potential on AR	
	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)
Reference control	6.57E-12 M	1.35E-08 M	2.27E-10 M	5.06E-07 M
MDA	5.14E-05 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	1.20E-04 M
4-AFD	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M
2-AFD	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M	> 1E-04 M

Thyroid assay

11.5 CS2 – A-Parts

11.5.1 General human health

11.5.1.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

	Concentration (µg/mL)	0	0,3	0,8	2	5	13	32	80	200
AP1	Median	98,4	99,7	99,5	99,1	103,1	111,2	99,1	0,6	9,4
	Interquartile range	4,3	11,0	3,2	9,4	47,8	47,4	46,1	10,6	19,7
AP2	Median	98,4	95,2	95,8	96,7	97,0	94,9	81,8	1,3	5,8
	Interquartile range	4,3	3,5	4,9	9,3	15,6	6,5	15,8	1,6	7,1
AP3	Median	99,9	99,4	101,1	99,8	107,0	136,4	94,4	0,7	7,2
	Interquartile range	6,5	12,7	9,0	13,6	40,2	46,7	29,6	2,9	18,0
AP4	Median	99,9	98,3	98,1	98,4	100,4	99,2	76,7	-0,6	0,7
	Interquartile range	6,5	4,9	3,0	3,3	6,9	16,3	21,1	0,8	1,0
AP-CL	Median	100,2	98,6	100,8	98,9	100,8	102,3	96,4	0,1	0,5
	Interquartile range	6,7	3,4	7,6	8,6	23,3	30,5	23,5	0,9	0,6

On Caco-2 cells

	Concentration (µg/mL)	0	0,3	0,8	2	5	13	32	80	200
AP1	Median	98,5	103,9	101,6	99,7	97,1	94,3	77,4	0,3	1,5
	Interquartile range	4,4	12,9	4,8	11,0	10,6	10,9	19,8	2,0	1,7
AP2	Median	98,5	99,0	95,5	97,9	90,8	93,3	84,4	11,8	1,5
	Interquartile range	4,4	6,3	6,8	5,8	8,6	4,8	11,6	12,0	0,3
AP3	Median	98,7	102,8	99,9	101,7	96,3	92,3	79,4	6,6	2,4
	Interquartile range	6,2	8,2	10,3	8,0	4,6	10,9	14,7	1,8	4,1
AP4	Median	98,7	97,3	97,9	98,4	94,7	92,0	79,8	1,3	0,3
	Interquartile range	6,2	4,2	6,7	5,6	3,7	5,5	10,1	2,1	0,4
AP-CL	Median	98,3	95,9	98,7	97,3	93,5	94,0	86,2	5,5	0,1
	Interquartile range	7,2	4,2	2,5	4,9	10,8	16,3	19,2	1,5	0,2

LDH Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

	Concentration (µg/mL)	0	0,3	0,8	2	5	13	32	80	200
AP1	Median	100,0	99,5	100,0	99,9	99,7	98,8	89,6	40,1	27,6
	Interquartile range	0,8	0,8	0,6	1,8	2,5	1,9	5,0	12,6	24,1
AP2	Median	100,0	99,7	100,1	100,1	98,7	98,9	94,9	72,0	26,0
	Interquartile range	0,8	0,4	1,4	1,4	2,0	2,1	1,9	5,7	18,3
AP3	Median	100,0	99,8	99,7	99,5	99,3	99,8	90,5	52,6	20,5
	Interquartile range	0,8	1,4	0,9	1,3	2,2	2,7	7,6	9,4	17,1
AP4	Median	100,0	99,6	99,7	99,4	99,7	99,1	93,0	50,7	27,1
	Interquartile range	0,8	1,0	1,0	1,4	2,2	1,2	3,9	10,3	24,9

	Concentration (µg/mL)	0	0,3	0,8	2	5	13	32	80	200
AP-CL	Median	99,9	99,9	100,0	100,5	100,1	100,1	95,4	52,8	18,2
	Interquartile range	0,4	0,9	1,4	0,9	2,5	1,1	4,0	18,1	15,8

On Caco-2 cells

	Concentration (µg/mL)	0	0,3	0,8	2	5	13	32	80	200
AP1	Median	100,5	102,5	99,5	99,0	98,3	95,2	94,0	50,7	27,9
	Interquartile range	2,8	3,0	4,4	3,7	7,1	4,5	6,2	30,2	13,4
AP2	Median	100,5	102,7	99,6	100,6	102,6	99,5	97,2	82,1	33,9
	Interquartile range	2,8	3,4	3,0	3,6	3,8	4,8	3,1	5,5	9,9
AP3	Median	100,2	101,5	99,5	101,1	101,7	101,1	96,1	85,0	39,8
	Interquartile range	2,5	2,1	3,2	6,3	3,7	3,3	4,6	4,2	4,0
AP4	Median	100,2	101,7	98,9	103,0	100,4	102,7	99,5	79,9	32,2
	Interquartile range	2,5	2,2	4,0	2,9	1,9	2,6	2,0	5,5	13,3
AP-CL	Median	100,3	101,7	100,5	101,0	101,1	101,6	100,2	88,4	31,6
	Interquartile range	3,1	3,6	1,5	3,0	3,5	4,1	3,7	5,3	4,0

11.5.1.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay – results in % of viability compared to the delta (positive control - solvent control)

On HaCaT cells

	Solvent control	Neg. Ctrl	AP1	AP2	AP3	AP4	AP-CL	Pos. Ctrl
Concentration (µg/mL)	-	-	33	33	33	33	33	-
Median	0,23	1,38	16,71	10,79	6,20	9,11	7,00	98,35
Interquartile range	9,35	8,34	9,98	7,79	5,85	8,74	13,11	19,33

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent control	Neg. Ctrl	AP1	AP2	AP3	AP4	AP-CL	Pos. Ctrl
Concentration (µg/mL)	-	-	33	33	33	33	33	-
Median	1,14	0,03	12,38	10,18	6,80	11,31	11,87	96,05
Interquartile range	8,44	8,07	17,29	17,32	23,43	7,00	7,90	21,60

11.5.1.3 Epigenetic DNA modifications quantified by HPLC-MS/MS – results in % of cytosine methylation

On Caco-2 cells

	Solvent Ctrl for Ctrl+	Positive control	Solvent control	AP1	AP2	AP3	AP4	AP-CL
Concentration (µg/mL)	-	-	20	20	20	20	20	-
Median	3,96	2,11	3,99	4,1	4,085	4,08	4,03	4,07
Interquartile range	0,2	0,1	0,1	0,4	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1

11.5.2 Genotoxicity

53BP1 assay – results in number of foci per cell

On HaCaT cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,32	0,16	100,4	3,1
Negative control	1,51	0,25	97,7	30,1
Etoposide, 25 µM	19,72	5,37	43,1	13,7
Etoposide, 50 µM	20,62	4,47	39,5	5,8
Etoposide, 100 µM	22,81	7,14	35,1	9,7
AP1, 20µg/mL	9,85	3,02	75,5	28,5
AP2, 20µg/mL	6,75	4,34	86,5	22,2
AP3, 20µg/mL	7,00	3,08	82,9	17,2
AP4, 20µg/mL	8,65	3,79	78,7	11,4
AP-CL, 20µg/mL	9,28	5,06	77,4	22,1

On Caco-2 cells

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	3,38	0,30	100,2	4,5
Negative control	3,22	0,67	101,8	7,9
Etoposide, 6.25 µM	16,83	5,51	79,5	16,1
Etoposide, 12.5 µM	22,42	6,71	74,4	13,1
Etoposide, 25 µM	20,88	5,62	70,6	15,2
AP1, 20µg/mL	11,41	6,70	78,6	8,9
AP2, 20µg/mL	9,24	3,68	89,5	19,4
AP3, 20µg/mL	9,13	4,43	89,5	35,0
AP4, 20µg/mL	8,34	5,65	82,5	29,4
AP-CL, 20µg/mL	9,52	1,24	90,5	9,9

Comet assay – results in % of tail intensity

On HaCaT cells

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,46	1,41
Negative control	1,73	2,77
H ₂ O ₂ control	47,86	14,56
MMS 2,2 µg/mL	19,37	6,36
MMS 3,3 µg/mL	28,97	13,76
AP1, 20µg/mL	1,65	1,89
AP2, 20µg/mL	0,82	1,11

On Caco-2 cells

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	0,90	0,69
Negative control	1,04	1,14
H ₂ O ₂ control	37,30	19,53
MMS 2,2 µg/mL	21,30	3,38
MMS 3,3 µg/mL	27,35	5,45
AP1, 20µg/mL	2,56	2,40
AP2, 20µg/mL	1,72	0,96

	Median	Interquartile range
AP3, 20µg/mL	0,95	0,76
AP4, 20µg/mL	1,00	1,25
AP-CL, 20µg/mL	1,40	0,91

	Median	Interquartile range
AP3, 20µg/mL	1,21	1,97
AP4, 20µg/mL	2,23	2,50
AP-CL, 20µg/mL	0,61	0,98

11.5.3 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

On U2OS CALUX[®] cells

	Disruption potential on ER α		Disruption potential on AR	
	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)	Agonist (EC ₅₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)
Reference control	1,93E-06 µg/mL	4,97E-03 µg/mL	7,41E-05 µg/mL	1,88E-01 µg/mL
All A-Parts	> 5 µg/mL	> 5 µg/mL	> 5 µg/mL	> 5 µg/mL

Thyroid assay

11.6 CS2 – Leachates from composites

11.6.1 General human health

11.6.1.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

	Concentration (% of dilution in culture medium)	0	0,05	0,1	0,2
Leach-SP1	Median	99,2	96,9	96,6	103,3
	Interquartile range	14,2	10,7	18,5	8,4
Leach-SP2	Median	99,2	104,1	103,9	133,2
	Interquartile range	14,2	13,9	2,4	47,3
Leach-SP3	Median	99,2	119,4	116,6	128,7
	Interquartile range	14,2	27,8	50,0	56,2
Leach-SP4	Median	99,9	84,7	94,1	122,5
	Interquartile range	29,1	35,7	36,6	66,8
Leach-TCPP	Median	99,9	87,0	104,7	98,4
	Interquartile range	29,1	36,8	45,1	54,6

On Caco-2 cells

	Concentration (% of dilution in culture medium)	0	0,5	1	2
Leach-SP1	Median	98,6	96,7	96,7	100,0
	Interquartile range	14,8	7,9	14,8	12,0

	Concentration (% of dilution in culture medium)	0	0,5	1	2
Leach-SP2	Median	98,6	113,3	103,1	103,8
	Interquartile range	14,8	31,4	6,3	14,5
Leach-SP3	Median	98,6	103,4	107,1	106,5
	Interquartile range	14,8	11,9	9,2	8,6
Leach-SP4	Median	99,0	97,7	96,0	100,0
	Interquartile range	10,5	16,3	25,2	7,6
Leach-TCPP	Median	99,0	100,8	90,9	53,7
	Interquartile range	10,5	13,9	13,1	7,5

LDH Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

	Concentration (% of dilution in culture medium)	0	0,05	0,1	0,2
Leach-SP1	Median	99,3	101,3	102,1	101,1
	Interquartile range	4,7	3,0	3,1	3,8
Leach-SP2	Median	99,3	100,0	100,0	97,2
	Interquartile range	4,7	4,0	2,1	3,5
Leach-SP3	Median	99,3	98,3	98,6	99,3
	Interquartile range	4,7	3,4	3,6	1,3
Leach-SP4	Median	99,5	102,1	103,3	97,5
	Interquartile range	3,5	2,7	4,4	7,8
Leach-TCPP	Median	99,5	100,4	100,2	99,9
	Interquartile range	3,5	2,2	6,5	11,4

On Caco-2 cells

	Concentration (% of dilution in culture medium)	0	0,5	1	2
Leach-SP1	Median	99,4	99,0	99,5	98,4
	Interquartile range	4,1	16,3	12,4	12,3
Leach-SP2	Median	99,4	94,1	96,3	102,1
	Interquartile range	4,1	15,4	13,1	11,3
Leach-SP3	Median	99,4	99,9	105,0	97,3
	Interquartile range	4,1	11,8	14,2	7,3
Leach-SP4	Median	99,9	100,5	99,0	95,6
	Interquartile range	4,1	6,6	1,7	3,9
Leach-TCPP	Median	99,9	102,2	102,9	98,2
	Interquartile range	4,1	6,9	5,3	7,4

11.6.1.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay – results in % of viability compared to the delta (positive control - solvent control)

On HaCaT cells, leachates at 0.2% dilution in culture medium

	Solvent control	Neg. Ctrl	Leach-SP1	Leach-SP2	Leach-SP3	Leach-SP4	Leach-TCPP	Pos. Ctrl
Median	-0,90	-5,41	3,28	-4,68	0,00	-0,44	0,11	98,46
Interquartile range	16,22	10,87	16,75	10,99	16,77	9,69	9,22	13,87

On Caco-2 cells, leachates at 2% dilution in culture medium

	Solvent control	Neg. Ctrl	Leach-SP1	Leach-SP2	Leach-SP3	Leach-SP4	Leach-TCPP	Pos. Ctrl
Median	-0,43	12,28	10,05	27,21	16,35	13,36	21,21	98,60
Interquartile range	33,76	42,51	48,45	60,13	64,19	51,57	23,70	30,70

11.6.2 Genotoxicity

53BP1 assay – results in number of foci per cell

On HaCaT cells, leachates at 0.2% dilution

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,2	0,44	99,9	2,0
Negative control	1,11	0,68	94,0	20,5
Etoposide, 25 µM	30,92	7,42	36,1	1,2
Etoposide, 50 µM	27,22	4,42	27,9	2,3
Etoposide, 100 µM	25,13	4,81	20,9	3,0
Leach-SP1	1,29	0,46	107,2	9,5
Leach-SP2	1,18	0,39	102,6	7,8
Leach-SP3	1,22	0,42	104,3	7,2
Leach-SP4	1,28	0,37	104,8	7,2
Leach-TCPP	1,24	0,27	102,5	10,0

On Caco-2 cells, leachates at 2% dilution

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,9	0,21	98,9	4,1
Negative control	1,87	0,18	132,5	29,9
Etoposide, 6.25 µM	14,43	6,09	97,6	61,9
Etoposide, 12.5 µM	17,68	7,02	89,4	49,2
Etoposide, 25 µM	19,77	4,85	79,5	48,2
Leach-SP1	2,26	0,15	116,3	76,4
Leach-SP2	2,32	0,31	112,2	52,7
Leach-SP3	2,73	0,24	127,9	53,3
Leach-SP4	2,53	0,12	144,2	114,3
Leach-TCPP	2,2	0,16	108,4	52,6

Comet assay – results in % of tail intensity

On HaCaT cells, leachates at 0.2% dilution

On Caco-2 cells, leachates at 2% dilution

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,506	0,9027
Negative control	1,09	1,1096
H ₂ O ₂ control	48,21	7,71
MMS 20 µM	21,27	10,05
MMS 30 µM	42,17	10,56
Leach-SP1	0,4763	0,4535
Leach-SP2	0,4955	0,6596
Leach-SP3	0,4965	1,066
Leach-SP4	0,294	0,8836
Leach-TCPP	0,8725	1,3773

	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,903	2,1864
Negative control	1,617	0,9759
H ₂ O ₂ control	39,17	6,98
MMS 20 µM	24,86	23,92
MMS 30 µM	35,27	28,46
Leach-SP1	0,5236	0,9044
Leach-SP2	0,4781	0,5233
Leach-SP3	0,4258	1,0667
Leach-SP4	0,6177	1,8709
Leach-TCPP	0,8329	1,1572

11.6.3 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

On U2OS CALUX[®] cells, leachates tested up to 1% dilution in culture medium

	Disruption potential on ER α		Disruption potential on AR	
	Agonist (EC ₅₀ and EC ₁₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)	Agonist (EC ₅₀ and EC ₁₀)	Antagonist (IC ₅₀)
Reference control	EC ₅₀ : 1.03E-11 M EC ₁₀ : 2.05E-12 M	IC ₅₀ : 1,02E-08 M	EC ₅₀ : 12.22E-10 M EC ₁₀ : 6.55E-11 M	IC ₅₀ : 5.06E-07 M

Leach-SP1	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%
Leach-SP2	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%
Leach-SP3	EC ₁₀ : 3.99E-01 %	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%
Leach-SP4	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%
Leach-TCPP	EC ₁₀ : 3.96E-01 %	EC ₁₀ > 1%	EC ₁₀ > 1%	IC ₁₀ : 1.26E-01 %

Thyroid assay

11.7 CS3 – Migration samples

11.7.1 General human health

11.7.1.1 Cytotoxicity

WST-1 Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

Leachate	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent B control	1 %	98,2	22,6
PO/PA/compat 11 B	1 %	116,2	20,2
PE/compat/PA 65 B	1 %	119,8	18,4

Leachate	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
PE/EVOH 129 B	1 %	136,3	20,8
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	1 %	130,1	30,0
Solvent Ethanol 95% control	0.2%	97,9	9,1
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	0.2%	99,5	10,9
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	0.2%	105,0	5,5
PE/EVOH 129 E95	0.2%	104,7	11,9
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	0.2%	103,0	6,0

On Caco-2 cells

Leachate	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent B control	1 %	97,06	29,14
PO/PA/compat 11 B	1 %	105,9	13,09
PE/compat/PA 65 B	1 %	104,7	17,77
PE/EVOH 129 B	1 %	109,4	12,7
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	1 %	110,8	16,7
Solvent Ethanol 95% control	2%	97,6	10,1
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	2%	87,5	13,0
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	2%	100,3	20,4
PE/EVOH 129 E95	2%	104,7	22,7
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	2%	96,4	15,4

LDH Cytotoxicity assay – results in % of viability compared to the solvent control

On HaCaT cells

Leachate	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent B control	1 %	100,1	2,28
PO/PA/compat 11 B	1 %	101,1	2,2
PE/compat/PA 65 B	1 %	102,4	6,87
PE/EVOH 129 B	1 %	101,4	5,74
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	1 %	102,3	3,7
Solvent Ethanol 95% control	0.2%	100,0	2,2
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	0.2%	97,5	3,1
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	0.2%	100,4	4,1
PE/EVOH 129 E95	0.2%	102,5	7,3
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	0.2%	98,5	10,2

On Caco-2 cells

Leachate	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent B control	1 %	99,86	9,92
PO/PA/compat 11 B	1 %	95,12	14,74
PE/compat/PA 65 B	1 %	91,77	20,61
PE/EVOH 129 B	1 %	99,33	13,11
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	1 %	94,87	11,51
Solvent Ethanol 95% control	2%	99,6	6,5
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	2%	100,3	5,7
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	2%	97,7	9,2
PE/EVOH 129 E95	2%	96,7	14,2

Leachate	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	2%	88,8	9,5

11.7.1.2 Oxidative stress

CM-H₂DCFDA assay – results in % of viability compared to the delta (positive control - solvent control)

On HaCaT cells

Leachates in acetic acid	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent B control	1 %	-0,14	7,61
Negative control	-	-0,27	24,00
PO/PA/compat 11 B	1 %	4,40	20,25
PE/compat/PA 65 B	1 %	1,43	10,09
PE/EVOH 129 B	1 %	9,33	33,08
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	1 %	-3,06	25,89
Positive control	-	94,97	31,81
Leachates in Ethanol	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
Ethanol Solvent control	0.2 %	2,65	20,77
Negative control	-	0,86	20,69
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	0.2 %	6,37	25,18
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	0.2 %	2,32	25,81
PE/EVOH 129 E95	0.2 %	-3,90	19,66
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	0.2 %	2,85	16,38
Positive control	-	101,90	18,05

On Caco-2 cells

Leachates in acetic acid	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent B control	1 %	-6,72	24,72
Negative control	-	-8,01	33,72
PO/PA/compat 11 B	1 %	7,43	37,65
PE/compat/PA 65 B	1 %	4,23	25,46
PE/EVOH 129 B	1 %	0,55	15,22
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	1 %	8,07	19,56
Positive control	-	98,39	32,21
Leachates in Ethanol	dilution in culture medium	Median	Interquartile range
Ethanol Solvent control	2 %	-1,96	35,35
Negative control	-	-20,62	49,63
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	2 %	9,29	30,71
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	2 %	-2,81	35,05
PE/EVOH 129 E95	2 %	10,70	64,36
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	2 %	27,49	80,72
Positive control	-	101,40	28,20

11.7.2 Genotoxicity

53BP1 assay – results in number of foci per cell

On HaCaT cells

Leachates B at 1% dilution in culture medium

Leachates E95 at 0.2% dilution

	number of foci per cell		viability	
Leachates in acetic acid	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,1	0,30	99,1	3,2
Negative control	1,1	0,40	105,1	5,0
Etoposide, 25 µM	19,21	11,05	40,7	4,0
Etoposide, 50 µM	16,93	9,79	33,9	4,2
Etoposide, 100 µM	18,56	7,96	23,5	3,0
PO/PA/compat 11 B	1,07	0,21	99,0	10,5
PE/compat/PA 65 B	1,12	0,17	100,1	7,0
PE/EVOH 129 B	1,11	0,21	98,8	5,4
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	1,06	0,20	99,5	5,7
Leachates in ethanol	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,20	0,44	99,9	2,0
Negative control	1,11	0,68	94,0	20,5
Etoposide, 25 µM	30,92	7,42	36,1	1,2
Etoposide, 50 µM	27,22	4,42	27,9	2,3
Etoposide, 100 µM	25,13	4,81	20,9	3,0
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	1,16	0,44	108,9	6,6
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	1,48	0,48	106,9	7,3
PE/EVOH 129 E95	1,46	0,41	106,6	7,7
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	1,41	0,42	107,8	8,5

On Caco-2 cells

Leachates B at 1% dilution in culture medium

Leachates E95 at 2% dilution

	number of foci per cell		viability	
Leachates in acetic acid	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,88	0,81	99,9	7,0
Negative control	1,88	0,62	106,8	15,6
Etoposide, 6.25 µM	12,83	8,40	70,5	7,8
Etoposide, 12.5 µM	15,48	9,31	67,4	9,9
Etoposide, 25 µM	16,99	11,03	64,8	7,3
PO/PA/compat 11 B	2,11	0,37	115,1	13,5
PE/compat/PA 65 B	1,98	0,42	114,8	14,3
PE/EVOH 129 B	1,84	0,45	114,8	15,8
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	1,94	0,47	108,6	12,2

	number of foci per cell		viability	
	Median	Interquartile range	Median	Interquartile range
Leachates in acetic acid				
Leachates in ethanol				
Solvent control	1,93	0,28	100,9	14,1
Negative control	1,87	0,18	149,0	91,3
Etoposide, 6.25 µM	14,43	6,09	109,8	128,5
Etoposide, 12.5 µM	17,68	7,02	100,6	106,4
Etoposide, 25 µM	19,77	4,85	89,4	102,7
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	2,33	0,25	165,4	138,7
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	2,28	0,16	153,7	184,2
PE/EVOH 129 E95	2,17	0,16	155,9	168,2
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	2,125	0,123	150,2	190,4

Comet assay – results in % of tail intensity

On HaCaT cells

On Caco-2 cells

Leachates B at 1% dilution in culture medium

Leachates B at 1% dilution in culture medium

Leachates E95 at 0.2% dilution

Leachates E95 at 2% dilution

Leachates in acetic acid	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,50	1,95
Negative control	1,09	1,11
H ₂ O ₂ control	48,21	7,71
MMS 20 µM	21,27	10,05
MMS 30 µM	42,17	10,56
PO/PA/compat 11 B	0,67	0,90
PE/compat/PA 65 B	0,26	0,45
PE/EVOH 129 B	0,45	0,72
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	0,47	0,50
Leachates in Ethanol	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,51	0,90
Negative control	1,09	1,11
H ₂ O ₂ control	48,21	7,71
MMS 20 µM	21,27	10,05
MMS 30 µM	42,17	10,56
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	0,27	0,37
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	0,59	0,59
PE/EVOH 129 E95	0,47	0,28
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	0,58	0,42

Leachates in acetic acid	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,23	1,20
Negative control	1,62	0,98
H ₂ O ₂ control	39,17	6,98
MMS 20 µM	24,86	23,92
MMS 30 µM	35,27	28,46
PO/PA/compat 11 B	0,66	0,57
PE/compat/PA 65 B	0,93	0,76
PE/EVOH 129 B	0,82	0,97
PE/compat/EVOH 129 B	0,81	0,83
Leachates in Ethanol	Median	Interquartile range
Solvent control	1,47	1,67
Negative control	1,62	0,98
H ₂ O ₂ control	39,17	6,98
MMS 20 µM	24,86	23,92
MMS 30 µM	35,27	28,46
PO/PA/compat 11 E95	0,46	0,90
PE/compat/PA 65 E95	0,54	0,91
PE/EVOH 129 E95	0,41	0,39
PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95	0,38	0,56

11.7.3 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disruption assay on ER α and AR

Thyroid assay